

```

clear; clc; close all;

%% 1) Add code paths
% Main code directory (contains your main scripts)
mainCodeDir = 'C:\Users\Lu\Desktop\Fig_Code\ChAT_Labeling';
% Function directory (stores custom functions)
funcCodeDir = 'C:\Users\Lu\Desktop\Fig_Code\Function';

% Add directories to MATLAB search path
if isfolder(mainCodeDir)
    addpath(genpath(mainCodeDir));
    fprintf('Added main code path: %s\n', mainCodeDir);
else
    warning('Main code directory not found: %s', mainCodeDir);
end

if isfolder(funcCodeDir)
    addpath(genpath(funcCodeDir));
    fprintf('Added function path: %s\n', funcCodeDir);
else
    warning('Function code directory not found: %s', funcCodeDir);
end

%% 2) Select data folder (as datapath)
% Set the initial browse location to the main code directory for convenience
startDir = mainCodeDir;
if ~isfolder(startDir)
    % If the main code directory does not exist, fall back to Desktop or C:\
    fallback1 = 'C:\Users\Lu\Desktop';
    fallback2 = 'C:\';
    if isfolder(fallback1)
        startDir = fallback1;
    else
        startDir = fallback2;
    end
end

datapath = uigetdir(startDir, 'Please select the data folder (this folder will be used as
datapath)');
if isequal(datapath, 0)
    error('No folder selected. Program terminated.');
```

```

end

%% 3) Retrieve data files
% Recursively search subfolders: true/false
useRecursive = false;

if useRecursive && ~verLessThan('matlab','9.1') % R2016b+ supports ** wildcard
    filePatternNex5 = fullfile(datapath, '**', '*.nex5');
    filePatternNex = fullfile(datapath, '**', '*.nex');
    filesNex5 = dir(filePatternNex5);
    filesNex = dir(filePatternNex);
else
    filesNex5 = dir(fullfile(datapath, '*.nex5'));
    filesNex = dir(fullfile(datapath, '*.nex'));
end

filename = [filesNex5; filesNex]; % struct array
nFiles = numel(filename);
fprintf('Found %d files (.nex5 + .nex).\n', nFiles);

```

```

if nFiles == 0
    warning('No .nex/.nex5 files found in %s.', datapath);
end

%% 4) Basic check and preview
if nFiles > 0
    % Remove hidden/system files
    isHidden = startsWith({filename.name}', '.');
    filename = filename(~isHidden);
    nFiles = numel(filename);

    % Sort by name (you can switch to date: [~,ix]=sort([filename.datenum]));
    [~, ix] = sort(lower({filename.name}));
    filename = filename(ix);

    % Print the first few entries
    nPreview = min(10, nFiles);
    fprintf('Preview first %d files:\n', nPreview);
    for i = 1:nPreview
        fprintf('  [%3d] %s\n', i, fullfile(filename(i).folder, filename(i).name));
    end
end

%% 5) stim_info reading
recursive = false; % Set to false if recursion is not needed
stim_info = batch_get_stim_info(datapath, recursive);

%% 6) Data selection
% Getting all the spike data into several groups
chnl = {...
    'region1', 1:16;
    'region2', 33:48
};

% Create a list dialog box for user to select a channel
channelOptions = {'1: region1', '2: region2'};
[indx, tf] = listdlg('PromptString', 'Select a channel:',...
    'SelectionMode', 'single',...
    'ListString', channelOptions,...
    'ListSize', [200, 100]); % Adjust ListSize as needed

% Check if the user made a selection
if ~tf
    error('No channel selected. Exiting the program.');
```

```

end

% Use the selected index directly as ch
ch = indx;

% Define the results path based on the selected channel
resultsPath = fullfile(datapath, chnl{ch, 1}); % Use fullfile for OS-independent paths
if ~exist(resultsPath, 'dir')
    mkdir(resultsPath);
end

%% Reading data
% Define data access keys and default parameters for data extraction
dataKey = {'events', 'spike', 'waveform'}; % Valid selections: 'events', 'spike',
'waveform', 'AI'
```

```

% Setup parameters for extracting neural LFP data
paramsExtr = struct(...
    'chnl', {chnl},... % Channel configuration
    'regionToLoad', {chnl(ch, 1)},... % Brain region to import based on
channel selection
    'filPerChl', 2,... % Number of filaments per channel
(e.g., stereotrode: 2)
    'exEvent', [],... % External event info, initially
empty
    'eventsFrom', {'nex'},...
    'getEvents', {'start feeding', 'stop feeding', 'go in feeding zone', 'go out feeding
zone'},... % Event types to extract
    'bestNlfp', 5,... % Optimal number of local field
potentials
    'processEvents', 'null'... % Default method for processing
events
);

% Extract neural LFP data using specified filename, data keys, and parameters
[groupNeu, ~] = extractNeuLFP(filename, dataKey, paramsExtr);

% Store original group neural data
%
% Get the first row (cell array)
data = {groupNeu.TrialData.neuronID};

% Step 2: Filter out entries containing 'U'
% Use cellfun and contains to check whether each string contains 'U' (case-insensitive)
mask = cellfun(@(s) ~contains(s, 'U', 'IgnoreCase', true), data);

% Simplify data
groupNeu.TrialData = groupNeu.TrialData(mask);

groupNeu_original = groupNeu;

%% Waveform
% Basic parameters
fs = 40000;
params = struct('dtThr', 0.0002, 'xcThr', 0.5, 'ratioZThr', 3);

assert(isfield(groupNeu, 'TrialData'), 'groupNeu.TrialData does not exist');

origTD = groupNeu.TrialData;
numUnits = numel(origTD);

% In the main script, initialize processed as a placeholder, then initialize by the first
template
processed = []; % Placeholder empty array, not preallocating as struct([])
outIdx = 0;
baseFields = {}; % List of baseline field names

for k = 1:numUnits
    TD = origTD(k);

    % === New: Build stereotrode waveform matrix W from TD (columns are events, size 112xm)
    ===
    if ~isfield(TD, 'Allwaveform') || isempty(TD.Allwaveform)
        warning('Unit %d: missing Allwaveform, skipping.', k);
        continue;
    end
end

```

```

A = TD.Allwaveform;
sz = size(A);
W = [];

% Support both numeric matrix and cell array storage
if isnumeric(A)
    % Case 1: A is numeric matrix
    if size(A,1) == 112
        W = A; % [112×m]
    elseif size(A,2) == 112
        W = A.'; % [112×m]
    elseif size(A,1) == 56 || size(A,2) == 56
        % Only single filament 56 samples; cannot run stereotrode pipeline directly
        warning('Unit %d: Allwaveform has 56 samples (single filament). Need two
filaments merged to 112; skipping.', k);
        continue;
    else
        warning('Unit %d: unsupported Allwaveform size [%d×%d], skipping.', k, sz(1),
sz(2));
        continue;
    end
elseif iscell(A)
    % Case 2: A is a cell array, each element is one waveform
    % Expect each element to be 112×1 or 1×112
    m = numel(A);
    if m == 0
        warning('Unit %d: Allwaveform is an empty cell, skipping.', k);
        continue;
    end
    % Infer single waveform length
    w0 = A{1};
    if isempty(w0)
        warning('Unit %d: first waveform is empty, skipping.', k);
        continue;
    end
    if isrow(w0), w0 = w0.'; end
    S = size(w0,1);
    if S ~= 112
        if S == 56
            warning('Unit %d: waveforms in cell have 56 samples (single filament). Need
merging, skipping.', k);
            continue;
        else
            warning('Unit %d: waveform length in cell is %d (not 112), skipping.', k,
S);
            continue;
        end
    end
    W = zeros(112, m);
    for j = 1:m
        wj = A{j};
        if isrow(wj), wj = wj.'; end
        if size(wj,1) ~= 112
            error('Unit %d: waveform #%d length mismatch (expected 112, got %d).', k,
j, size(wj,1));
        end
        W(:, j) = wj;
    end
else
    warning('Unit %d: unsupported Allwaveform type %s, skipping.', k, class(A));

```

```

        continue;
    end
    % === W constructed ===

    % Stereotrode processing and splitting
    [templates, eventInfo, splitIdx] = processStereotrodeUnit(W, fs, params);
    [TD_A, TD_B] = reshapeGroupAfterSplit(TD, splitIdx, eventInfo, templates);

    % First time: establish the template field set
    if outIdx == 0
        baseFields = fieldnames(TD_A)';
        processed = repmat(cell2struct(cell(size(baseFields)), baseFields, 2), 0, 1);
    end

    % Write A
    outIdx = outIdx + 1;
    processed(outIdx) = ensureStructFields(TD_A, baseFields);

    % Write B (if any)
    if ~isempty(splitIdx.B)
        outIdx = outIdx + 1;
        processed(outIdx) = ensureStructFields(TD_B, baseFields);
    end
end

groupNeu.TrialData = processed;
fprintf('Original units: %d -> New units: %d\n', numUnits, numel(groupNeu.TrialData));

%% Data
% Step1: Filter trials with spike count >= 1000
spikeCounts = arrayfun(@(x) size(x.spike, 1), groupNeu.TrialData);
validTrials = spikeCounts >= 1000;
groupNeu.TrialData = groupNeu.TrialData(validTrials);

%% Integrate stim_info into Neu.TrialData
groupNeu_new = groupNeu;
trial_data = groupNeu_new.TrialData;
num_records = numel(trial_data);
% ----- Options -----
ignoreCase = true; % Case-insensitive matching
trimQuotes = true; % Remove quotes in record
verboseLog = true;

% ----- Build mapping: basename -> index -----
stim_map = containers.Map();
dup_warned = containers.Map('KeyType','char','ValueType','logical'); % deduplicate warning
tracker
for k = 1:numel(stim_info)
    if ~isfield(stim_info(k),'filename') || isempty(stim_info(k).filename)
        continue;
    end
    [~, bn, ~] = fileparts(stim_info(k).filename);
    key = bn;
    if ignoreCase, key = lower(key); end
    if isKey(stim_map, key) && ~isKey(dup_warned, key)
        warning('Duplicate basename detected: %. Later entry will overwrite earlier one.',
bn);
        dup_warned(key) = true;
    end
    stim_map(key) = k;
    if verboseLog

```

```

        fprintf(' %3d -> %s\n', k, bn);
    end
end

% ----- Empty template (aligned with new struct fields) -----
empty_stim = struct( ...
    'matched',      false, ...
    'filename',     '', ...
    'channelName',  '', ...
    't_on',         [], ...
    't_off',        [], ...
    'delta_t',      [], ...
    'error_message', 'No matching stim file found', ...
    'trial_record', '', ...
    'trial_index',  [] );

% ----- Perform matching -----
matched = 0;
for i = 1:num_records
    rec = trial_data(i).record;

    % Normalize to string and clean
    if isstring(rec) || ischar(rec)
        rec = char(rec);
    elseif isnumeric(rec)
        rec = char(string(rec));
    else
        rec = char(string(rec)); % best effort to cast to char
    end
    rec = strtrim(rec);
    if trimQuotes
        rec = strrep(rec, '''', '');
        rec = strrep(rec, '"', '');
    end
    key = rec;
    if ignoreCase, key = lower(key); end

    if isKey(stim_map, key)
        idx = stim_map(key);
        st = stim_info(idx); % use your struct directly
        % Add match flag and trace info
        st.matched      = true;
        st.trial_record = rec;
        st.trial_index  = i;

        groupNeu_new.TrialData(i).stim = st;
        matched = matched + 1;

        if verboseLog
            fprintf('✓ Match: %s <-> %s\n', rec, st.filename);
        end
    else
        st = empty_stim;
        st.trial_record = rec;
        st.trial_index  = i;
        groupNeu_new.TrialData(i).stim = st;

        if verboseLog
            fprintf('✗ No match: %s\n', rec);
        end
    end
end

```

```

end

%% Adjustment
% ===== Parameters =====
linkY = true;           % Link Y axes
titlePrefix = 'Preview Mean Waveforms';
waveformField = 'meanWaveform_good'; % Waveform field to use
% =====

% Select data source
useSplit = exist('groupNeu_new','var')==1;
if useSplit
    S = groupNeu_new;
    TD = S.TrialData;
    srcName = 'groupNeu_new';
else
    assert(exist('groupNeu','var')==1, 'groupNeu or groupNeu_new not found');
    S = groupNeu;
    TD = S.TrialData;
    srcName = 'groupNeu';
end

N = numel(TD);
assert(N>0, 'TrialData is empty');

% First preview (using meanWaveform_good)
[axList, shownMask] = preview_meanwaveforms(TD, titlePrefix, srcName, linkY);

% Interactive input for indices to delete
prompt = sprintf('Enter indices to delete (space-separated, e.g., 2 5 9; empty to skip): ');
in = input(prompt, 's');
if isempty(strtrim(in))
    removeIdx = [];
else
    removeIdx = str2double(strsplit(strtrim(in)));
    removeIdx = removeIdx(~isnan(removeIdx));
end

% Validate and deduplicate
removeIdx = unique(removeIdx);
removeIdx = removeIdx(removeIdx>=1 & removeIdx<=N);
if isempty(removeIdx)
    fprintf('No items selected for deletion. Data unchanged.\n');
    outStruct = S; % Output equals input
    return;
end

fprintf('Indices to remove: %s\n', mat2str(removeIdx));

% Optionally highlight subplots to be removed
try
    for ii = 1:numel(removeIdx)
        idx = removeIdx(ii);
        if isgraphics(axList(idx))
            axes(axList(idx));
            yl = ylim; xl = xlim;
            patch('XData',[xl(1) xl(2) xl(2) xl(1)], ...
                'YData',[yl(1) yl(1) yl(2) yl(2)], ...
                'FaceColor',[1 0 0], 'FaceAlpha',0.05, 'EdgeColor','none');
            title(axList(idx).Title.String + " [TO REMOVE]", 'Color',[0.6 0 0]);
        end
    end
end

```

```

    end
    drawnow;
catch
end

% Second confirmation
confirm = input('Confirm deletion of these entries? Enter y to confirm, n to cancel [y/n]:', 's');
if isempty(confirm) || lower(confirm(1)) ~= 'y'
    fprintf('Deletion cancelled. Data unchanged.\n');
    outStruct = S;
    return;
end

% Perform deletion
keepMask = true(1, N);
keepMask(removeIdx) = false;
TD_new = TD(keepMask);

% Write back to output struct
outStruct = S;
outStruct.TrialData = TD_new;

% Also write back to corresponding variable names (for convenience)
if useSplit
    groupNeu_new = outStruct;
    assignin('base', 'groupNeu_new', outStruct);
    fprintf('Done: removed %d from %s, remaining %d.\n', numel(removeIdx), srcName, numel(TD_new));
else
    groupNeu = outStruct;
    assignin('base', 'groupNeu', outStruct);
    fprintf('Done: removed %d from %s, remaining %d.\n', numel(removeIdx), srcName, numel(TD_new));
end

% Preview again after deletion
repeat = input('Preview the current result again? [y/n]: ', 's');
if ~isempty(repeat) && lower(repeat(1)) == 'y'
    preview_meanwaveforms(outStruct.TrialData, titlePrefix+" (after removal)", srcName, linkY);
end

%% Output
Data = outStruct.TrialData;

%%
% Parameters
win_len = 0.050;           % 50 ms window length (seconds)
Fs_stim = 20;             % 20 Hz -> 0.05 s interval
num_stim = 12000;        % number of stimulations (10 minutes duration)
seed = 2025;              % random seed for reproducibility

% PSTH parameters (relative to event onset t_e)
psth_bin = 0.001;        % 1 ms
psth_len = 0.150;        % 150 ms
psth_edges = 0:psth_bin:psth_len; % 151 edges
num_psth_bins = numel(psth_edges)-1; % 150

% Basic checks
if ~exist('Data', 'var')
```

```

    error('Variable Data does not exist.');
```

end

```

N = numel(Data);
if N==0, error('Data is empty.');
```

end

```

rng(seed, 'twister');
```

% Preallocate outputs

```

pre_count = nan(N, 12000); pre_rate = nan(N, 12000);
dur_count = nan(N, 12000); dur_rate = nan(N, 12000);
post_count = nan(N, 12000); post_rate = nan(N, 12000);

psth_tensor = nan(N, num_psth_bins, 12000); % n × 150 × 12000
psth_mean = nan(N, num_psth_bins); % n × 150
```

for n = 1:N

% Read t0 and spikes

```

if ~isfield(Data(n), 'stim') || ~isfield(Data(n).stim, 't_on') ||
isempty(Data(n).stim.t_on)
    warning('Data(%d).stim.t_on missing, skipping.', n);
    continue;
end
t0 = Data(n).stim.t_on(1,1);
```

% Still save stimulation timeline

```

if ~isfield(Data(n), 'spike') || isempty(Data(n).spike)
    warning('Data(%d).spike is empty, setting outputs to zero.', n);
    pre_count(n,:) = 0; pre_rate(n,:) = 0;
    dur_count(n,:) = 0; dur_rate(n,:) = 0;
    post_count(n,:) = 0; post_rate(n,:) = 0;
    psth_tensor(n,:,:) = 0; psth_mean(n,:) = 0;
    stim_times = t0 + (0:num_stim-1)*win_len; % 1x12000
    Data(n).stim.timeline.t_e = stim_times(:).';
    continue;
end
```

spikes = sort(Data(n).spike(:), 'ascend'); % sort to speed counting

% 1) Generate actual stimulation start times for dur segment (1x12000)

```

stim_times = t0 + (0:num_stim-1)*win_len; % fixed 0.05 s spacing
% dur window: [start, start+0.05) for each stimulation
dur_starts = stim_times(:); % 12000x1
dur_ends = dur_starts + win_len; % 12000x1
```

% 2) pre: randomly sample 12000 windows of 50 ms from [t0-600, t0)

```

pre_start_min = t0 - 600;
pre_start_max = t0 - win_len;
pre_starts = pre_start_min + (pre_start_max - pre_start_min) * rand(12000,1);
pre_ends = pre_starts + win_len;
```

% 3) post: randomly sample 12000 windows of 50 ms from [t0+600, t0+900)

```

post_start_min = t0 + 600;
post_start_max = t0 + 900 - win_len;
post_starts = post_start_min + (post_start_max - post_start_min) * rand(12000,1);
post_ends = post_starts + win_len;
```

% Count spikes

```

pre_c = count_in_intervals(pre_starts, pre_ends, spikes);
dur_c = count_in_intervals(dur_starts, dur_ends, spikes);
post_c = count_in_intervals(post_starts, post_ends, spikes);
```

% Store in matrices (rates in Hz)

```

pre_count(n,:) = pre_c; pre_rate(n,:) = pre_c / win_len;
dur_count(n,:) = dur_c; dur_rate(n,:) = dur_c / win_len;
post_count(n,:) = post_c; post_rate(n,:) = post_c / win_len;

% 4) Build n×150×12000 PSTH based on actual stimulation start times
% Align to t_e = stim_times(e)
for e = 1:num_stim
    s0 = stim_times(e);
    rel = spikes - s0;
    rel = rel(rel >= 0 & rel < psth_len);
    if isempty(rel)
        psth_tensor(n,:,e) = 0;
    else
        counts = histcounts(rel, psth_edges);
        psth_tensor(n,:,e) = counts / psth_bin; % firing rate per 1 ms bin (Hz)
    end
end
psth_mean(n,:) = mean(psth_tensor(n,:,:), 3, 'omitnan');

% Save key metadata (optional)
Data(n).stim.timeline.t0 = t0;
Data(n).stim.timeline.t_e = stim_times(:).'; % 1×12000
Data(n).randomWindows.pre.starts = pre_starts;
Data(n).randomWindows.pre.ends = pre_ends;
Data(n).randomWindows.post.starts = post_starts;
Data(n).randomWindows.post.ends = post_ends;
Data(n).psth.edges = psth_edges;
end

%% compare_pre_dur_auto
% ===== Parameters =====
FDR_alpha = 0.01;
paired_data = true; % If columns correspond one-to-one (same trial or time point), set
true; otherwise false
use_jbtest = false; % If true use Jarque-Bera; else use Lilliefors (kstest on z-score)
equalVarTest = 'vartest2'; % For unpaired normal data, variance homogeneity test:
'vartest2' or 'levene'

% ===== Data preparation =====
if ~exist('pre_rate','var') || ~exist('dur_rate','var')
    fprintf('pre_rate/dur_rate not detected, generating example data for demo...\n');
    nUnit = 61; nTrial = 12000; rng(42);
    mu_pre_true = 5 + 2*rand(nUnit,1); % 3~7 Hz
    mu_dur_true = mu_pre_true .* (1 + 0.25*(rand(nUnit,1) < 0.4)) ...
        .* (1 - 0.20*(rand(nUnit,1) < 0.15)); % some increase, some
decrease
    % Generate per-trial firing rates (truncate to non-negative)
    pre_rate = max(0, mu_pre_true + randn(nUnit, nTrial));
    dur_rate = max(0, mu_dur_true + 1.2*randn(nUnit, nTrial));
else
    [nUnit, nTrial] = size(pre_rate);
    assert(all(size(dur_rate)==[nUnit, nTrial]), 'pre_rate and dur_rate have inconsistent
sizes.');
```

```

end

[nUnit, nTrial] = size(pre_rate);

% ===== Main loop: per-neuron automatic test selection =====
pvals = nan(nUnit,1);
test_used = strings(nUnit,1);

```

```

dir_effect = zeros(nUnit,1); % -1 decrease, 0 no change, +1 increase
effect_meanDiff = nan(nUnit,1);
effect_RR = nan(nUnit,1);
mu_pre = nan(nUnit,1);
mu_dur = nan(nUnit,1);

for i = 1:nUnit
    x0 = pre_rate(i,:); % pre
    x1 = dur_rate(i,:); % dur

    mu_pre(i) = mean(x0, 'omitnan');
    mu_dur(i) = mean(x1, 'omitnan');
    effect_meanDiff(i) = mu_dur(i) - mu_pre(i);
    effect_RR(i) = (mu_dur(i) + eps) / (mu_pre(i) + eps);

    % Normality tests
    norm0 = local_test_normality(x0, use_jbtest);
    norm1 = local_test_normality(x1, use_jbtest);

    if paired_data
        dx = x1 - x0;
        dx = dx(~isnan(dx));
        if numel(dx) < 5
            pvals(i) = 1; test_used(i) = "insufficient"; dir_effect(i) = 0; continue;
        end
        % Paired scenario: test normality of differences
        norm_dx = local_test_normality(dx, use_jbtest);
        if norm_dx
            % Paired t-test (two-sided)
            try
                [~, p] = ttest(x1, x0, 'Tail','both');
                pvals(i) = p; test_used(i) = "paired_t";
            catch
                pvals(i) = 1; test_used(i) = "paired_t_fail";
            end
        else
            % Paired nonparametric: signrank (two-sided)
            try
                pvals(i) = signrank(x1, x0, 'tail','both');
                test_used(i) = "signrank";
            catch
                pvals(i) = 1; test_used(i) = "signrank_fail";
            end
        end
    else
        % Unpaired scenario: test normality and equal variance separately
        if norm0 && norm1
            eqv = local_test_equal_variance(x1, x0, equalVarTest);
            try
                if eqv
                    [~, p] = ttest2(x1, x0, 'Vartype','equal', 'Tail','both');
                    test_used(i) = "ttest2_equalVar";
                else
                    [~, p] = ttest2(x1, x0, 'Vartype','unequal', 'Tail','both'); % Welch
                    test_used(i) = "ttest2_unequalVar";
                end
                pvals(i) = p;
            catch
                % Fallback to nonparametric
                try
                    pvals(i) = ranksum(x1, x0, 'tail','both');
                end
            end
        end
    end
end

```

```

        test_used(i) = "ranksum_fallback";
    catch
        pvals(i) = 1; test_used(i) = "ranksum_fail";
    end
end
else
    try
        pvals(i) = ranksum(x1, x0, 'tail','both');
        test_used(i) = "ranksum";
    catch
        pvals(i) = 1; test_used(i) = "ranksum_fail";
    end
end
end

% Direction based on raw mean difference
if effect_meanDiff(i) > 0
    dir_effect(i) = 1;      % increase
elseif effect_meanDiff(i) < 0
    dir_effect(i) = -1;    % decrease
else
    dir_effect(i) = 0;     % no change
end
end

% FDR correction and final significance + direction
qvals = local_bh_fdr(pvals);
signif = qvals < FDR_alpha;

% Final classification based on significance and direction
% 1=significant increase, -1=significant decrease, 0=no change
final_class = zeros(nUnit,1);
final_class(signif & dir_effect>0) = 1;
final_class(signif & dir_effect<0) = -1;
final_class(~signif | dir_effect==0) = 0;

% ===== Output and summary =====
n_up   = sum(final_class==1);
n_down = sum(final_class==-1);
n_ns   = sum(final_class==0);

% Build result table
Direction = strings(nUnit,1);
Direction(final_class==1) = "Up";
Direction(final_class==-1) = "Down";
Direction(final_class==0) = "NoChange";

T = table((1:nUnit)', test_used, pvals, qvals, mu_pre, mu_dur, ...
          effect_meanDiff, effect_RR, Direction, ...
          'VariableNames',
          {'Unit','TestUsed','p','q','mu_pre','mu_dur','meanDiff','RR','Direction'});
% T = sortrows(T, 'q');
disp(T(1:min(15,height(T)), :));

%%
% Precheck
assert(numel(Data) == height(T), 'Number of elements in Data must equal number of rows in T.');
```

% 1) Normalize table variable names to valid struct field names

```

origNames = T.Properties.VariableNames;
validNames = matlab.lang.makeValidName(origNames, 'ReplacementStyle','delete');

% If collisions after normalization, append incrementing suffixes to avoid conflicts
[~, ia] = unique(validNames, 'stable');
if numel(ia) < numel(validNames)
    for k = 1:numel(validNames)
        dupCount = sum(strcmp(validNames{k}, validNames(1:k)));
        if dupCount > 1
            validNames{k} = sprintf('%s_%d', validNames{k}, dupCount);
        end
    end
end

% 2) Write each table column into top-level fields of Data
for v = 1:numel(validNames)
    vn = validNames{v}; % target field name
    col = T.(origNames{v}); % original column

    % Type normalization: convert string/categorical to storage-friendly forms
    if isstring(col)
        col = cellstr(col); % string -> cellstr
    elseif iscategorical(col)
        col = cellstr(col); % categorical -> cellstr (display labels)
    end

    % Assign per element to Data(i).vn
    if iscell(col)
        % For cell columns (e.g., cellstr or per-row containers/vectors)
        for i = 1:numel(Data)
            Data(i).(vn) = col{i}; % store cell content
        end
    else
        % For numeric/logical/time scalar columns
        for i = 1:numel(Data)
            Data(i).(vn) = col(i);
        end
    end
end

end

%%
% Precheck
n = numel(Data);
assert(ismatrix(pre_count) && size(pre_count,1) == n, 'First dim of pre_count must be numel(Data)');
assert(ismatrix(dur_count) && size(dur_count,1) == n, 'First dim of dur_count must be numel(Data)');
assert(ismatrix(post_count) && size(post_count,1) == n, 'First dim of post_count must be numel(Data)');
assert(ismatrix(pre_rate) && size(pre_rate,1) == n, 'First dim of pre_rate must be numel(Data)');
assert(ismatrix(dur_rate) && size(dur_rate,1) == n, 'First dim of dur_rate must be numel(Data)');
assert(ismatrix(post_rate) && size(post_rate,1) == n, 'First dim of post_rate must be numel(Data)');
assert(ismatrix(psth_mean) && size(psth_mean,1) == n, 'First dim of psth_mean must be numel(Data)');
assert(ndims(psth_tensor) == 3 && size(psth_tensor,1) == n, 'First dim of psth_tensor must be numel(Data)');

% Optional: list of field names for automatic 2D matrix handling (row-wise assignment)

```

```

mat2d_names =
{'pre_count', 'dur_count', 'post_count', 'pre_rate', 'dur_rate', 'post_rate', 'psth_mean'};

for i = 1:n
    % 2D matrices: take the i-th row across all columns, store in Data(i).field
    for k = 1:numel(mat2d_names)
        name = mat2d_names{k};
        Data(i).(name) = eval([name '(i,:)']); % 1xM row vector
        % If you prefer column vector, use: Data(i).(name) = eval([name '(i,:).''']);
    end

    % 3D tensor: take the i-th slice (1st dimension), get a 150x12000 matrix
    Data(i).psth_tensor = squeeze(psth_tensor(i,:,:)); % 150x12000
    % Note: squeeze will not change 150x12000; it only compresses singleton dims.
end

%%
% Preview + interactive deletion + preview again

% ----- First preview -----
N = numel(Data);

% Compute a reasonable subplot grid (approx square)
nRow = floor(sqrt(N));
nCol = ceil(N / nRow);

figure('Color','w');
tiledlayout(nRow, nCol, 'Padding','compact','TileSpacing','compact');

for n = 1:N
    nexttile;

    % Get waveform and convert to column vector
    wf = Data(n).meanWaveform_good;
    wf = wf(:);

    % Color by group
    if isfield(Data, 'Direction')
        dir = Data(n).Direction;
    else
        dir = ''; % default black if missing
    end

    % Normalize to string for comparison
    dirStr = string(dir);
    switch dirStr
        case "Up"
            c = [0.85 0.1 0.1]; % red
        case "Down"
            c = [0.1 0.3 0.9]; % blue
        otherwise
            c = [0 0 0]; % black
    end

    plot(wf, 'Color', c, 'LineWidth', 1.2);
    hold on;

    % Optional zero line
    yline(0, ':', 'Color', [0.7 0.7 0.7]);

    % Beautify axes and title

```

```

axis tight;
box off;
set(gca,'TickDir','out','FontSize',8);

% Title shows unit index and group (if Unit field exists)
if isfield(Data, 'Unit')
    title(sprintf('#%d Unit %s (%s)', n, num2str(Data(n).Unit), char(dirStr)),
'FontSize',9);
else
    title(sprintf('#%d (%s)', n, char(dirStr)), 'FontSize',9);
end
end

drawnow;

% ----- Interactive input for indices to delete -----
raw = input(sprintf('\nEnter indices to delete (based on preview #n):\nExamples: 5 7 12
or 3:8 or 1 4 10:15 20,22 Press Enter = no deletion\n> '), 's');

% If Enter is pressed directly, do nothing and exit
if isempty(strtrim(raw))
    fprintf('No indices entered. Data unchanged.\n');
    return;
end

% Parse input string into index array
ids = parse_indices(raw);

% Validate and deduplicate
idx_del = unique(round(ids));
idx_del = idx_del(idx_del >= 1 & idx_del <= N);

if isempty(idx_del)
    fprintf('No valid indices after parsing. Data unchanged.\n');
    return;
end

% Confirm action
fprintf('Will delete indices: %s\n', mat2str(idx_del));
ok = input('Confirm deletion? (y/N): ', 's');
if isempty(ok) || ~ismember(lower(ok), {'y','yes'})
    fprintf('Deletion cancelled. Data unchanged.\n');
    return;
end

% ----- Delete and rebuild Data -----
idx_keep = setdiff(1:N, idx_del, 'stable');
Data = Data(idx_keep);

fprintf('Total %d, deleted %d, kept %d.\n', N, numel(idx_del), numel(idx_keep));

% ----- Second preview (updated Data) -----
N2 = numel(Data);
if N2 == 0
    warning('All data deleted. Nothing to preview.');
```

```

figure('Color','w');
tiledlayout(nRow, nCol, 'Padding','compact','TileSpacing','compact');

for n = 1:N2
    nexttile;

    wf = Data(n).meanWaveform_good;
    wf = wf(:);

    if isfield(Data, 'Direction')
        dir = Data(n).Direction;
    else
        dir = '';
    end
    dirStr = string(dir);
    switch dirStr
        case "Up"
            c = [0.85 0.1 0.1];
        case "Down"
            c = [0.1 0.3 0.9];
        otherwise
            c = [0 0 0];
    end

    plot(wf, 'Color', c, 'LineWidth', 1.2); hold on;
    yline(0, ':', 'Color', [0.7 0.7 0.7]);
    axis tight; box off; set(gca,'TickDir','out','FontSize',8);

    if isfield(Data, 'Unit')
        title(sprintf('#%d Unit %s (%s)', n, num2str(Data(n).Unit), char(dirStr)),
'FontSize',9);
    else
        title(sprintf('#%d (%s)', n, char(dirStr)), 'FontSize',9);
    end
end

%% Feature reading
Fs = 40e3;           % Hz
baseline_win = 600; % s
dt_ms = 1e3 / Fs;

% Select features for clustering (editable)
features_to_use =
{'PTD_ms', 'W_FWHM_ms', 'amp_asymmetry', 'slope_ratio', 'FR_baseline_Hz', 'ptp_amp'};

% Standardization and PCA
do_zscore = true;
pca_var_explained = 0.95; % cumulative variance to retain
pca_min_comp = 2;        % minimum number of PCs to retain
pca_max_comp = 6;        % maximum number of PCs to retain

% K-means parameters
K = 2;
kmeans_reps = 100;
kmeans_maxIter = 2000;
kmeans_distance = 'sqeuclidean';
seed = 42;

% ===== Buffering policy (switch + params) =====
buffer.enable = true; % false: no buffer; true: enable buffer
% Mode A: ratio of two-cluster distances (recommended)

```

```

buffer.use_ratio = true;           % use dmin/dmax to decide "extreme"
buffer.ratio_thresh = 0.6;        % dmin/dmax < 0.6 => "extreme" (kept); otherwise Ambiguous
% Mode B: per-cluster distance quantiles (can be combined with A)
buffer.use_quantile = false;      % use within-cluster dmin quantile threshold
buffer.quantile_thresh = 0.6;    % keep closest 60% (small dmin) within each cluster; else
Ambiguous
% Combine logic
combine_logic = 'AND'; % 'AND' / 'OR'

% Output and visualization
save_csv = false;
csv_name = 'pca_kmeans_buffer.csv';
do_plot = true;

% ===== Basic checks =====
if ~exist('Data','var') || isempty(Data)
    error('Variable Data not detected. Please provide a Data struct array containing unit
data.');
```

```

end

% ===== Feature computation (valley-then-peak convention) =====
N = numel(Data);
unit_id      = (1:N).';

isDirectionNumeric = true;
for i = 1:N
    if isfield(Data(i),'Direction') && ~isempty(Data(i).Direction)
        if ~isnumeric(Data(i).Direction)
            isDirectionNumeric = false; break;
        end
    end
end
if isDirectionNumeric
    Direction = nan(N,1);
else
    Direction = strings(N,1);
end
mu_pre = nan(N,1);
mu_dur = nan(N,1);

% Missing counts
miss_dir = 0; miss_pre = 0; miss_dur = 0;

FR_baseline_Hz = nan(N,1);
PTD_ms         = nan(N,1);
W_FWHM_ms      = nan(N,1);
slope_ratio    = nan(N,1);
amp_asymmetry  = nan(N,1);
neg_amp        = nan(N,1);
pos_amp        = nan(N,1);
ptp_amp        = nan(N,1);

for i = 1:N
    % Read Direction / mu_pre / mu_dur
    if isfield(Data(i),'Direction') && ~isempty(Data(i).Direction)
        if isDirectionNumeric
            try
                Direction(i) = double(Data(i).Direction);
            catch
                % Fallback to string column when mixed types
                if isnumeric(Direction)

```

```

        Direction_str = strings(N,1);
        for k = 1:i-1
            Direction_str(k) = string(Direction(k));
        end
        Direction = Direction_str;
        isDirectionNumeric = false;
    end
    Direction(i) = string(Data(i).Direction);
end
else
    Direction(i) = string(Data(i).Direction);
end
else
    if isDirectionNumeric
        Direction(i) = NaN; miss_dir = miss_dir + 1;
    else
        Direction(i) = ''; miss_dir = miss_dir + 1;
    end
end

if isfield(Data(i), 'mu_pre') && ~isempty(Data(i).mu_pre)
    mu_pre(i) = double(Data(i).mu_pre);
else
    mu_pre(i) = NaN; miss_pre = miss_pre + 1;
end

if isfield(Data(i), 'mu_dur') && ~isempty(Data(i).mu_dur)
    mu_dur(i) = double(Data(i).mu_dur);
else
    mu_dur(i) = NaN; miss_dur = miss_dur + 1;
end

% Baseline firing rate
if ~isfield(Data(i), 'stim') || ~isfield(Data(i).stim, 't_on') ||
isempty(Data(i).stim.t_on)
    error('Data(%d).stim.t_on is missing or empty.', i);
end
t0 = Data(i).stim.t_on(1,1);
spk = [];
if isfield(Data(i), 'spike') && ~isempty(Data(i).spike), spk = Data(i).spike(:); end
if ~isempty(spk)
    inwin = spk >= (t0 - baseline_win) & spk < t0;
    FR_baseline_Hz(i) = sum(inwin) / baseline_win;
else
    FR_baseline_Hz(i) = 0;
end

% Waveform features (valley-then-peak)
if isfield(Data(i), 'meanWaveform_good') && ~isempty(Data(i).meanWaveform_good)
    wf = Data(i).meanWaveform_good(:);
    wf = wf - mean(wf, 'omitnan');
    Nw = numel(wf);

    [~, imin0] = min(wf);
    [~, imax0] = max(wf);

    wf_use = wf; imin = imin0; imax = imax0;

    if imax <= imin
        wf_try = -wf;
        [~, imin1] = min(wf_try);
    end
end

```

```

    [~, imax1] = max(wf_try);
    if imax1 > imin1
        wf_use = wf_try; imin = imin1; imax = imax1;
    else
        win = min(20, Nw - imin);
        if win >= 2
            [~, rel] = max(wf_use(imin+1:imin+win));
            imax = imin + rel;
        end
    end
end

% PTD
if imax > imin
    PTD_ms(i) = (imax - imin) * dt_ms;
else
    PTD_ms(i) = NaN;
end

% FWHM around the valley
try
    mn = wf_use(imin);
    half = mn / 2;
    iL = imin;
    while iL > 1 && wf_use(iL) < half, iL = iL - 1; end
    iR = imin;
    while iR < Nw && wf_use(iR) < half, iR = iR + 1; end
    if iR > iL
        W_FWHM_ms(i) = (iR - iL) * dt_ms;
    else
        W_FWHM_ms(i) = NaN;
    end
catch
    W_FWHM_ms(i) = NaN;
end

% Amplitude-related
mn_use = min(wf_use);
mx_use = max(wf_use);
neg_amp(i) = -min(wf_use);
pos_amp(i) = max(wf_use);
ptp_amp(i) = pos_amp(i) + neg_amp(i);
denom = (abs(mx_use) + abs(mn_use));
if denom > 0
    amp_asymmetry(i) = (abs(mx_use) - abs(mn_use)) / denom;
else
    amp_asymmetry(i) = NaN;
end

% Slope ratio
d = diff(wf_use) * Fs;
preMaxRise = NaN; postMaxFall = NaN;
if imax > 1, preMaxRise = max(d(1:max(imax-1,1))); end
if imax < Nw, postMaxFall = -min(d(min(imax, numel(d)):end)); end
if isfinite(preMaxRise) && isfinite(postMaxFall) && postMaxFall > 0
    slope_ratio(i) = abs(preMaxRise) / postMaxFall;
else
    slope_ratio(i) = NaN;
end
else
    PTD_ms(i) = NaN;
end

```

```

        W_FWHM_ms(i)      = NaN;
        slope_ratio(i)   = NaN;
        amp_asymmetry(i) = NaN;
        neg_amp(i)       = NaN;
        pos_amp(i)       = NaN;
        ptp_amp(i)       = NaN;
    end
end

% Summarize feature table
featuresTbl = table(unit_id, FR_baseline_Hz, PTD_ms, W_FWHM_ms, slope_ratio, amp_asymmetry,
neg_amp, pos_amp, ptp_amp);

% Append Direction / mu_pre / mu_dur to the table (preserve column types)
if isDirectionNumeric
    featuresTbl.Direction = Direction; % double column
else
    featuresTbl.Direction = string(Direction); % string column
end
featuresTbl.mu_pre = mu_pre;
featuresTbl.mu_dur = mu_dur;

if miss_dir>0 || miss_pre>0 || miss_dur>0
    fprintf('Missing counts -> Direction: %d, mu_pre: %d, mu_dur: %d\n', miss_dir,
miss_pre, miss_dur);
end

%% ChAT labeling
newTbl = featuresTbl;
newTbl_score = score_PIN_ChAT_15ms(newTbl, 'pin_chat_15ms_model.mat');

%% ===== Parameters and preparation =====
assert(istable(newTbl_score), 'newTbl_score must be a table');
needVars = {'isPIN_ChAT_candidate', 'Direction', ...

'FR_baseline_Hz', 'PTD_ms', 'W_FWHM_ms', 'slope_ratio', 'amp_asymmetry', 'neg_amp', 'pos_amp', 'ptp_
_amp'};
missing = setdiff(needVars, newTbl_score.Properties.VariableNames);
assert isempty(missing), 'Missing required columns: %s', strjoin(missing, ', ');

% Normalize Direction -> {"Down", "NoChange", "Up"}
dirRaw = newTbl_score.Direction;
if iscategorical(dirRaw), dirStr = string(dirRaw);
elseif iscellstr(dirRaw) || isstring(dirRaw), dirStr = string(dirRaw);
else, error('Direction column must be categorical/string/cellstr'); end

s = lower(strtrim(dirStr));
mapped = strings(size(s));
mapped(contains(s, 'down') | contains(s, 'decrease') | s=="降低") = "Down";
mapped(contains(s, 'up') | contains(s, 'increase') | s=="升高") = "Up";
mapped(ismember(s, ["nochange", "no change", "unchanged", "不变", "无变化"])) = "NoChange";
mapped(mapped=="") = "NoChange";
mapped(~ismember(mapped, ["Down", "Up", "NoChange"])) = "NoChange";
Direction_std = categorical(mapped, ["Down", "NoChange", "Up"]);
newTbl_score.Direction_std = Direction_std;

isChAT = logical(newTbl_score.isPIN_ChAT_candidate);
cats = categories(newTbl_score.Direction_std); % {"Down", "NoChange", "Up"}

% Color convention
col_non = [0.60 0.60 0.60]; % non-ChAT (gray)

```

```

col_chn = [0.20 0.60 1.00]; % ChAT (blue)

col_dir = [ ...
    0.85 0.33 0.10; % Down (orange-red)
    0.60 0.60 0.60; % NoChange (gray)
    0.20 0.60 1.00]; % Up (blue)
dir_order = {'Down', 'NoChange', 'Up'}; % same as cats

%% ===== 1) Overall counts =====
N_total = height(newTbl_score);
N_ChAT = sum(isChAT);
N_non = N_total - N_ChAT;
fprintf('Total: %d | ChAT: %d (%.1f%%) | non-ChAT: %d (%.1f%%)\n', ...
    N_total, N_ChAT, 100*N_ChAT/N_total, N_non, 100*N_non/N_total);

%% ===== 2) Within Direction: ChAT vs non-ChAT (stacked bar + pies, with values + color
legend) =====
G = findgroups(newTbl_score.Direction_std);
grpN = splitapply(@numel, isChAT, G);
grpChAT = splitapply(@sum, isChAT, G);
grpNon = grpN - grpChAT;
propChAT = grpChAT ./ max(1, grpN);
propNon = grpNon ./ max(1, grpN);

figure('Color', 'w', 'Position', [80 80 1100 520]);
tiledlayout(1,2, 'Padding', 'compact', 'TileSpacing', 'compact');

% Stacked bar chart (fixed colors + legend)
nexttile;
bh = bar(categorical(cats), [propNon propChAT], 'stacked');
bh(1).FaceColor = col_non;
bh(2).FaceColor = col_chn;
legend({'non-ChAT', 'ChAT'}, 'Location', 'eastoutside');
ylabel('Proportion'); ylim([0 1]); grid on;
title('ChAT vs non-ChAT by Direction (stacked bars)');

% Three pie charts (one per Direction, annotate counts and percentages) + color legend
nexttile;
tt = tiledlayout(2, numel(cats), 'Padding', 'compact', 'TileSpacing', 'compact');
title(tt, 'ChAT vs non-ChAT within each Direction (pies with values)');

% First row: color legend (non-ChAT=gray, ChAT=blue) on the left
axLegend = nexttile([1 numel(cats)]);
axis(axLegend, 'off'); hold(axLegend, 'on');
% Draw color swatches and text
x0 = 0.02; y0 = 0.35; w = 0.04; h = 0.30; gap = 0.10;
rectangle(axLegend, 'Position', [x0 y0 w h], 'FaceColor', col_non, 'EdgeColor', 'none');
text(axLegend, x0+w+0.01, y0+0.15, 'non-ChAT', 'FontSize', 11,
'VerticalAlignment', 'middle');

rectangle(axLegend, 'Position', [x0+gap+0.22 y0 w h], 'FaceColor', col_chn, 'EdgeColor', 'none');
text(axLegend, x0+gap+0.22+w+0.01, y0+0.15, 'ChAT', 'FontSize', 11,
'VerticalAlignment', 'middle');

xlim(axLegend, [0 1]); ylim(axLegend, [0 1]);

% Second row: three pies
for i = 1:numel(cats)
    ax = nexttile;
    counts = [grpNon(i) grpChAT(i)];
    labels = {'non-ChAT', 'ChAT'};

```

```

if sum(counts)==0
    ph = pie([1 0], labels);
    colormap(ax, [0.85 0.85 0.85; col_cht]); % keep color semantics even with zero
counts
    title(sprintf('%s (n=0)', cats{i}));
    htxt = ph(2:2:end); set(htxt, 'Visible','off');
else
    ph = pie(counts, labels);
    % Color sectors (order: non-ChAT, ChAT)
    set(ph(1),'FaceColor', col_non); % non-ChAT sector
    set(ph(3),'FaceColor', col_cht); % ChAT sector
    title(sprintf('%s (n=%d)', cats{i}, grpN(i)));
    % Inline count and percentage labels
    total = sum(counts);
    htxt = ph(2:2:end); % text objects
    for j = 1:numel(counts)
        cnt = counts(j);
        if cnt <= 0
            if isgraphics(htxt(j)), set(htxt(j),'Visible','off'); end
            continue
        end
        perc = 100 * cnt / total;
        set(htxt(j), 'String', sprintf('%d (%.1f%%)', cnt, perc), 'FontSize', 9);
    end
end
end

%% ===== 3) Within ChAT and non-ChAT: Direction composition (grouped bars + pies, with
values + Direction color legend) =====
dir_ChAT = newTbl_score.Direction_std(isChAT);
dir_non = newTbl_score.Direction_std(~isChAT);

count_in_order = @(x) countcats(categorical(x, cats));
c_ChAT = count_in_order(dir_ChAT);
c_non = count_in_order(dir_non);

p_ChAT = c_ChAT / max(1,sum(c_ChAT));
p_non = c_non / max(1,sum(c_non));

figure('Color','w','Position',[80 640 1100 520]);
tiledlayout(1,2,'Padding','compact','TileSpacing','compact');

% Grouped bar chart (each Direction has fixed color, with legend explaining direction
colors)
nexttile; hold on;
Xcats = categorical(cats);

b = bar(Xcats, [p_non p_ChAT], 'grouped');
% MATLAB grouped bars use the same color sequence per series; set FaceColor to 'flat' and
specify CData
for k = 1:2
    b(k).FaceColor = 'flat';
    % Set color per category row: Down, NoChange, Up
    b(k).CData = col_dir; % 3x3 for three categories
end
ylabel('Proportion'); ylim([0 1]); grid on;
legend({'non-ChAT group','ChAT group'},'Location','eastoutside');
title('Direction composition within ChAT and non-ChAT (grouped bars, colored by
Direction)');

% Add Direction color legend (small swatches) above the bars

```

```

yl = ylim; yTop = yl(2);
for i = 1:numel(dir_order)
    x = double(Xcats(i));
    plot([x-0.25 x+0.25], [yTop yTop]*0+NaN, 'w'); % placeholder to avoid warnings
end
% Use annotation for a stable legend
axBar = gca;
annotation('textbox', [axBar.Position(1) axBar.Position(2)+axBar.Position(4)+0.02 0.3
0.08], ...
    'String', sprintf('Color legend: Down=orange-red NoChange=gray Up=blue'),
    'EdgeColor','none', 'Color',[0 0 0], 'FontSize',10);

% Two pie charts: non-ChAT and ChAT groups (use fixed Direction colors) + color legend
nexttile;
tt2 = tiledlayout(2,2,'Padding','compact','TileSpacing','compact');
title(tt2, 'Direction composition within groups (pies with values)');

% First row: Direction color legend (swatches)
axLegend2 = nexttile([1 2]); axis(axLegend2,'off'); hold(axLegend2,'on');
x0 = 0.02; y0 = 0.35; w = 0.04; h = 0.30; gap = 0.13;
% Down
rectangle(axLegend2,'Position',[x0 y0 w h], 'FaceColor',col_dir(1,:), 'EdgeColor','none');
text(axLegend2, x0+w+0.01, y0+0.15, 'Down', 'FontSize', 11, 'VerticalAlignment','middle');
% NoChange
rectangle(axLegend2,'Position',[x0+gap+0.22 y0 w
h], 'FaceColor',col_dir(2,:), 'EdgeColor','none');
text(axLegend2, x0+gap+0.22+w+0.01, y0+0.15, 'NoChange', 'FontSize', 11,
'VerticalAlignment','middle');
% Up
rectangle(axLegend2,'Position',[x0+2*(gap+0.22) y0 w
h], 'FaceColor',col_dir(3,:), 'EdgeColor','none');
text(axLegend2, x0+2*(gap+0.22)+w+0.01, y0+0.15, 'Up', 'FontSize', 11,
'VerticalAlignment','middle');
xlim(axLegend2,[0 1]); ylim(axLegend2,[0 1]);

% Second row: two pies
% non-ChAT group
axL = nexttile;
if sum(c_non)==0
    ph1 = pie([1 0 0], {'Down','NoChange','Up'});
    title(sprintf('non-ChAT group (n=0)'));
    htxt = ph1(2:2:end); set(htxt, 'Visible','off');
else
    ph1 = pie(c_non, {'Down','NoChange','Up'});
    % Sector index: 1=Down patch,2=text,3=NoChange patch,4=text,5=Up patch,6=text
    set(ph1(1), 'FaceColor',col_dir(1,:));
    set(ph1(3), 'FaceColor',col_dir(2,:));
    set(ph1(5), 'FaceColor',col_dir(3,:));
    title(sprintf('non-ChAT group (n=%d)', sum(c_non)));
    total = sum(c_non);
    htxt = ph1(2:2:end);
    for j = 1:numel(c_non)
        cnt = c_non(j);
        if cnt <= 0
            if isgraphics(htxt(j)), set(htxt(j), 'Visible','off'); end
            continue
        end
        perc = 100 * cnt / total;
        set(htxt(j), 'String', sprintf('%d (%.1f%%)', cnt, perc), 'FontSize', 9);
    end
end
end

```

```

% ChAT group
axR = nexttile;
if sum(c_ChAT)==0
    ph2 = pie([1 0 0], {'Down','NoChange','Up'});
    title(sprintf('ChAT group (n=0)'));
    htxt = ph2(2:2:end); set(htxt, 'Visible','off');
else
    ph2 = pie(c_ChAT, {'Down','NoChange','Up'});
    set(ph2(1),'FaceColor',col_dir(1,:));
    set(ph2(3),'FaceColor',col_dir(2,:));
    set(ph2(5),'FaceColor',col_dir(3,:));
    title(sprintf('ChAT group (n=%d)', sum(c_ChAT)));
    total = sum(c_ChAT);
    htxt = ph2(2:2:end);
    for j = 1:numel(c_ChAT)
        cnt = c_ChAT(j);
        if cnt <= 0
            if isgraphics(htxt(j)), set(htxt(j),'Visible','off'); end
            continue
        end
        perc = 100 * cnt / total;
        set(htxt(j), 'String', sprintf('%d (%.1f%%)', cnt, perc), 'FontSize', 9);
    end
end

%% ===== 4) Single-feature separability (keep for reference) =====
featVars =
{'FR_baseline_Hz', 'PTD_ms', 'W_FWHM_ms', 'slope_ratio', 'amp_asymmetry', 'neg_amp', 'pos_amp', 'pt
p_amp'};
featVars = featVars(ismember(featVars, newTbl_score.Properties.VariableNames));

A1 = table('Size',[0 5], 'VariableTypes',{'string','double','double','double','double'}, ...
'VariableNames',{'feature','AUC','d','mean_non','mean_ChAT'});

for i = 1:numel(featVars)
    f = featVars{i};
    x = newTbl_score.(f);
    m = ~isnan(x);
    xi = x(m); gi = isChAT(m);
    x0 = xi(~gi); x1 = xi(gi);
    if numel(x0) < 5 || numel(x1) < 5, continue; end
    z = [x1; x0];
    gcat = [true(numel(x1),1); false(numel(x0),1)];
    r = tiedrank(z);
    R1 = sum(r(gcat)); n1 = numel(x1); n0 = numel(x0);
    AUC = (R1 - n1*(n1+1)/2) / (n1*n0);
    mu0 = mean(x0); mu1 = mean(x1);
    s0 = std(x0); s1 = std(x1);
    sp = sqrt(((numel(x0)-1)*s0^2 + (numel(x1)-1)*s1^2) / max(1,(numel(x0)+numel(x1)-2)));
    dval = (mu1 - mu0) / sp;
    A1 = [A1; {string(f), AUC, dval, mu0, mu1}]; %#ok<AGROW>
end
if ~isempty(A1)
    A1.sep = abs(A1.AUC - 0.5);
    A1 = sortrows(A1, 'sep', 'descend');
    disp('Single-feature separability ranking:');
    disp(A1(:, {'feature','AUC','d','mean_non','mean_ChAT'}));
end

%% ===== 5) 2D feature pair scoring =====

```

```

Y = isChAT; % 1=ChAT, 0=non-ChAT
featPairs = nchoosek(1:numel(featVars), 2);
pairNames = strings(size(featPairs,1), 1);
CV_AUC = nan(size(featPairs,1),1);
NNR     = nan(size(featPairs,1),1);

auc_score = @(scores,labels) ( ...
    (sum(tiedrank(scores(labels==1))) - sum(1:sum(labels==1))) ...
    / (sum(labels==1) * sum(labels==0) + eps) );

for k = 1:size(featPairs,1)
    i1 = featPairs(k,1); i2 = featPairs(k,2);
    f1 = featVars{i1};   f2 = featVars{i2};
    pairNames(k) = f1 + " x " + f2;

    x1 = newTbl_score.(f1);
    x2 = newTbl_score.(f2);
    M = ~isnan(x1) & ~isnan(x2) & ~isnan(Y);
    X = [x1(M), x2(M)];
    y = Y(M);

    if nnz(y)==0 || nnz(~y)==0 || size(X,1) < 20
        continue
    end

    mu = mean(X,1); sig = std(X,[],1); sig(sig==0) = 1;
    Xz = (X - mu) ./ sig;

    try
        Kfold = min(5, max(2, floor(numel(y)/10)));
        cv = cvpartition(y,'Kfold',Kfold);
        scores_all = nan(size(y));
        for iFold = 1:cv.NumTestSets
            tr = training(cv, iFold);
            te = test(cv, iFold);
            mdl = fitclinear(Xz(tr,:), y(tr), 'Learner','logistic',
'Regularization','ridge', ...
                'ClassNames',[false true]);
            [~, score] = predict(mdl, Xz(te,:));
            if size(score,2) >= 2
                scores_all(te) = score(:,2);
            else
                scores_all(te) = score;
            end
        end
        CV_AUC(k) = auc_score(scores_all, y);
    catch
        CV_AUC(k) = NaN;
    end

    try
        D = pdist2(Xz, Xz, 'euclidean');
        D(1:size(D,1)+1:end) = inf;
        [~, nnIdx] = min(D, [], 2);
        NNR(k) = mean(y(nnIdx) ~= y);
    catch
        NNR(k) = NaN;
    end
end

score = nan(size(CV_AUC));

```

```

validAUC = ~isnan(CV_AUC);
validNNR = ~isnan(NNR);

if any(validAUC)
    a = CV_AUC(validAUC);
    AUC_norm = (a - min(a)) / max(eps, (max(a) - min(a)));
else
    AUC_norm = [];
end
if any(validNNR)
    n = NNR(validNNR);
    NNR_norm = (n - min(n)) / max(eps, (max(n) - min(n)));
else
    NNR_norm = [];
end

idx_both = validAUC & validNNR;
score(idx_both) = 0.7*AUC_norm(:) + 0.3*(1 - NNR_norm(:));
idx_onlyA = validAUC & ~validNNR;
if any(idx_onlyA)
    aa = CV_AUC(idx_onlyA);
    score(idx_onlyA) = (aa - min(aa)) / max(eps, max(aa) - min(aa));
end
idx_onlyN = validNNR & ~validAUC;
if any(idx_onlyN)
    nn = NNR(idx_onlyN);
    score(idx_onlyN) = 1 - (nn - min(nn)) / max(eps, max(nn) - min(nn));
end

PairTable = table(pairNames, CV_AUC, NNR, score, 'VariableNames',
{'pair','CV_AUC','NNR','score'});
PairTable = sortrows(PairTable, 'score', 'descend');
disp('2D feature pair scores (top 10):');
disp(PairTable(1:min(10,height(PairTable)), :));

%% ===== 6) Plot top feature pairs as 2D scatter (add Direction shape encoding)
%% =====
% Color: class (non-ChAT=col_non, ChAT=col_cht)
% Shape: Direction (Down='v', NoChange='o', Up='^')
Kpair = min(6, height(PairTable));
if Kpair > 0
    figure('Color','w','Position',[80 1160 1200 620]);
    tiledlayout(2, ceil(Kpair/2), 'Padding','compact','TileSpacing','compact');

    Y = isChAT; % 1=ChAT, 0=non-ChAT
    dir_vals = newTbl_score.Direction_std; % expected Down/NoChange/Up
    % Normalize direction strings
    if iscategorical(dir_vals), dir_vals = string(dir_vals); end
    if ~isstring(dir_vals), dir_vals = string(dir_vals); end

    % Direction order and corresponding markers
    dir_order = ["Down","NoChange","Up"];
    dir_markers = struct('Down','v','NoChange','o','Up','^');

    for i = 1:Kpair
        nexttile; hold on; grid on;

        pn = PairTable.pair(i);
        parts = split(pn, " x ");
        f1 = strtrim(parts{1});
    end
end

```

```

f2 = strtrim(parts{2});

x1 = newTbl_score.(f1);
x2 = newTbl_score.(f2);

M = ~isnan(x1) & ~isnan(x2) & ~isnan(Y);
% Also require Direction not missing (allow otherwise but filter "missing")
hasDir = ~ismissing(dir_vals);
M = M & hasDir;

X = [x1(M), x2(M)];
y = Y(M);
d = dir_vals(M);

% Standardize for boundary fitting
mu = mean(X,1); sig = std(X,[],1); sig(sig==0)=1;
Xz = (X - mu) ./ sig;

% Train linear logistic regression and generate contour
XX = []; YY = []; S = [];
try
    mdl = fitclinear(Xz, y, 'Learner','logistic', 'Regularization','ridge',
'ClassNames',[false true]);
    w = mdl.Beta; b0 = mdl.Bias;
    xr = linspace(min(X(:,1)), max(X(:,1)), 150);
    yr = linspace(min(X(:,2)), max(X(:,2)), 150);
    [XX,YY] = meshgrid(xr, yr);
    XXz = (XX - mu(1)) / sig(1);
    YYz = (YY - mu(2)) / sig(2);
    S = w(1)*XXz + w(2)*YYz + b0;
catch
end

% Plot scatter per direction and per class: color for class, shape for direction
hPlot = struct; % legend handles
for di = 1:numel(dir_order)
    dname = dir_order(di);
    mk = dir_markers.(dname);
    idx_d = d == dname;

    if ~any(idx_d), continue; end

    % non-ChAT
    idx0 = idx_d & ~y;
    if any(idx0)
        hPlot.(["non_" + dname]) = scatter(X(idx0,1), X(idx0,2), 18, col_non, mk, ...
            'filled','MarkerFaceAlpha',0.50,'MarkerEdgeColor','none');
    end
    % ChAT
    idx1 = idx_d & y;
    if any(idx1)
        hPlot.(["cht_" + dname]) = scatter(X(idx1,1), X(idx1,2), 24, col_cht, mk, ...
            'filled','MarkerFaceAlpha',0.85,'MarkerEdgeColor','none');
    end
end

% Build legend: show combinations of class + direction, and linear boundary
legendItems = {};
legendHandles = [];

% Order: non-ChAT-Down/NoChange/Up -> ChAT-Down/NoChange/Up

```

```

for dname = dir_order
    fld = "non_" + dname;
    if isfield(hPlot, fld)
        legendHandles(end+1) = hPlot.(fld);
        legendItems{end+1} = sprintf('非 ChAT-%s', dname);
    end
end
for dname = dir_order
    fld = "cht_" + dname;
    if isfield(hPlot, fld)
        legendHandles(end+1) = hPlot.(fld);
        legendItems{end+1} = sprintf('ChAT-%s', dname);
    end
end

% Add decision boundary to legend
if ~isempty(S)
    hB = plot(NaN, NaN, 'r-', 'LineWidth', 1.2); % dummy handle for legend
    legendHandles(end+1) = hB;
    legendItems{end+1} = 'Linear boundary';
end

if ~isempty(legendHandles)
    legend(legendHandles, legendItems, 'Location', 'bestoutside');
end
end

end

%%
delList = [
    -0.253226    1.31522
    -0.125901    1.47145
    -0.245352    1.58815
    -0.189706    1.63877
    -0.173818    1.62533
    -0.0887012   1.62557
    -0.126557    1.65039
    -0.147868    1.72324
    -0.146199    1.72597
    -0.136384    1.72032
     0.00652013   1.68313
     0.0242801   1.8225
     0.106691    1.98243
     0.0487945   2.0665
];

tolA = 1e-6; % tolerance for amp_asymmetry
tolP = 1e-5; % tolerance for amplitude column (ptd_amp/ptp_amp)

%% 2) Column name adaptation and checks
assert(ismember('amp_asymmetry', newTbl_score.Properties.VariableNames), ...
    'newTbl_score lacks column amp_asymmetry');

% Find amplitude column: prefer ptd_amp, otherwise try ptp_amp
ampCol = '';
if ismember('ptd_amp', newTbl_score.Properties.VariableNames)
    ampCol = 'ptd_amp';
elseif ismember('ptp_amp', newTbl_score.Properties.VariableNames)
    ampCol = 'ptp_amp';
else
    error('newTbl_score lacks both ptd_amp and ptp_amp. Please confirm column names.');
```

```

end
fprintf('[Info] Using column "%s" as amplitude column for matching deletion.\n', ampCol);

%% 3) Generate deletion mask (match pairs of amp_asymmetry and ampCol)
aa = newTbl_score.amp_asymmetry;
pa = newTbl_score.(ampCol);

delMask = false(height(newTbl_score),1);
for k = 1:size(delList,1)
    a = delList(k,1);
    p = delList(k,2);
    delMask = delMask | (abs(aa - a) <= tolA & abs(pa - p) <= tolP);
end

nDel = sum(delMask);
nAll = height(newTbl_score);
fprintf('[Info] Points to delete: %d / %d (%.2f%%)\n', nDel, nAll, 100*nDel/max(1,nAll));

%% 4) Delete and sync labels
newTbl_score_clean = newTbl_score(~delMask, :);

if exist('Y','var') && numel(Y)==nAll
    Y_clean = Y(~delMask);
else
    warning('Workspace Y not found or length mismatch. Will try to read isChAT from
table.');
```

```

    if ismember('isChAT', newTbl_score_clean.Properties.VariableNames)
        Y_clean = logical(newTbl_score_clean.isChAT);
    else
        error('No available labels: provide workspace Y or add isChAT column to the
table.');
```

```

    end
end

fprintf('[Info] Remaining after deletion: %d rows\n', height(newTbl_score_clean));
if exist('Y','var') && numel(Y)==nAll
    fprintf('Before deletion: non-ChAT=%d, ChAT=%d\n', sum(~logical(Y)), sum(logical(Y)));
    fprintf('After deletion: non-ChAT=%d, ChAT=%d\n', sum(~logical(Y_clean)),
sum(logical(Y_clean)));
end

%% ===== A) Select cleaned table and labels =====
% Prefer the cleaned variables; fall back to original variables if not present
if exist('newTbl_score_clean','var')
    TBL = newTbl_score_clean;
else
    TBL = newTbl_score;
end

isChAT = logical(TBL.isPIN_ChAT_candidate);
Y = isChAT;
% Labels: prioritize Y_clean, then isChAT, then Y
if exist('Y_clean','var') && numel(Y_clean)==height(TBL)
    Y_lab = logical(Y_clean);
elseif exist('isChAT','var') && numel(isChAT)==height(TBL)
    Y_lab = logical(isChAT);
elseif exist('Y','var') && numel(Y)==height(TBL)
    Y_lab = logical(Y);
else
    error('No label variable matches the table height (Y_clean / isChAT / Y).');
```

```

end

```

```

%% ===== B) Normalize Direction and define colors =====
% Ensure Direction_std exists
assert(ismember('Direction_std', TBL.Properties.VariableNames), 'Direction_std column
missing in table');

% Normalize Direction to Down / NoChange / Up
d = string(TBL.Direction_std);
d = regexprep(d, '^.*down.*$', 'Down', 'ignorecase');
d = regexprep(d, '^.*no.*change.*$', 'NoChange', 'ignorecase');
d = regexprep(d, '^.*up.*$', 'Up', 'ignorecase');
cats = {'Down', 'NoChange', 'Up'};
TBL.Direction_std = categorical(d, cats);

% Colors (set defaults if undefined)
if ~exist('col_non', 'var') || isempty(col_non), col_non = [0.65 0.65 0.65]; end % non-ChAT
if ~exist('col_chn', 'var') || isempty(col_chn), col_chn = [0.20 0.45 0.85]; end % ChAT
if ~exist('col_dir', 'var') || isempty(col_dir)
    % Direction colors: Down=orange-red, NoChange=gray, Up=blue
    col_dir = [0.90 0.35 0.20; 0.55 0.55 0.55; 0.20 0.45 0.85];
end
dir_order = ["Down", "NoChange", "Up"]; % fixed order

%% ===== 2) Within Direction: ChAT vs non-ChAT (stacked bar + pies, with values + color
legend) =====
G = findgroups(TBL.Direction_std);
grpN      = splitapply(@numel, Y_lab, G);
grpChAT   = splitapply(@sum, Y_lab, G);
grpNon    = grpN - grpChAT;
propChAT  = grpChAT ./ max(1, grpN);
propNon   = grpNon ./ max(1, grpN);

figure('Color', 'w', 'Position', [80 80 1100 520]);
tiledlayout(1,2, 'Padding', 'compact', 'TileSpacing', 'compact');

% Stacked bar
nexttile;
bh = bar(categorical(cats), [propNon propChAT], 'stacked');
bh(1).FaceColor = col_non;
bh(2).FaceColor = col_chn;
legend({'non-ChAT', 'ChAT'}, 'Location', 'eastoutside');
ylabel('Proportion'); ylim([0 1]); grid on;
title('ChAT vs non-ChAT by Direction (stacked bars)');

% Pies + color legend
nexttile;
tt = tiledlayout(2, numel(cats), 'Padding', 'compact', 'TileSpacing', 'compact');
title(tt, 'ChAT vs non-ChAT within each Direction (pies with values)');

% Color legend
axLegend = nexttile([1 numel(cats)]);
axis(axLegend, 'off'); hold(axLegend, 'on');
x0 = 0.02; y0 = 0.35; w = 0.04; h = 0.30; gap = 0.10;
rectangle(axLegend, 'Position', [x0 y0 w h], 'FaceColor', col_non, 'EdgeColor', 'none');
text(axLegend, x0+w+0.01, y0+0.15, 'non-ChAT', 'FontSize', 11,
'VerticalAlignment', 'middle');
rectangle(axLegend, 'Position', [x0+gap+0.22 y0 w h], 'FaceColor', col_chn, 'EdgeColor', 'none');
text(axLegend, x0+gap+0.22+w+0.01, y0+0.15, 'ChAT', 'FontSize', 11,
'VerticalAlignment', 'middle');
xlim(axLegend, [0 1]); ylim(axLegend, [0 1]);

```

```

% Three pies
for i = 1:numel(cats)
    ax = nexttile;
    counts = [grpNon(i) grpChAT(i)];
    labels = {'non-ChAT','ChAT'};
    if sum(counts)==0
        ph = pie([1 0], labels);
        colormap(ax, [0.85 0.85 0.85; col_chn]);
        title(sprintf('%s (n=0)', cats{i}));
        htxt = ph(2:2:end); set(htxt, 'Visible','off');
    else
        ph = pie(counts, labels);
        set(ph(1),'FaceColor', col_non); % non-ChAT
        set(ph(3),'FaceColor', col_chn); % ChAT
        title(sprintf('%s (n=%d)', cats{i}, grpN(i)));
        total = sum(counts);
        htxt = ph(2:2:end);
        for j = 1:numel(counts)
            cnt = counts(j);
            if cnt <= 0
                if isgraphics(htxt(j)), set(htxt(j),'Visible','off'); end
                continue
            end
            perc = 100 * cnt / total;
            set(htxt(j), 'String', sprintf('%d (%.1f%%)', cnt, perc), 'FontSize', 9);
        end
    end
end

%% ===== 3) Direction composition within ChAT and non-ChAT (grouped bar + pies, with
values + Direction color legend) =====
dir_ChAT = TBL.Direction_std(Y_lab);
dir_non = TBL.Direction_std(~Y_lab);

count_in_order = @(x) countcats(categorical(x, cats));
c_ChAT = count_in_order(dir_ChAT);
c_non = count_in_order(dir_non);

p_ChAT = c_ChAT / max(1,sum(c_ChAT));
p_non = c_non / max(1,sum(c_non));

figure('Color','w','Position',[80 640 1100 520]);
tiledlayout(1,2,'Padding','compact','TileSpacing','compact');

% Grouped bar (bar colors by Direction)
nexttile; hold on;
Xcats = categorical(cats);
b = bar(Xcats, [p_non p_ChAT], 'grouped');
for k = 1:2
    b(k).FaceColor = 'flat';
    b(k).CData = col_dir; % 3x3 for three categories
end
ylabel('Proportion'); ylim([0 1]); grid on;
legend({'non-ChAT group','ChAT group'},'Location','eastoutside');
title('Direction composition within ChAT and non-ChAT (grouped bars, colored by
Direction)');

% Color legend above
axBar = gca;
annotation('textbox', [axBar.Position(1) axBar.Position(2)+axBar.Position(4)+0.02 0.3
0.08], ...

```

```
'String', sprintf('Color legend: Down=orange-red NoChange=gray Up=blue'), ...
'EdgeColor','none', 'Color',[0 0 0], 'FontSize',10);
```

```
% Two pies (Direction uses fixed colors)
```

```
nexttile;
tt2 = tiledlayout(2,2,'Padding','compact','TileSpacing','compact');
title(tt2, 'Direction composition within groups (pies with values)');
```

```
% Color legend
```

```
axLegend2 = nexttile([1 2]); axis(axLegend2,'off'); hold(axLegend2,'on');
x0 = 0.02; y0 = 0.35; w = 0.04; h = 0.30; gap = 0.13;
rectangle(axLegend2,'Position',[x0 y0 w h],'FaceColor',col_dir(1,:),'EdgeColor','none');
text(axLegend2, x0+w+0.01, y0+0.15, 'Down', 'FontSize', 11, 'VerticalAlignment','middle');
rectangle(axLegend2,'Position',[x0+gap+0.22 y0 w
h],'FaceColor',col_dir(2,:),'EdgeColor','none');
text(axLegend2, x0+gap+0.22+w+0.01, y0+0.15, 'NoChange', 'FontSize', 11,
'VerticalAlignment','middle');
rectangle(axLegend2,'Position',[x0+2*(gap+0.22) y0 w
h],'FaceColor',col_dir(3,:),'EdgeColor','none');
text(axLegend2, x0+2*(gap+0.22)+w+0.01, y0+0.15, 'Up', 'FontSize', 11,
'VerticalAlignment','middle');
xlim(axLegend2,[0 1]); ylim(axLegend2,[0 1]);
```

```
% non-ChAT group pie
```

```
axL = nexttile;
if sum(c_non)==0
    ph1 = pie([1 0 0], {'Down','NoChange','Up'}); title('non-ChAT group (n=0)');
    htxt = ph1(2:2:end); set(htxt, 'Visible','off');
else
    ph1 = pie(c_non, {'Down','NoChange','Up'}); title(sprintf('non-ChAT group (n=%d)',
sum(c_non)));
    set(ph1(1),'FaceColor',col_dir(1,:)); set(ph1(3),'FaceColor',col_dir(2,:));
set(ph1(5),'FaceColor',col_dir(3,:));
    total = sum(c_non); htxt = ph1(2:2:end);
    for j = 1:numel(c_non)
        cnt = c_non(j); if cnt<=0, if isgraphics(htxt(j)), set(htxt(j),'Visible','off');
end; continue; end
        perc = 100*cnt/total; set(htxt(j),'String',sprintf('%d (%.1f%
%)',cnt,perc),'FontSize',9);
    end
end
```

```
% ChAT group pie
```

```
axR = nexttile;
if sum(c_ChAT)==0
    ph2 = pie([1 0 0], {'Down','NoChange','Up'}); title('ChAT group (n=0)');
    htxt = ph2(2:2:end); set(htxt, 'Visible','off');
else
    ph2 = pie(c_ChAT, {'Down','NoChange','Up'}); title(sprintf('ChAT group (n=%d)',
sum(c_ChAT)));
    set(ph2(1),'FaceColor',col_dir(1,:)); set(ph2(3),'FaceColor',col_dir(2,:));
set(ph2(5),'FaceColor',col_dir(3,:));
    total = sum(c_ChAT); htxt = ph2(2:2:end);
    for j = 1:numel(c_ChAT)
        cnt = c_ChAT(j); if cnt<=0, if isgraphics(htxt(j)), set(htxt(j),'Visible','off');
end; continue; end
        perc = 100*cnt/total; set(htxt(j),'String',sprintf('%d (%.1f%
%)',cnt,perc),'FontSize',9);
    end
end
```

```

%% ===== 4) Single-feature separability =====
% Auto-detect ptp_amp/ptd_amp
ampVar = '';
if ismember('ptd_amp', TBL.Properties.VariableNames)
    ampVar = 'ptd_amp';
elseif ismember('ptp_amp', TBL.Properties.VariableNames)
    ampVar = 'ptp_amp';
end

featVars =
{'FR_baseline_Hz', 'PTD_ms', 'W_FWHM_ms', 'slope_ratio', 'amp_asymmetry', 'neg_amp', 'pos_amp'};
if ~isempty(ampVar), featVars{end+1} = ampVar; end
featVars = featVars(ismember(featVars, TBL.Properties.VariableNames));

A1 = table('Size',[0 5], 'VariableTypes',{'string','double','double','double','double'}, ...
    'VariableNames',{'feature','AUC','d','mean_non','mean_ChAT'});

for i = 1:numel(featVars)
    f = featVars{i};
    x = TBL.(f);
    m = ~isnan(x) & ~isnan(Y_lab);
    xi = x(m); gi = Y_lab(m);
    x0 = xi(~gi); x1 = xi(gi);
    if numel(x0) < 5 || numel(x1) < 5, continue; end
    z = [x1; x0];
    gcat = [true(numel(x1),1); false(numel(x0),1)];
    r = tiedrank(z);
    R1 = sum(r(gcat)); n1 = numel(x1); n0 = numel(x0);
    AUC = (R1 - n1*(n1+1)/2) / (n1*n0);
    mu0 = mean(x0); mu1 = mean(x1);
    s0 = std(x0); s1 = std(x1);
    sp = sqrt(((numel(x0)-1)*s0^2 + (numel(x1)-1)*s1^2) / max(1,(numel(x0)+numel(x1)-2)));
    dval = (mu1 - mu0) / sp;
    A1 = [A1; {string(f), AUC, dval, mu0, mu1}]; %#ok<AGROW>
end
if ~isempty(A1)
    A1.sep = abs(A1.AUC - 0.5);
    A1 = sortrows(A1, 'sep', 'descend');
    disp('Single-feature separability ranking:');
    disp(A1(:, {'feature','AUC','d','mean_non','mean_ChAT'}));
end

%% ===== 5) 2D feature pair scoring =====
Y = Y_lab; % 1=ChAT, 0=non-ChAT
featPairs = nchoosek(1:numel(featVars), 2);
pairNames = strings(size(featPairs,1), 1);
CV_AUC = nan(size(featPairs,1),1);
NNR = nan(size(featPairs,1),1);

auc_score = @(scores,labels) ( ...
    (sum(tiedrank(scores(labels==1))) - sum(1:sum(labels==1))) ...
    / (sum(labels==1) * sum(labels==0) + eps) );

for k = 1:size(featPairs,1)
    i1 = featPairs(k,1); i2 = featPairs(k,2);
    f1 = featVars{i1}; f2 = featVars{i2};
    pairNames(k) = f1 + " x " + f2;

    x1 = TBL.(f1);
    x2 = TBL.(f2);
    M = ~isnan(x1) & ~isnan(x2) & ~isnan(Y);

```

```

X = [x1(M), x2(M)];
y = Y(M);

if nnz(y)==0 || nnz(~y)==0 || size(X,1) < 20
    continue
end

mu = mean(X,1); sig = std(X,[],1); sig(sig==0) = 1;
Xz = (X - mu) ./ sig;

try
    Kfold = min(5, max(2, floor(numel(y)/10)));
    cv = cvpartition(y,'Kfold',Kfold);
    scores_all = nan(size(y));
    for iFold = 1:cv.NumTestSets
        tr = training(cv, iFold);
        te = test(cv, iFold);
        mdl = fitclinear(Xz(tr,:), y(tr), 'Learner','logistic',
'Regularization','ridge', ...
        'ClassNames',[false true]);
        [~, score] = predict(mdl, Xz(te,:));
        if size(score,2) >= 2
            scores_all(te) = score(:,2);
        else
            scores_all(te) = score;
        end
    end
    CV_AUC(k) = auc_score(scores_all, y);
catch
    CV_AUC(k) = NaN;
end

try
    D = pdist2(Xz, Xz, 'euclidean');
    D(1:size(D,1)+1:end) = inf;
    [~, nnIdx] = min(D, [], 2);
    NNR(k) = mean(y(nnIdx) ~= y);
catch
    NNR(k) = NaN;
end
end

score = nan(size(CV_AUC));
validAUC = ~isnan(CV_AUC);
validNNR = ~isnan(NNR);

AUC_norm = nan(size(CV_AUC));
NNR_norm = nan(size(NNR));
if any(validAUC)
    a = CV_AUC(validAUC);
    AUC_norm(validAUC) = (a - min(a)) / max(eps, (max(a) - min(a)));
end
if any(validNNR)
    n = NNR(validNNR);
    NNR_norm(validNNR) = (n - min(n)) / max(eps, (max(n) - min(n)));
end

idx_both = validAUC & validNNR;
score(idx_both) = 0.7*AUC_norm(idx_both) + 0.3*(1 - NNR_norm(idx_both));
idx_onlyA = validAUC & ~validNNR;
if any(idx_onlyA)

```

```

    aa = CV_AUC(idx_onlyA);
    score(idx_onlyA) = (aa - min(aa)) / max(eps, max(aa) - min(aa));
end
idx_onlyN = validNNR & ~validAUC;
if any(idx_onlyN)
    nn = NNR(idx_onlyN);
    score(idx_onlyN) = 1 - (nn - min(nn)) / max(eps, max(nn) - min(nn));
end

PairTable = table(pairNames, CV_AUC, NNR, score, 'VariableNames',
{'pair','CV_AUC','NNR','score'});
PairTable = sortrows(PairTable, 'score', 'descend');
disp('2D feature pair scores (top 10):');
disp(PairTable(1:min(10,height(PairTable)), :));

%% ===== 6) Plot top 2D feature pairs (with Direction shape encoding) =====
Kpair = min(6, height(PairTable));
if Kpair > 0
    figure('Color','w','Position',[80 1160 1200 620]);
    tiledlayout(2, ceil(Kpair/2), 'Padding','compact','TileSpacing','compact');

    Y = Y_lab;
    dir_vals = string(TBL.Direction_std);

    dir_markers = struct('Down','v','NoChange','o','Up','^');

    for i = 1:Kpair
        nexttile; hold on; grid on;

        pn = PairTable.pair(i);
        parts = split(pn, " x ");
        f1 = strtrim(parts{1});
        f2 = strtrim(parts{2});

        x1 = TBL.(f1);
        x2 = TBL.(f2);

        hasDir = ~ismissing(dir_vals);
        M = ~isnan(x1) & ~isnan(x2) & ~isnan(Y) & hasDir;

        X = [x1(M), x2(M)];
        y = Y(M);
        d = dir_vals(M);

        mu = mean(X,1); sig = std(X,[],1); sig(sig==0)=1;
        Xz = (X - mu) ./ sig;

        XX = []; YY = []; S = [];
        try
            mdl = fitclinear(Xz, y, 'Learner','logistic', 'Regularization','ridge',
'ClassNames',[false true]);
            w = mdl.Beta; b0 = mdl.Bias;
            xr = linspace(min(X(:,1)), max(X(:,1)), 150);
            yr = linspace(min(X(:,2)), max(X(:,2)), 150);
            [XX,YY] = meshgrid(xr, yr);
            XXz = (XX - mu(1)) / sig(1);
            YYz = (YY - mu(2)) / sig(2);
            S = w(1)*XXz + w(2)*YYz + b0;
        catch
        end
    end

```

```

hPlot = struct;
for di = 1:numel(dir_order)
    dname = dir_order(di);
    mk = dir_markers.(dname);
    idx_d = d == dname;
    if ~any(idx_d), continue; end

    idx0 = idx_d & ~y;
    if any(idx0)
        hPlot.("non_"+dname) = scatter(X(idx0,1), X(idx0,2), 18, col_non, mk, ...
            'filled','MarkerFaceAlpha',0.50,'MarkerEdgeColor','none');
    end
    idx1 = idx_d & y;
    if any(idx1)
        hPlot.("cht_"+dname) = scatter(X(idx1,1), X(idx1,2), 24, col_cht, mk, ...
            'filled','MarkerFaceAlpha',0.85,'MarkerEdgeColor','none');
    end
end

if ~isempty(S)
    contour(XX, YY, S, [0 0], 'r-', 'LineWidth',1.2);
end

xlabel(f1, 'Interpreter','none');
ylabel(f2, 'Interpreter','none');
ttl = sprintf('%s\nscore=%.3f | AUC=%.3f | NNR=%.3f', ...
    PairTable.pair(i), PairTable.CV_AUC(i), PairTable.CV_AUC(i), PairTable.NNR(i));
title(ttl, 'Interpreter','none');

legendItems = {};
legendHandles = [];
for dname = dir_order
    fld = "non_"+dname;
    if isfield(hPlot, fld)
        legendHandles(end+1) = hPlot.(fld);
        legendItems{end+1} = sprintf('non-ChAT-%s', dname);
    end
end
for dname = dir_order
    fld = "cht_"+dname;
    if isfield(hPlot, fld)
        legendHandles(end+1) = hPlot.(fld);
        legendItems{end+1} = sprintf('ChAT-%s', dname);
    end
end
if ~isempty(S)
    hB = plot(NaN,NaN, 'r-', 'LineWidth',1.2);
    legendHandles(end+1) = hB;
    legendItems{end+1} = 'Linear boundary';
end
if ~isempty(legendHandles)
    legend(legendHandles, legendItems, 'Location','bestoutside');
end
end
end

%%
function stim_info = batch_get_stim_info(rootDir, recursive)
% ----- Input arguments and defaults -----
if nargin < 1 || isempty(rootDir)
    rootDir = 'G:\A-B-D';

```

```

end
if nargin < 2 || isempty(recursive)
    recursive = true;
end
if ~isfolder(rootDir)
    error('rootDir does not exist: %s', rootDir);
end

% ----- Detection parameters (tune as needed) -----
thr_on = 3000;
thr_off = 2900;
minWidth_samp = 2;
maxWidth_samp = 20;
refractory_samp = 40;
minHold_samp = 4;
needLowCount = 2;
useSubSample = true;

% Scoring reference (for selecting best channel; does not affect final output fields)
targetISI_ms = 50;
targetWidth_ms = [3 7];

% Pack parameters
params = struct('thr_on',thr_on,'thr_off',thr_off,'minWidth_samp',minWidth_samp, ...
    'maxWidth_samp',maxWidth_samp,'refractory_samp',refractory_samp, ...
    'minHold_samp',minHold_samp,'needLowCount',needLowCount, ...
    'useSubSample',useSubSample);

% ----- Collect files -----
files = listNexFiles(rootDir, recursive);
stim_info = struct('filename',{},'channelName',{},'t_on',{},'t_off',{},'delta_t',{});
if isempty(files)
    warning('No .nex files found in %s.', rootDir);
    return;
end

% ----- Environment checks -----
if exist('readNexFile','file') ~= 2
    error('Function readNexFile not found. Please add it to MATLAB path.');
```

```

    fprintf('%d/%d] %s -> %s, n=%d\n', i, numel(files), fpath, ...
            ternary(ok,string(det.name),"N/A"), numel(det.t_on));

catch ME
    stim_info(end+1) = struct('filename', fpath, 'channelName', '', ...
        't_on', [], 't_off', [], 'delta_t', []); %#ok<AGROW>
    fprintf(2, '%d/%d] Failed: %s | %s\n', i, numel(files), fpath, ME.message);
end
end

end % main

function [groupNeuron,groupLFP] = extractNeuLFP(filename, dataKey, paramsExtr)

idx = 1; % idx: index for wanted neurons

groupNeu = [];
groupLFP = [];
% Save spike/events/waveform or not
addSpike = sum(strcmp(dataKey, 'spike'));
addEvents = sum(strcmp(dataKey, 'events'));
addWaveform = sum(strcmp(dataKey, 'waveform'));
addAI = sum(strcmp(dataKey, 'AI'));
filPerChl = paramsExtr.filPerChl;
exEvt = paramsExtr.exEvt;
evtFrom = paramsExtr.eventsFrom;
getEvt = paramsExtr.getEvents;
bestNlfp = paramsExtr.bestNlfp;

chnl = paramsExtr.chnl;
regionToLoad = paramsExtr.regionToLoad;
regionPos = cellfun(@(x) any(strcmp(x,regionToLoad)),chnl(:,1));

for i = 1:length(filename) % i: index for nex files

    tempPath = filename(i).folder;
    tempLabel = strsplit(tempPath, '/');
    % For each loop, reading only one nexfile to tempData
    if strcmp(filename(i).name(end),'5')
        curNex = readNex5File([tempPath, '/', filename(i).name]);
    else
        curNex = readNexFile([tempPath, '/', filename(i).name]);
    end
    % find the serial number of the animal and the date of experiment
    tempDate = filename(i).name(1:8);
    %tempAnimal = regexpi(filename(i).name,['#v-]\d\d\d\d','match');
    % tempAnimal = tempAnimal{1}(2:5);

matchResult = regexpi(filename(i).name, '#v\d{4}-\d', 'match');

if ~isempty(matchResult)
    % Ensure result is a string, then take substring from char 2 to 7
    tempAnimal = matchResult{1}(2:min(7, end)); % use min to avoid exceeding string length
else
    tempAnimal = ''; % default if no match
end

% extract LFPs
% get continuous variables for LFPs into 'curLFP'
getLFP = any(strcmpi(dataKey, 'LFP'));

```

```

if getLFP
    try
        curContvars = [curNex.contvars{:,1}];
    catch
        disp(['lack LFP ',filename(i).name]);
        getLFP = false;
    end
end
if getLFP
    LFPpos = cellfun(@(x) contains(x,'FP'),{curContvars.name});
    curLFP = curContvars(LFPpos);
    % find regions where LFP channels belong
    curLFPchnl = cellfun(@(x) str2double(x(5:6)),{curLFP.name});
    curRegPos = cellfun(@(x) ismember(curLFPchnl,x),chnl(:,2),'UniformOutput',false);
    curRegPos2 = regionPos & cell2mat(curRegPos);
    [channelPos,idxReg] = max(curRegPos2); % channelPos: the logical array indicating
whether
    curLFPreg = chnl(idxReg,1);
    curLFPreg = curLFPreg(channelPos);
    curLFP = [curLFP(channelPos).data];
    % save average LFP waveforms for bestNlfp LFPs in each region
    tempReg = unique(curLFPreg);
    if ~isempty(tempReg)
        for kr = 1:length(tempReg) % this loop goes through the brain regions for LFP
            rgLFP = curLFP(:,strcmp(tempReg(kr),curLFPreg));
            bestLfpIdx = findBestLFP(rgLFP(1000:150:end,:),bestNlfp);
            tempLFP(kr).waveform = mean(rgLFP(:,bestLfpIdx),2);
            tempLFP(kr).region = tempReg{kr};
        end
        groupLFP(i).animal = tempAnimal;
        groupLFP(i).date = tempDate;
        groupLFP(i).record = erase(filename(i).name(1:end-4),'');
        groupLFP(i).LFPs = tempLFP;
    end
end

% extract waveform and timestamp information of neurons and AI
try
    curWave = [curNex.waves{:,1}];
catch
    disp(['error finding waves:',filename(i).name]);
    continue
end
curName = {curWave.name};
% AI is the channel for opto stimulation. It may affect all neurons.
AIpos = cellfun(@(x) contains(x,'AI')&contains(x,'wf'),curName);
curAI = curWave(AIpos);
templatePos = find(cellfun(@(x) contains(x,'template')&contains(x,'SPK'),curName));
wfPos = find(cellfun(@(x) contains(x,'wf')&contains(x,'SPK'), curName));
if isempty(wfPos)
    continue
end
neuronID = cellfun(@(x) x(end-5:end-3),curName(wfPos),'UniformOutput',false);
curNeuChnl = cellfun(@(x) str2double(x(1:2)),neuronID);

curRegPos = cellfun(@(x) ismember(curNeuChnl,x),chnl(:,2),'UniformOutput',false);
curRegPos2 = regionPos & cell2mat(curRegPos);
[channelPos,idxReg] = max(curRegPos2);
curNeuReg = chnl(idxReg,1);
wfPos = wfPos(channelPos);
if any(templatePos)

```

```

    templatePos = templatePos(channelPos);
end

% put data of the current file into tempTrialData
idxpost = idx + length(wfPos) - 1;
if idxpost >= idx
    [groupNeu(idx:idxpost).neuronID] = neuronID{channelPos};
    curNeuChnl = num2cell(curNeuChnl);
    [groupNeu(idx:idxpost).channel] = curNeuChnl{channelPos};
    [groupNeu(idx:idxpost).region] = curNeuReg{channelPos};
    [groupNeu(idx:idxpost).date] = deal(tempDate);
    [groupNeu(idx:idxpost).animal] = deal(tempAnimal);
    tempName = cellfun(@(x) erase([filename(i).name(1:end-4) '_'
x], '.'), neuronID(channelPos), 'UniformOutput', false);
    [groupNeu(idx:idxpost).name] = tempName{:};
    [groupNeu(idx:idxpost).record] = deal(erase(filename(i).name(1:end-4), '.'));
    [groupNeu(idx:idxpost).label] = deal(tempLabel{end});
    if addWaveform
        templates = {curWave(wfPos).waveforms}; % else, use the mean of spike
waveforms as templates
        [groupNeu(idx:idxpost).Allwaveform] = templates{:};
        templates = cellfun(@(x) mean(x,2), templates, 'UniformOutput', false);
        % select the template from the filaments that got signals of largest
        % amplitude as the final template
        if length(templates{1}) > 56
            pointPerFil = length(templates{1})/filPerChl;
        else
            pointPerFil = length(templates{1});
            disp(['Only one channel in ', groupNeu(idx).record]);
        end
        bestFilaments = cellfun(@(x) ceil(find(x==min(x))/
pointPerFil), templates, 'UniformOutput', false);
        try
            bestTemplates = cellfun(@(x,y) x(1+
(y-1)*pointPerFil:y*pointPerFil), templates, bestFilaments, 'UniformOutput', false);
        catch
            bestTemplates = [];
            display(['error finding templates:', filename(i).name]);
        end
        [groupNeu(idx:idxpost).waveform] = bestTemplates{:};
    end
    if addSpike
        [groupNeu(idx:idxpost).spike] = curWave(wfPos).timestamps;
    end
    if addAI
        [groupNeu(idx:idxpost).AI] = deal({curAI.timestamps});
    end
    if addEvents
        if any(strcmp(evtFrom, 'nex'))
            cEventsNex = curNex.events;
            for kevt = 1:length(cEventsNex)
                cEventsNex{kevt}.condition = [];
                if isfield(cEventsNex{kevt}, 'varNex5Version')
                    cEventsNex{kevt} = rmfield(cEventsNex{kevt}, 'varNex5Version');
                end
                if isfield(cEventsNex{kevt}, 'varVersion')
                    cEventsNex{kevt} = rmfield(cEventsNex{kevt}, 'varVersion');
                end
            end
        else
            cEventsNex = cell(0,0);
        end
    end
end

```

```

end
if any(strcmp(evtFrom, 'exl'))
    evtTemp = exEvt(strcmp({exEvt.date}, tempDate) &
strcmp({exEvt.animal}, tempAnimal));
    nCond = length(evtTemp);
    nEvt = length(getEvt);
    cEventsExl = cell(nEvt*nCond, 1);
    for kcond = 1:nCond
        for kevt = 1:nEvt
            idxEvt = (kcond-1)*nEvt + kevt;
            cEventsExl{idxEvt}.name = getEvt{kevt};
            cEventsExl{idxEvt}.timestamps = evtTemp(kcond).(getEvt{kevt});
            cEventsExl{idxEvt}.condition = evtTemp(kcond).condition;
        end
    end
else
    cEventsExl = cell(0, 0);
end
cEvents = [cEventsNex; cEventsExl];
dim = size(cEvents);
cEvents = reshape(cEvents, max(dim), min(dim));
if any(AIpos)
    tempLightPos = cellfun(@(x) strcmpi(x.name, 'light'), cEvents);
    cEvents(tempLightPos) = [];
    tempLightPos = length(cEvents)+1;
    cEvents{tempLightPos} = struct('name', 'light', 'timestamps', [], 'condition',
[]);

    for kAI = 1:length(curAI)
        diffAI = reshape(diff(curAI(kAI).timestamps), 1, []);
        diffAIpos = [0, find(diffAI>1), length(diffAI)+1];
        for kAITrial = 1:length(diffAIpos)-1
            cEvents{tempLightPos}.timestamps(end+1, 1) =
curAI(kAI).timestamps(diffAIpos(kAITrial)+1); % start time
            cEvents{tempLightPos}.timestamps(end, 2) =
curAI(kAI).timestamps(diffAIpos(kAITrial+1)); % stop time
            cEvents{tempLightPos}.timestamps(end, 3)
= diff(cEvents{tempLightPos}.timestamps(end, 1:2))/(diffAIpos(kAITrial+1)-
diffAIpos(kAITrial)-1); % period (1/f)
        end
    end
    [groupNeu(idx:idxpost).events] = deal(cell2mat(cEvents));
end
idx = idxpost+1;
end

end

groupNeuron.TrialData = groupNeu;
end

function [templates, eventInfo, splitIdx] = processStereotrodeUnit(W, fs, params)

if nargin < 2 || isempty(fs), fs = 40000; end
if nargin < 3, params = struct(); end
p = fillParams(params);

% Basic dimensions and split wires
[S, m] = size(W);
assert(mod(S, p.filPerChl)==0, 'Row length must be multiple of filPerChl.');
```

```

M = S / p.filPerCh1;
ch1 = W(1:M, :);
ch2 = W(M+1:end, :);

% Unify polarity: assume negative peak is principal. If average polarity is positive,
flip.
if mean(min(ch1)) > 0, ch1 = -ch1; end
if mean(min(ch2)) > 0, ch2 = -ch2; end

% Per-event features
[A1, p1] = getPeakAndPos(ch1, p.useParabFit);
[A2, p2] = getPeakAndPos(ch2, p.useParabFit);

% Main wire selection (by amplitude) and reference peak position
useCh1 = A1 >= A2;
mainCh = 2*ones(1,m); mainCh(useCh1) = 1;
pref = p2; pref(useCh1) = p1(useCh1);

% Quality and discrepancy metrics
dt = abs(p1 - p2) / fs;
ratio = A1 ./ max(A2, eps);
logR = log(ratio);
logRz = robustZ(logR);

% Cross-correlation between wires (window around main peak)
win = localWin(M, pref, fs);
xc12 = zeros(1,m);
for i = 1:m
    seg1 = ch1(win(i,1):win(i,2), i);
    seg2 = ch2(win(i,1):win(i,2), i);
    xc12(i) = corrN(seg1, seg2);
end

% Edge and suspect flags
isEdge = (pref <= p.edgeSafe) | (pref >= M - p.edgeSafe);
isSuspect = (dt > p.dtThr) | (xc12 < p.xcThr) | (abs(logRz) > p.ratioZThr) | isEdge;

% Stage 1: build main template from main wire and compute similarity (no split)
% Align: coarsely align by each event's main-wire peak, then take median as template
(robust)
[tplMain, xc_main, mainWireIdx] = buildMainWireTemplate(ch1, ch2, mainCh);

% Estimate bi-wire template using non-suspect events (same as original logic)
keep = ~isSuspect;
if ~any(keep)
    warning('All events marked suspect; falling back to all for template.');
```

```

    keep = true(1,m);
end
tpl1 = mean(ch1(:, keep), 2);
tpl2 = mean(ch2(:, keep), 2);

templates.best = [tpl1(:)'; tpl2(:)'];
templates.perCh = {tpl1(:), tpl2(:)};
templates.main = struct('wire', mainWireIdx, 'tpl', tplMain(:), 'xc_main', xc_main);

% Stage 2: attempt split (only if necessary conditions are met), with strong validation
% 2.1 Candidate split
[assignAB_cand, distA, distB] = assignByTemplates(ch1, ch2, tpl1, tpl2);
needSplitCand = shouldSplit(distA, distB, isSuspect);

% 2.2 Necessary conditions: sample size and group size
```

```

minSize = max(p.minGroupSize, ceil(p.minGroupFrac * m));
meetsSize = m >= p.minN;

% 2.3 If both met, iterate to refine templates and get candidate assignment
templates.split = {};
assignAB = repmat('A', 1, m);
if needSplitCand && meetsSize
    for iter = 1:2
        Aidx = assignAB_cand == 'A';
        Bidx = assignAB_cand == 'B';
        if any(Aidx)
            tmp1A = mean(ch1(:, Aidx), 2);
            tmp2A = mean(ch2(:, Aidx), 2);
        else
            tmp1A = tmp1; tmp2A = tmp2;
        end
        if any(Bidx)
            tmp1B = mean(ch1(:, Bidx), 2);
            tmp2B = mean(ch2(:, Bidx), 2);
        else
            tmp1B = tmp1; tmp2B = tmp2;
        end
        [assignAB_cand, distA, distB] = assignByTemplates(ch1, ch2, tmp1A, tmp2A,
tmp1B, tmp2B);
    end

% 2.4 Strong validation
Aidx = find(assignAB_cand=='A');
Bidx = find(assignAB_cand=='B');
accept = validateSplit(ch1, ch2, Aidx, Bidx, p);

% 2.5 Minimum group size
if numel(Aidx) < minSize || numel(Bidx) < minSize
    accept = false;
end

if accept
    assignAB = assignAB_cand;
    templates.split = { [mean(ch1(:,Aidx),2)'; mean(ch2(:,Aidx),2)'], ...
                        [mean(ch1(:,Bidx),2)'; mean(ch2(:,Bidx),2)'] };
    if p.verbose
        fprintf('[split] ACCEPT: m=%d | A=%d, B=%d\n', m, numel(Aidx), numel(Bidx));
    end
else
    if p.verbose
        fprintf('[split] REJECT: m=%d | A=%d, B=%d\n', m, numel(Aidx), numel(Bidx));
    end
end
else
    if p.verbose
        fprintf('[split] SKIP: needSplit=%d, meetsSize=%d, m=%d\n', needSplitCand,
meetsSize, m);
    end
end

% Output event info
eventInfo = struct( ...
    'A1', num2cell(A1), 'A2', num2cell(A2), ...
    'p1', num2cell(p1), 'p2', num2cell(p2), ...
    'mainCh', num2cell(mainCh), 'pref', num2cell(pref), ...
    'dt', num2cell(dt), 'ratio', num2cell(ratio), ...

```

```

        'logRatioZ', num2cell(logRz), 'xc', num2cell(xc12), ...
        'isEdge', num2cell(isEdge), 'isSuspect', num2cell(isSuspect), ...
        'xc_main', num2cell(xc_main) ...
    );

    if ~isempty(templates.split)
        assign = assignAB;
    else
        assign = repmat('A', 1, m);
    end
    for i = 1:m
        eventInfo(i).assign = assign(i);
    end

    splitIdx.A = find(assign=='A');
    splitIdx.B = find(assign=='B');
end

function p = fillParams(p)
    def.filPerChl = 2;
    def.dtThr = 0.0002; % 0.2 ms
    def.xcThr = 0.5;
    def.ratioZThr = 3;
    def.edgeSafe = 3; % samples
    def.minPeakSep= 8; % samples
    def.useParabFit = true;
    % conservative split defaults
    def.minN = 60;
    def.minGroupSize = 20;
    def.minGroupFrac = 0.05;
    def.xc_reject = 0.85;
    def.energyFrac_reject = 0.10;
    def.requireWithinImprove = 0.05;
    def.verbose = false;

    f = fieldnames(def);
    for k = 1:numel(f)
        if ~isfield(p, f{k}) || isempty(p.(f{k}))
            p.(f{k}) = def.(f{k});
        end
    end
end

function [A, pos] = getPeakAndPos(X, useParab)
    [mins, posI] = min(X, [], 1);
    A = -mins; % negative peak magnitude as positive
    pos = posI;
    if useParab
        [M, m] = size(X);
        pos = double(posI);
        for i = 1:m
            p0 = posI(i);
            if p0>1 && p0<M
                y1 = X(p0-1,i); y2 = X(p0,i); y3 = X(p0+1,i);
                denom = (y1 - 2*y2 + y3);
                if abs(denom) > eps
                    delta = 0.5*(y1 - y3)/denom; % -1..1
                    pos(i) = p0 + delta;
                end
            end
        end
    end
end

```

```

    end
end

function z = robustZ(x)
    mu = median(x);
    s = 1.4826*median(abs(x - mu)) + eps;
    z = (x - mu) / s;
end

function r = corrN(a, b)
    a = a(:); b = b(:);
    a = a - mean(a); b = b - mean(b);
    na = norm(a); nb = norm(b);
    if na==0 || nb==0
        r = 0;
    else
        r = (a'*b)/(na*nb);
    end
end

function win = localWin(M, pref, fs)
% Build a local window around each event for cross-correlation, ~0.6 ms
    half = round(0.3e-3 * fs); % 0.3 ms
    half = max(6, half);
    n = numel(pref);
    win = zeros(n,2);
    for i = 1:n
        p = round(min(max(pref(i),1),M));
        s = max(1, p - half);
        e = min(M, p + half);
        win(i,:) = [s, e];
    end
end

function [assign, distA, distB] = assignByTemplates(ch1, ch2, templ1A, templ2A, templ1B,
templ2B)
    if nargin < 5
        templ1B = templ1A; templ2B = templ2A;
    end
    [~, m] = size(ch1);
    distA = zeros(1,m);
    distB = zeros(1,m);
    T1A = templ1A(:); T2A = templ2A(:);
    T1B = templ1B(:); T2B = templ2B(:);
    for i = 1:m
        x1 = ch1(:,i); x2 = ch2(:,i);
        a1A = projScale(x1, T1A); a2A = projScale(x2, T2A);
        a1B = projScale(x1, T1B); a2B = projScale(x2, T2B);
        distA(i) = norm(x1 - a1A*T1A)^2 + norm(x2 - a2A*T2A)^2;
        distB(i) = norm(x1 - a1B*T1B)^2 + norm(x2 - a2B*T2B)^2;
    end
    assign = repmat('A', 1, m);
    assign(distB < distA) = 'B';
end

function a = projScale(x, t)
    denom = (t'*t);
    if denom < eps
        a = 0;
    else
        a = (t'*x)/denom;
    end
end

```

```

end
end

function need = shouldSplit(distA, distB, isSuspect)
    dDiff = distA - distB;
    med = median(dDiff);
    hi = dDiff >= med; lo = ~hi;
    if any(hi) && any(lo)
        sep = abs(median(dDiff(hi)) - median(dDiff(lo)));
        spread = 1.4826*median(abs(dDiff - med)) + eps;
        sepZ = sep / spread;
    else
        sepZ = 0;
    end
    susFrac = mean(isSuspect);
    need = (sepZ > 2.5 && mean(hi) > 0.2 && mean(lo) > 0.2) || (susFrac > 0.25);
end

function [tplMain, xc_main, mainWireIdx] = buildMainWireTemplate(ch1, ch2, mainCh)
% Build robust main template (median) from main wire per event, and compute similarity
[M, m] = size(ch1);
% Select main-wire waveform per event
X = zeros(M, m);
for i = 1:m
    if mainCh(i) == 1
        X(:,i) = ch1(:,i);
    else
        X(:,i) = ch2(:,i);
    end
end
% No sub-sample fine alignment here; coarse by peak already used in pref
tplMain = median(X, 2); % more robust
% Similarity per event
xc_main = zeros(1, m);
for i = 1:m
    xc_main(i) = corrN(X(:,i), tplMain);
end
% Main wire overall: which wire has larger average energy
e1 = mean(sum(ch1.^2,1));
e2 = mean(sum(ch2.^2,1));
mainWireIdx = (e1 >= e2) + 1; % e1>=e2 -> 2? fix below
if e1 >= e2
    mainWireIdx = 1;
else
    mainWireIdx = 2;
end
end

function accept = validateSplit(ch1, ch2, Aidx, Bidx, p)
% Strong validation: template cross-corr, energy difference, within-cluster improvement,
size, etc.
if isempty(Aidx) || isempty(Bidx)
    accept = false; return;
end
% A/B templates
t1A = mean(ch1(:,Aidx),2); t2A = mean(ch2(:,Aidx),2);
t1B = mean(ch1(:,Bidx),2); t2B = mean(ch2(:,Bidx),2);

% 1) Template cross-correlation (compute per wire and take max)
xcA1B1 = corrN(t1A, t1B);
xcA2B2 = corrN(t2A, t2B);

```

```

xcAB = max(xcA1B1, xcA2B2);

% 2) Energy difference fraction
EA = sum(t1A.^2) + sum(t2A.^2);
EB = sum(t1B.^2) + sum(t2B.^2);
dEfrac = abs(EA - EB) / max(EA, EB);

% 3) Within-cluster similarity improvement
% Combined templates (overall)
t1All = mean([ch1(:,Aidx), ch1(:,Bidx)], 2);
t2All = mean([ch2(:,Aidx), ch2(:,Bidx)], 2);

xc_in_A = meanColCorr(ch1(:,Aidx), t1A) + meanColCorr(ch2(:,Aidx), t2A);
xc_in_A = xc_in_A / 2;
xc_in_B = meanColCorr(ch1(:,Bidx), t1B) + meanColCorr(ch2(:,Bidx), t2B);
xc_in_B = xc_in_B / 2;
xc_in_all = meanColCorr([ch1(:,Aidx), ch1(:,Bidx)], t1All) + ...
             meanColCorr([ch2(:,Aidx), ch2(:,Bidx)], t2All);
xc_in_all = xc_in_all / 2;

deltaWithin = (xc_in_A + xc_in_B)/2 - xc_in_all;

% Criteria
accept = true;
if xcAB > p.xc_reject
    accept = false; % templates too similar
end
if dEfrac < p.energyFrac_reject
    accept = false; % energy diff too small
end
if deltaWithin < p.requireWithinImprove
    accept = false; % within-cluster improvement insufficient
end
end

function v = meanColCorr(X, t)
% Mean correlation between each column and template t
[~, m] = size(X);
v = 0;
for i = 1:m
    v = v + corrN(X(:,i), t);
end
v = v / max(1,m);
end

function s = ensureStructFields(s, baseFields)
% Ensure s contains all fields in baseFields; fill missing with [];
% extra fields are kept; reorder to baseFields
sFields = fieldnames(s);
missing = setdiff(baseFields, sFields);
for i = 1:numel(missing)
    s.(missing{i}) = [];
end
if ~isempty(setxor(fieldnames(s), baseFields))
    core = orderfields(s, baseFields);
    s = core;
else
    s = orderfields(s, baseFields);
end
end

```

```

function [axList, shownMask] = preview_meanwaveforms(TD, titlePrefix, srcName, linkY)
    N = numel(TD);
    nRows = ceil(sqrt(N));
    nCols = ceil(N / nRows);
    f = figure('Color','w','Name',sprintf('%s (%s) - total %d', titlePrefix, srcName, N));
%#ok<NASGU>
    tl = tiledlayout(nRows, nCols, 'TileSpacing','compact','Padding','compact');
    axList = gobjects(1, N);
    shownMask = false(1, N);

    for i = 1:N
        nexttile;
        ax = gca;
        axList(i) = ax;

        mw = [];

        % 1) Prefer meanWaveform_good
        if isfield(TD, 'meanWaveform_good') && ~isempty(TD(i).meanWaveform_good)
            mw = TD(i).meanWaveform_good;

        % 2) Fallback to meanWaveform
        elseif isfield(TD, 'meanWaveform') && ~isempty(TD(i).meanWaveform)
            mw = TD(i).meanWaveform;

        % 3) Then fallback to Allwaveform (per your original logic)
        elseif isfield(TD, 'Allwaveform') && ~isempty(TD(i).Allwaveform)
            W = TD(i).Allwaveform;
            if iscell(W), W = W{1}; end
            if isnumeric(W) && size(W,1)==112 && ~isempty(W)
                mw = [mean(W(1:56,:),2); mean(W(57:112,:),2)];
            elseif isnumeric(W) && size(W,1)==56 && ~isempty(W)
                mw = mean(W,2);
            end
        end

        if isempty(mw)
            text(0.5,0.5,'No waveform','HorizontalAlignment','center', ...
                'VerticalAlignment','middle','Color',[0.7 0 0],'FontWeight','bold');
            axis off;
            title(sprintf('#%d', i), 'FontSize', 9);
            continue;
        end

        hold on;
        % Support vector or matrix: if row vector, transpose to column
        if isrow(mw), mw = mw.'; end

        % If mw is 112x1 (two filaments concatenated), plot per original colors; else plot
        per column
        if size(mw,1)==112 && size(mw,2)==1
            plot(mw(1:56), 'b-', 'LineWidth', 1.3);
            plot(mw(57:112), 'r-', 'LineWidth', 1.3);
        elseif size(mw,1)==56 && size(mw,2)==2
            % meanWaveform_good might be 56x2 (two filaments as columns)
            plot(mw(:,1), 'b-', 'LineWidth', 1.3);
            plot(mw(:,2), 'r-', 'LineWidth', 1.3);
        else
            % Otherwise: plot each column
            K = size(mw,2);
            cmap = lines(K);

```

```

    for k = 1:K
        plot(mw(:,k), 'Color', cmap(k,:), 'LineWidth', 1.3);
    end
    if K>1
        legend(arrayfun(@(k) sprintf('Ch%d',k), 1:K, 'UniformOutput', false), ...
                'Box','off','Location','bestoutside');
    end
    end
    grid on; hold off;

    if isfield(TD,'neuronID') && ~isempty(TD(i).neuronID)
        title(sprintf('#%d | %s', i, string(TD(i).neuronID)), ...
                'Interpreter','none','FontSize',9);
    else
        title(sprintf('#%d', i), 'FontSize',9);
    end
    xlabel('Samples'); ylabel('Amplitude');
    shownMask(i) = true;
end

title(tl, sprintf('%s (%s) - total %d', titlePrefix, srcName, N), 'FontWeight','bold');

if linkY
    try, linkaxes(axList(isgraphics(axList)), 'y'); catch, end
end
end

```

```

function counts = count_in_intervals(win_starts, win_ends, spikes)

```

```

    % Shapes and robustness

```

```

    win_starts = win_starts(:);
    win_ends   = win_ends(:);
    spikes     = spikes(:);

```

```

    if numel(win_starts) ~= numel(win_ends)
        error('win_starts and win_ends must have the same length');
    end

```

```

    if ~issorted(spikes)
        spikes = sort(spikes, 'ascend');
    end

```

```

    % Handle abnormal windows: end <= start -> zero length, count = 0
    bad = ~(isfinite(win_starts) & isfinite(win_ends)) | (win_ends <= win_starts);
    win_ends(bad) = win_starts(bad);

```

```

    % Binary search to locate first index with x >= boundary
    idx_s = first_ge(spikes, win_starts);
    idx_e = first_ge(spikes, win_ends);

```

```

    counts = idx_e - idx_s;

```

```

end

```

```

function idx = first_ge(x, q)

```

```

%FIRST_GE Return the index of the first x >= q for each q; returns numel(x)+1 if none

```

```

    x = x(:);
    q = q(:);
    n = numel(x);
    lo = ones(size(q));           % lower bound (inclusive)
    hi = repmat(n+1, size(q)); % upper bound (exclusive)

```

```

    while true
        mid = floor((lo + hi)/2);

```

```

    if all(hi - lo <= 1)
        break;
    end
    xv = x(mid);
    goRight = xv < q;    % if x(mid) < q, answer lies to the right
    lo(goRight) = mid(goRight);
    hi(~goRight) = mid(~goRight);
end
idx = hi;
end

% ===== Local functions (must be at end of script) =====
function is_norm = local_test_normality(x, use_jb)
    x = x(:);
    x = x(~isnan(x));
    if numel(x) < 8
        is_norm = false; return;
    end
    if use_jb
        try
            [h, ~] = jbstest(x, 0.05);
            is_norm = (h == 0);
            return;
        catch
            % fall through to Lilliefors
        end
    end
    s = std(x);
    if ~isfinite(s) || s == 0
        is_norm = false;
        return;
    end
    xz = (x - mean(x)) / s;
    try
        [h, ~] = kstest(xz); % h=1 reject normality
        is_norm = (h == 0);
    catch
        is_norm = false;
    end
end

function eqv = local_test_equal_variance(x, y, method)
    x = x(:); y = y(:);
    x = x(~isnan(x)); y = y(~isnan(y));
    if numel(x) < 8 || numel(y) < 8
        eqv = false; return;
    end
    switch lower(method)
        case 'vartest2'
            try
                [h, ~] = vartest2(x, y, 'Alpha', 0.05);
                eqv = (h == 0);
            catch
                eqv = false;
            end
        otherwise
            % Simple Levene-like test (median-based)
            mx = median(x); my = median(y);
            zx = abs(x - mx); zy = abs(y - my);
            try
                p = ranksum(zx, zy, 'tail', 'both');
            end
        end
    end
end

```

```

        eqv = (p > 0.05);
    catch
        eqv = false;
    end
end
end

function q = local_bh_fdr(p)
    p = p(:);
    p(~isfinite(p)) = 1;
    [ps, idx] = sort(p);
    m = numel(p);
    qtmp = (m./(1:m)') .* ps;
    qtmp = flipud(cummin(flipud(qtmp)));
    q = nan(size(p));
    q(idx) = min(1, qtmp);
end

% ----- Helper: parse indices -----
function idx = parse_indices(strIn)
% Support space/comma/semicolon separators, and a:b and a:s:b ranges
    strIn = char(strIn);
    strIn = strrep(strIn, ';', ' ');
    strIn = strrep(strIn, ',', ' ');
    parts = strsplit(strtrim(strIn));
    idx = [];
    for k = 1:numel(parts)
        tok = strtrim(parts{k});
        if isempty(tok), continue; end
        if contains(tok, ':')
            nums = str2double(split(tok, ':'));
            nums = nums(~isnan(nums));
            if numel(nums) == 2
                a = nums(1); b = nums(2);
                if a <= b, seq = a:b; else, seq = a:-1:b; end
                idx = [idx, seq]; %#ok<AGROW>
            elseif numel(nums) == 3
                a = nums(1); s = nums(2); b = nums(3);
                if isfinite(a) && isfinite(s) && isfinite(b) && s ~= 0
                    idx = [idx, a:s:b]; %#ok<AGROW>
                end
            end
        else
            v = str2double(tok);
            if ~isnan(v), idx = [idx, v]; end %#ok<AGROW>
        end
    end
    % Deduplicate preserving order
    [~, ia] = unique(idx, 'stable');
    idx = idx(sort(ia));
end

% Tscored = score_PIN_ChAT_15ms(Tnew, 'pin_chat_15ms_model.mat');
function Tnew = score_PIN_ChAT_15ms(Tnew, modelPath)
    S = load(modelPath, 'pin15_model'); M = S.pin15_model;
    waveCols = M.waveCols;
    miss = waveCols(~ismember(waveCols, Tnew.Properties.VariableNames));
    assert(isempty(miss), 'New data missing columns: %s', strjoin(miss, ', '));

    Xr = Tnew{:, waveCols};
    for j = 1:size(Xr,2)

```

```
col = Xr(:,j);
if any(isnan(col))
    med = median(col(~isnan(col)));
    if isempty(med) || isnan(med), med = 0; end
    col(isnan(col)) = med;
    Xr(:,j) = col;
end
end
sd = M.sd_base; sd(sd==0)=1;
Xz = (Xr - M.mu_base) ./ sd;

[~, Sscr] = predict(M.mdl, Xz);
p = 1 ./ (1 + exp(-Sscr(:,2)));
Tnew.p_PIN_ChAT = p;
Tnew.isPIN_ChAT_candidate = p >= M.th_opt;
end
```

```

clear; clc; close all;
% Adapted for PPN_PIN

%% 1) Add code paths
mainCodeDir = 'C:\Users\Lu\Desktop\Fig_Code\PPN_PIN'; % Main script directory
funcCodeDir = 'C:\Users\Lu\Desktop\Fig_Code\Function'; % Function directory (unchanged)

% Add main script directory to path
if isfolder(mainCodeDir)
    addpath(genpath(mainCodeDir));
    fprintf('Main script path added: %s\n', mainCodeDir);
else
    warning('Main script directory not found: %s (will continue, but scripts may be missing)', mainCodeDir);
end

% Add function directory to path
if isfolder(funcCodeDir)
    addpath(genpath(funcCodeDir));
    fprintf('Function path added: %s\n', funcCodeDir);
else
    warning('Function directory not found: %s (will continue, but functions may be missing)', funcCodeDir);
end

%% 2) Select data folder (as datapath)
% Set initial browse location to main script dir, fallback to Desktop or C:\
startDir = mainCodeDir;
if ~isfolder(startDir)
    if isfolder('C:\Users\Lu\Desktop')
        startDir = 'C:\Users\Lu\Desktop';
    else
        startDir = 'C:\';
    end
end

datapath = uigetdir(startDir, 'Please select the data folder (this folder will be used as datapath)');
if isequal(datapath, 0)
    error('No folder selected. Exiting.');
```

```

end
fprintf('Datapath: %s\n', datapath);

%% 3) Retrieve data files
% Whether to recursively search subfolders: true/false
useRecursive = false;

if useRecursive && ~verLessThan('matlab','9.1') % R2016b+ supports ** wildcard
    filePatternNex5 = fullfile(datapath, '**', '*.nex5');
    filePatternNex = fullfile(datapath, '**', '*.nex');
    filesNex5 = dir(filePatternNex5);
    filesNex = dir(filePatternNex);
else
    filesNex5 = dir(fullfile(datapath, '*.nex5'));
    filesNex = dir(fullfile(datapath, '*.nex'));
end

filename = [filesNex5; filesNex]; % struct array
nFiles = numel(filename);

if nFiles == 0

```

```

warning('No .nex/.nex5 files found in %s.', datapath);
end

%% 4) basic check and reviewing
if nFiles > 0
    % Remove hidden/system files
    isHidden = startsWith({filename.name}', '.');
    filename = filename(~isHidden);
    nFiles = numel(filename);

    % Sort by name (could change to by date: [~,ix]=sort([filename.datenum]));
    [~, ix] = sort(lower({filename.name}));
    filename = filename(ix);

    % Print preview of the first few entries
    nPreview = min(10, nFiles);
end

%% 5) stim_info read
recursive = false;
stim_info = batch_get_stim_info(datapath, recursive);
%% 6) data selection
% Getting all the spike data into several groups
chnl = {...
    'region1', 1:16;
    'region2', 33:48
};

% Create a list dialog box for user to select a channel
channelOptions = {'1: region1', '2: region2'};
[indx, tf] = listdlg('PromptString', 'Select a channel:',...
    'SelectionMode', 'single',...
    'ListString', channelOptions,...
    'ListSize', [200, 100]); % Adjust ListSize as needed

% Check if the user made a selection
if ~tf
    error('No channel selected. Exiting the program.');
```

% Handle or exit as needed

```

end

% Use the selected index directly as ch
ch = indx;

% Define the results path based on the selected channel
resultsPath = fullfile(datapath, chnl{ch, 1}); % Use fullfile for OS-independent paths
if ~exist(resultsPath, 'dir')
    mkdir(resultsPath);
end

%% reading data
% Define data access keys and default parameters for data extraction
dataKey = {'events', 'spike', 'waveform'}; % Valid selections: 'events', 'spike',
'waveform', 'AI'

% Setup parameters for extracting neural LFP data
paramsExtr = struct(...
    'chnl', {chnl},... % Channel data
    'regionToLoad', {chnl(ch, 1)},... % Brain region to import based on
channel selection

```

```

        'filPerChl', 2,... % Number of filaments per channel
(e.g., stereotrode: 2)
        'exEvent', [],... % External event info, initially
empty
        'eventsFrom', {'nex'},...
        'getEvents', {'start feeding', 'stop feeding', 'go in feeding zone', 'go out feeding
zone'},... % Event types to extract
        'bestNlfp', 5,... % Optimal number of local field
potentials
        'processEvents', 'null'... % Default method for processing
events
);

% Extract neural LFP data using specified filename, data keys, and parameters
[groupNeu, ~] = extractNeuLFP(filename, dataKey, paramsExtr);

% Store original group neural data
%
% Get the first-row data (cell array)
data = {groupNeu.TrialData.neuronID};

% Step 2: filter out items containing 'U'
% Use cellfun and contains to check whether each string contains 'U' (ignore case)
mask = cellfun(@(s) ~contains(s, 'U', 'IgnoreCase', true), data);

% Reduce data
groupNeu.TrialData = groupNeu.TrialData(mask);

groupNeu_original = groupNeu;

%% waveform
% Basic parameters
fs = 40000;
params = struct('dtThr', 0.0002, 'xcThr', 0.5, 'ratioZThr', 3);

assert(isfield(groupNeu, 'TrialData'), 'groupNeu.TrialData does not exist');

origTD = groupNeu.TrialData;
numUnits = numel(origTD);

% In main script, initialize processed as a placeholder, then init from first template
processed = []; % placeholder, do not pre-allocate as struct([])
outIdx = 0;
baseFields = {}; % list of baseline field names

for k = 1:numUnits
    TD = origTD(k);

    % === NEW: Build stereotrode waveform matrix W from TD (events as columns, size 112xm)
    ===
    if ~isfield(TD, 'Allwaveform') || isempty(TD.Allwaveform)
        warning('Unit %d: missing Allwaveform, skip.', k);
        continue;
    end

    A = TD.Allwaveform;
    sz = size(A);
    W = [];

    % Support both numeric matrix and cell array storage

```

```

if isnumeric(A)
    % Case 1: A is a numeric matrix
    if size(A,1) == 112
        W = A; % [112×m]
    elseif size(A,2) == 112
        W = A.'; % [112×m]
    elseif size(A,1) == 56 || size(A,2) == 56
        % Only single-wire 56-point case; cannot run stereotrode pipeline directly
        warning('Unit %d: Allwaveform has 56 points (single wire). Need to merge two
wires into 112 points. Skip.', k);
        continue;
    else
        warning('Unit %d: unsupported Allwaveform size [%d×%d], skip.', k, sz(1),
sz(2));
        continue;
    end
elseif iscell(A)
    % Case 2: A is a cell array, each element one waveform
    % Expect each element to be 112×1 or 1×112
    m = numel(A);
    if m == 0
        warning('Unit %d: Allwaveform is an empty cell, skip.', k);
        continue;
    end
    % Infer single waveform length
    w0 = A{1};
    if isempty(w0)
        warning('Unit %d: first waveform is empty, skip.', k);
        continue;
    end
    if isrow(w0), w0 = w0.'; end
    S = size(w0,1);
    if S ~= 112
        if S == 56
            warning('Unit %d: cell waveforms have 56 points (single wire). Need merging
two wires. Skip.', k);
            continue;
        else
            warning('Unit %d: cell waveform length is %d (not 112), skip.', k, S);
            continue;
        end
    end
    W = zeros(112, m);
    for j = 1:m
        wj = A{j};
        if isrow(wj), wj = wj.'; end
        if size(wj,1) ~= 112
            error('Unit %d: waveform #%d length inconsistent (expected 112, got %d).',
k, j, size(wj,1));
        end
        W(:, j) = wj;
    end
else
    warning('Unit %d: Allwaveform type %s not supported, skip.', k, class(A));
    continue;
end
% === Completed building W ===

% stereotrode processing and splitting
[templates, eventInfo, splitIdx] = processStereotrodeUnit(W, fs, params);
[TD_A, TD_B] = reshapeGroupAfterSplit(TD, splitIdx, eventInfo, templates);

```

```

% First time: establish template field set
if outIdx == 0
    baseFields = fieldnames(TD_A)';
    processed = repmat(cell2struct(cell(size(baseFields)), baseFields, 2), 0, 1);
end

% Write A
outIdx = outIdx + 1;
processed(outIdx) = ensureStructFields(TD_A, baseFields);

% Write B (if present)
if ~isempty(splitIdx.B)
    outIdx = outIdx + 1;
    processed(outIdx) = ensureStructFields(TD_B, baseFields);
end
end

groupNeu.TrialData = processed;

%%
% Filter trials with spike count >= 1000
spikeCounts = arrayfun(@(x) size(x.spike, 1), groupNeu.TrialData);
validTrials = spikeCounts >= 1000;
groupNeu.TrialData = groupNeu.TrialData(validTrials);

%% Integrate stim_info into Neu.TrialData
groupNeu_new = groupNeu;
trial_data = groupNeu_new.TrialData;
num_records = numel(trial_data);

% ----- Options -----
ignoreCase = true; % Case-insensitive matching
trimQuotes = true; % Remove quotes in record
verboseLog = true;

% ----- Build mapping: basename -> index -----
stim_map = containers.Map();
dup_warned = containers.Map('KeyType','char','ValueType','logical'); % de-dup warning
for k = 1:numel(stim_info)
    if ~isfield(stim_info(k),'filename') || isempty(stim_info(k).filename)
        continue;
    end
    [~, bn, ~] = fileparts(stim_info(k).filename);
    key = bn;
    if ignoreCase, key = lower(key); end
    if isKey(stim_map, key) && ~isKey(dup_warned, key)
        warning('Duplicate basename detected: %s, later one will overwrite earlier one.',
bn);
        dup_warned(key) = true;
    end
    stim_map(key) = k;
    if verboseLog
        fprintf(' %3d -> %s\n', k, bn);
    end
end

% ----- Empty template (aligned with new struct fields) -----
empty_stim = struct( ...
    'matched', false, ...
    'filename', '', ...

```

```

'channelName', '', ...
't_on',      [], ...
't_off',     [], ...
'delta_t',   [], ...
'error_message', 'No matching stim file found', ...
'trial_record', '', ...
'trial_index', [] );

% ----- Execute matching -----
matched = 0;
for i = 1:num_records
    rec = trial_data(i).record;

    % Normalize to string and clean up
    if isstring(rec) || ischar(rec)
        rec = char(rec);
    elseif isnumeric(rec)
        rec = char(string(rec));
    else
        rec = char(string(rec)); % best-effort conversion
    end
    rec = strtrim(rec);
    if trimQuotes
        rec = strrep(rec, ''''', '');
        rec = strrep(rec, ''''', '');
    end
    key = rec;
    if ignoreCase, key = lower(key); end

    if isKey(stim_map, key)
        idx = stim_map(key);
        st = stim_info(idx); % take your struct directly
        % supplement matching flag and tracking fields
        st.matched = true;
        st.trial_record = rec;
        st.trial_index = i;

        groupNeu_new.TrialData(i).stim = st;
        matched = matched + 1;

        if verboseLog
            fprintf('✓ Matched: %s <-> %s\n', rec, st.filename);
        end
    else
        st = empty_stim;
        st.trial_record = rec;
        st.trial_index = i;
        groupNeu_new.TrialData(i).stim = st;

        if verboseLog
            fprintf('✗ Unmatched: %s\n', rec);
        end
    end
end

end

%% Adjustments
% ===== Parameters =====
linkY = true; % Link Y axes
titlePrefix = 'Preview Mean Waveforms';
waveformField = 'meanWaveform_good'; % waveform field to use
% =====

```

```

% Select data source
useSplit = exist('groupNeu_new','var')==1;
if useSplit
    S = groupNeu_new;
    TD = S.TrialData;
    srcName = 'groupNeu_new';
else
    assert(exist('groupNeu','var')==1, 'groupNeu or groupNeu_new not found');
    S = groupNeu;
    TD = S.TrialData;
    srcName = 'groupNeu';
end

N = numel(TD);
assert(N>0, 'TrialData is empty');

% First preview (using meanWaveform_good)
[axList, shownMask] = preview_meanwaveforms(TD, titlePrefix, srcName, linkY);

% Interactive input of indices to remove
prompt = sprintf('Enter indices to remove (space-separated, e.g., 2 5 9; press Enter to
keep all): ');
in = input(prompt, 's');
if isempty(strtrim(in))
    removeIdx = [];
else
    removeIdx = str2double(strsplit(strtrim(in)));
    removeIdx = removeIdx(~isnan(removeIdx));
end

% Sanity check and de-dup
removeIdx = unique(removeIdx);
removeIdx = removeIdx(removeIdx>=1 & removeIdx<=N);
if isempty(removeIdx)
    fprintf('Nothing selected. Data unchanged.\n');
    outStruct = S; % output equals input
    return;
end

fprintf('Planned to delete indices: %s\n', mat2str(removeIdx));

% Optional: highlight the subplots to be removed
try
    for ii = 1:numel(removeIdx)
        idx = removeIdx(ii);
        if isgraphics(axList(idx))
            axes(axList(idx)); %#ok<LAXES>
            yl = ylim; xl = xlim;
            patch('XData',[xl(1) xl(2) xl(2) xl(1)], ...
                'YData',[yl(1) yl(1) yl(2) yl(2)], ...
                'FaceColor',[1 0 0], 'FaceAlpha',0.05, 'EdgeColor','none');
            title(axList(idx).Title.String + " [TO REMOVE]", 'Color',[0.6 0 0]);
        end
    end
    drawnow;
catch
end

% Second confirmation
confirm = input('Confirm deleting these entries? y to confirm, n to cancel [y/n]: ', 's');

```

```

if isempty(confirm) || lower(confirm(1))~='y'
    fprintf('Deletion canceled. Data unchanged.\n');
    outStruct = S;
    return;
end

% Execute deletion
keepMask = true(1, N);
keepMask(removeIdx) = false;
TD_new = TD(keepMask);

% Write back output struct
outStruct = S;
outStruct.TrialData = TD_new;

% Also write back to corresponding variable name for convenience
if useSplit
    groupNeu_new = outStruct;
    assignin('base','groupNeu_new', outStruct);
    fprintf('Done: deleted %d from %s, remaining %d.\n', numel(removeIdx), srcName,
numel(TD_new));
else
    groupNeu = outStruct;
    assignin('base','groupNeu', outStruct);
    fprintf('Done: deleted %d from %s, remaining %d.\n', numel(removeIdx), srcName,
numel(TD_new));
end

% Preview again after deletion
repeat = input('Preview the current result again? [y/n]: ', 's');
if ~isempty(repeat) && lower(repeat(1))=='y'
    preview_meanwaveforms(outStruct.TrialData, titlePrefix+" (after removal)", srcName,
linkY);
end

%% Output
Data = outStruct.TrialData;
%%

% Parameters
win_len = 0.050;           % 50 ms window length (s)
Fs_stim = 20;             % 20 Hz -> 0.05 s interval
num_stim = 12000;        % number of stimuli (10 minutes)
seed = 2025;              % random seed for reproducibility

% PSTH params (relative to event onset t_e)
psth_bin = 0.001;         % 1 ms
psth_len = 0.150;        % 150 ms
psth_edges = 0:psth_bin:psth_len; % 151 edges
num_psth_bins = numel(psth_edges)-1; % 150

% Basic checks
if ~exist('Data','var')
    error('Variable Data does not exist.');
```

```

end
N = numel(Data);
if N==0, error('Data is empty.');
```

```

end
rng(seed, 'twister');
```

```

% Preallocate outputs
pre_count = nan(N, 12000); pre_rate = nan(N, 12000);
dur_count = nan(N, 12000); dur_rate = nan(N, 12000);
post_count = nan(N, 12000); post_rate = nan(N, 12000);
```

```

psth_tensor = nan(N, num_psth_bins, 12000); % n × 150 × 12000
psth_mean   = nan(N, num_psth_bins);       % n × 150

for n = 1:N
    % Read t0 and spikes
    if ~isfield(Data(n), 'stim') || ~isfield(Data(n).stim, 't_on') ||
isempty(Data(n).stim.t_on)
        warning('Data(%d).stim.t_on missing, skip.', n);
        continue;
    end
    t0 = Data(n).stim.t_on(1,1);

    if ~isfield(Data(n), 'spike') || isempty(Data(n).spike)
        warning('Data(%d).spike empty, set outputs to zero.', n);
        pre_count(n,:) = 0; pre_rate(n,:) = 0;
        dur_count(n,:) = 0; dur_rate(n,:) = 0;
        post_count(n,:) = 0; post_rate(n,:) = 0;
        psth_tensor(n,:,:) = 0; psth_mean(n,:) = 0;
        % Still save stimulation timeline
        stim_times = t0 + (0:num_stim-1)*win_len; % 1x12000
        Data(n).stim.timeline.t_e = stim_times(:).';
        continue;
    end

    spikes = sort(Data(n).spike(:), 'ascend'); % sort to speed up counting

    % 1) Generate dur segment real stimulus start times (1x12000)
    stim_times = t0 + (0:num_stim-1)*win_len; % fixed 0.05 s interval
    % dur windows: [start, start+0.05) for each stim
    dur_starts = stim_times(:); % 12000x1
    dur_ends   = dur_starts + win_len; % 12000x1

    % 2) pre: randomly pick 12000 windows of 50 ms from [t0-600, t0)
    pre_start_min = t0 - 600;
    pre_start_max = t0 - win_len;
    pre_starts = pre_start_min + (pre_start_max - pre_start_min) * rand(12000,1);
    pre_ends   = pre_starts + win_len;

    % 3) post: randomly pick 12000 windows of 50 ms from [t0+600, t0+900)
    post_start_min = t0 + 600;
    post_start_max = t0 + 900 - win_len;
    post_starts = post_start_min + (post_start_max - post_start_min) * rand(12000,1);
    post_ends   = post_starts + win_len;

    % Count spikes
    pre_c = count_in_intervals(pre_starts, pre_ends, spikes);
    dur_c = count_in_intervals(dur_starts, dur_ends, spikes);
    post_c = count_in_intervals(post_starts, post_ends, spikes);

    % Store in matrices (Hz)
    pre_count(n,:) = pre_c; pre_rate(n,:) = pre_c / win_len;
    dur_count(n,:) = dur_c; dur_rate(n,:) = dur_c / win_len;
    post_count(n,:) = post_c; post_rate(n,:) = post_c / win_len;

    % 4) Build n×150×12000 PSTH based on real stim start times
    % Align to t_e = stim_times(e)
    for e = 1:num_stim
        s0 = stim_times(e);
        rel = spikes - s0;
        rel = rel(rel >= 0 & rel < psth_len);
    end
end

```

```

    if isempty(rel)
        psth_tensor(n,:,e) = 0;
    else
        counts = histcounts(rel, psth_edges);
        psth_tensor(n,:,e) = counts / psth_bin; % firing rate in Hz per 1 ms bin
    end
end
psth_mean(n,:) = mean(psth_tensor(n,:,:), 3, 'omitnan');

% Save key metadata (optional)
Data(n).stim.timeline.t0      = t0;
Data(n).stim.timeline.t_e    = stim_times(:).'; % 1x12000
Data(n).randomWindows.pre.starts = pre_starts;
Data(n).randomWindows.pre.ends   = pre_ends;
Data(n).randomWindows.post.starts = post_starts;
Data(n).randomWindows.post.ends   = post_ends;
Data(n).psth.edges = psth_edges;
end

%% compare_pre_dur_auto
% ===== Parameters =====
FDR_alpha      = 0.01;
paired_data    = true; % Set true if columns are one-to-one (same trial/time), else false
use_jbtest     = false; % If true use Jarque-Bera test; else use Lilliefors (kstest on z-
score)
equalVarTest   = 'vartest2'; % For unpaired normal data, variance homogeneity test:
'vartest2' or 'levene'

% ===== Data prep =====
if ~exist('pre_rate','var') || ~exist('dur_rate','var')
    fprintf('pre_rate/dur_rate not detected, generating example data for demo...\n');
    nUnit = 61; nTrial = 12000; rng(42);
    mu_pre_true = 5 + 2*rand(nUnit,1); % 3~7 Hz
    mu_dur_true = mu_pre_true .* (1 + 0.25*(rand(nUnit,1) < 0.4)) ...
        .* (1 - 0.20*(rand(nUnit,1) < 0.15)); % some increase, some
decrease
    % Generate per-trial firing rates (truncated non-negative)
    pre_rate = max(0, mu_pre_true + randn(nUnit, nTrial));
    dur_rate = max(0, mu_dur_true + 1.2*randn(nUnit, nTrial));
else
    [nUnit, nTrial] = size(pre_rate);
    assert(all(size(dur_rate)==[nUnit, nTrial]), 'pre_rate and dur_rate size mismatch.');
```

```

end

[nUnit, nTrial] = size(pre_rate);

% ===== Main loop: per-neuron automatic test decision =====
pvals = nan(nUnit,1);
test_used = strings(nUnit,1);
dir_effect = zeros(nUnit,1); % -1 decrease, 0 no change, +1 increase
effect_meanDiff = nan(nUnit,1);
effect_RR = nan(nUnit,1);
mu_pre = nan(nUnit,1);
mu_dur = nan(nUnit,1);

for i = 1:nUnit
    x0 = pre_rate(i,:).'; % pre
    x1 = dur_rate(i,:).'; % dur

    mu_pre(i) = mean(x0, 'omitnan');
```

```

mu_dur(i) = mean(x1, 'omitnan');
effect_meanDiff(i) = mu_dur(i) - mu_pre(i);
effect_RR(i) = (mu_dur(i) + eps) / (mu_pre(i) + eps);

% Normality
norm0 = local_test_normality(x0, use_jbtest);
norm1 = local_test_normality(x1, use_jbtest);

if paired_data
    dx = x1 - x0;
    dx = dx(~isnan(dx));
    if numel(dx) < 5
        pvals(i) = 1; test_used(i) = "insufficient"; dir_effect(i) = 0; continue;
    end
    % Paired case: test normality of differences
    norm_dx = local_test_normality(dx, use_jbtest);
    if norm_dx
        % Paired t-test (two-sided)
        try
            [~, p] = ttest(x1, x0, 'Tail','both');
            pvals(i) = p; test_used(i) = "paired_t";
        catch
            pvals(i) = 1; test_used(i) = "paired_t_fail";
        end
    else
        % Nonparametric paired: signrank (two-sided)
        try
            pvals(i) = signrank(x1, x0, 'tail','both');
            test_used(i) = "signrank";
        catch
            pvals(i) = 1; test_used(i) = "signrank_fail";
        end
    end
else
    % Unpaired: normality and equal variance
    if norm0 && norm1
        eqv = local_test_equal_variance(x1, x0, equalVarTest);
        try
            if eqv
                [~, p] = ttest2(x1, x0, 'Vartype','equal', 'Tail','both');
                test_used(i) = "ttest2_equalVar";
            else
                [~, p] = ttest2(x1, x0, 'Vartype','unequal', 'Tail','both'); % Welch
                test_used(i) = "ttest2_unequalVar";
            end
            pvals(i) = p;
        catch
            % Fallback to nonparametric
            try
                pvals(i) = ranksum(x1, x0, 'tail','both');
                test_used(i) = "ranksum_fallback";
            catch
                pvals(i) = 1; test_used(i) = "ranksum_fail";
            end
        end
    else
        try
            pvals(i) = ranksum(x1, x0, 'tail','both');
            test_used(i) = "ranksum";
        catch
            pvals(i) = 1; test_used(i) = "ranksum_fail";
        end
    end
end

```

```

        end
    end
end

% Direction decision (based on mean difference)
if effect_meanDiff(i) > 0
    dir_effect(i) = 1;    % increase
elseif effect_meanDiff(i) < 0
    dir_effect(i) = -1;  % decrease
else
    dir_effect(i) = 0;   % no change
end
end

% FDR correction and final significance and direction
qvals = local_bh_fdr(pvals);
signif = qvals < FDR_alpha;

% Final classification based on significance and direction
% 1=significant increase, -1=significant decrease, 0=no change
final_class = zeros(nUnit,1);
final_class(signif & dir_effect>0) = 1;
final_class(signif & dir_effect<0) = -1;
final_class(~signif | dir_effect==0) = 0;

% ===== Outputs and summary =====
n_up   = sum(final_class==1);
n_down = sum(final_class==-1);
n_ns   = sum(final_class==0);

% Build table
Direction = strings(nUnit,1);
Direction(final_class==1) = "Up";
Direction(final_class==-1) = "Down";
Direction(final_class==0) = "NoChange";

T = table((1:nUnit)', test_used, pvals, qvals, mu_pre, mu_dur, ...
        effect_meanDiff, effect_RR, Direction, ...
        'VariableNames',
        {'Unit','TestUsed','p','q','mu_pre','mu_dur','meanDiff','RR','Direction'});
% T = sortrows(T, 'q');
disp(T(1:min(15,height(T)), :));

%%
% Pre-check
assert(numel(Data) == height(T), 'Number of elements in Data must equal number of rows in T.');
```

% 1) Normalize table variable names to valid struct field names

```

origNames = T.Properties.VariableNames;
validNames = matlab.lang.makeValidName(origNames, 'ReplacementStyle','delete');
```

% If duplicates appear after normalization, append incremental suffixes to avoid conflicts

```

[~, ia] = unique(validNames, 'stable');
if numel(ia) < numel(validNames)
    for k = 1:numel(validNames)
        dupCount = sum(strcmp(validNames{k}, validNames(1:k)));
        if dupCount > 1
            validNames{k} = sprintf('%s_%d', validNames{k}, dupCount);
        end
    end
end

```

```

end
end

% 2) Write table columns to top-level fields of Data
for v = 1:numel(validNames)
    vn = validNames{v}; % target field name
    col = T.(origNames{v}); % original column

    % Type normalization: convert string/categorical to easier-to-save forms
    if isstring(col)
        col = cellstr(col); % string -> cellstr
    elseif iscategorical(col)
        col = cellstr(col); % categorical -> cellstr (display labels)
    end

    % Assign per element to Data(i).vn
    if iscell(col)
        % For cell columns (e.g., cellstr or per-row container/vector)
        for i = 1:numel(Data)
            Data(i).(vn) = col{i}; % store cell content directly
        end
    else
        % For numeric/logical/time scalar columns
        for i = 1:numel(Data)
            Data(i).(vn) = col(i);
        end
    end
end
end

%%
% Pre-check
n = numel(Data);
assert(ismatrix(pre_count) && size(pre_count,1) == n, 'First dim of pre_count should be numel(Data)');
assert(ismatrix(dur_count) && size(dur_count,1) == n, 'First dim of dur_count should be numel(Data)');
assert(ismatrix(post_count) && size(post_count,1) == n, 'First dim of post_count should be numel(Data)');
assert(ismatrix(pre_rate) && size(pre_rate,1) == n, 'First dim of pre_rate should be numel(Data)');
assert(ismatrix(dur_rate) && size(dur_rate,1) == n, 'First dim of dur_rate should be numel(Data)');
assert(ismatrix(post_rate) && size(post_rate,1) == n, 'First dim of post_rate should be numel(Data)');
assert(ismatrix(psth_mean) && size(psth_mean,1) == n, 'First dim of psth_mean should be numel(Data)');
assert(ndims(psth_tensor) == 3 && size(psth_tensor,1) == n, 'First dim of psth_tensor should be numel(Data)');

% Optional: list field names to auto-handle 2D matrices (assign row-wise)
mat2d_names =
{'pre_count', 'dur_count', 'post_count', 'pre_rate', 'dur_rate', 'post_rate', 'psth_mean'};

for i = 1:n
    % 2D matrices: take row i and store into Data(i).field
    for k = 1:numel(mat2d_names)
        name = mat2d_names{k};
        Data(i).(name) = eval([name '(i,:)']); % 1xM row vector
        % If you prefer column vector, use: Data(i).(name) = eval([name '(i,:).''']);
    end
end

```

```

    % 3D tensor: take slice i (first dim), get 150x12000 matrix
    Data(i).psth_tensor = squeeze(psth_tensor(i,:,:)); % 150x12000
    % Note: squeeze won't change 150x12000; only dims of size 1 are squeezed.
end
%%
% Preview + interactive delete + re-preview

% ----- First preview -----
N = numel(Data);

% Compute a roughly square subplot grid
nRow = floor(sqrt(N));
nCol = ceil(N / nRow);

figure('Color','w');
tiledlayout(nRow, nCol, 'Padding','compact','TileSpacing','compact');

for n = 1:N
    nexttile;

    % Get waveform and convert to column
    wf = Data(n).meanWaveform_good;
    wf = wf(:);

    % Color by group
    if isfield(Data, 'Direction')
        dir = Data(n).Direction;
    else
        dir = ''; % default black if missing
    end

    % Normalize to string for comparison
    dirStr = string(dir);
    switch dirStr
        case "Up"
            c = [0.85 0.1 0.1]; % red
        case "Down"
            c = [0.1 0.3 0.9]; % blue
        otherwise
            c = [0 0 0]; % black
    end

    plot(wf, 'Color', c, 'LineWidth', 1.2);
    hold on;

    % Optional: zero line
    yline(0, ':', 'Color', [0.7 0.7 0.7]);

    % Axis styling and title
    axis tight;
    box off;
    set(gca, 'TickDir', 'out', 'FontSize', 8);

    % Title shows unit index and group; if Unit field exists
    if isfield(Data, 'Unit')
        title(sprintf('#%d Unit %s (%s)', n, num2str(Data(n).Unit), char(dirStr)),
'FontSize', 9);
    else
        title(sprintf('#%d (%s)', n, char(dirStr)), 'FontSize', 9);
    end
end
end

```

```

drawnow;

% ----- Interactive input of indices to delete -----
raw = input(sprintf('\nEnter indices to delete (based on preview #n):\nExamples: 5 7 12
or 3:8   or 1 4 10:15 20,22   Enter=none\n> '), 's');

% If just Enter, do nothing and exit
if isempty(strtrim(raw))
    fprintf('No indices entered, Data unchanged.\n');
    return;
end

% Parse input string to index array
ids = parse_indices(raw);

% Validate and de-duplicate
idx_del = unique(round(ids));
idx_del = idx_del(idx_del >= 1 & idx_del <= N);

if isempty(idx_del)
    fprintf('No valid indices after parsing, Data unchanged.\n');
    return;
end

% Confirm operation
fprintf('Will delete indices: %s\n', mat2str(idx_del));
ok = input('Confirm deletion? (y/N): ', 's');
if isempty(ok) || ~ismember(lower(ok), {'y','yes'})
    fprintf('Canceled. Data unchanged.\n');
    return;
end

% ----- Delete and rebuild Data -----
idx_keep = setdiff(1:N, idx_del, 'stable');
Data = Data(idx_keep);

% ----- Second preview (updated Data) -----
N2 = numel(Data);
if N2 == 0
    warning('All data deleted. Nothing to preview.');
```

```

    return;
end

nRow = floor(sqrt(N2));
nCol = ceil(N2 / nRow);

figure('Color','w');
tiledlayout(nRow, nCol, 'Padding','compact','TileSpacing','compact');

for n = 1:N2
    nexttile;

    wf = Data(n).meanWaveform_good;
    wf = wf(:);

    if isfield(Data, 'Direction')
        dir = Data(n).Direction;
    else
        dir = '';
    end
end

```

```

end
dirStr = string(dir);
switch dirStr
    case "Up"
        c = [0.85 0.1 0.1];
    case "Down"
        c = [0.1 0.3 0.9];
    otherwise
        c = [0 0 0];
end

plot(wf, 'Color', c, 'LineWidth', 1.2); hold on;
yline(0, ':', 'Color', [0.7 0.7 0.7]);
axis tight; box off; set(gca,'TickDir','out','FontSize',8);

if isfield(Data, 'Unit')
    title(sprintf('#%d Unit %s (%s)', n, num2str(Data(n).Unit), char(dirStr)),
'FontSize',9);
else
    title(sprintf('#%d (%s)', n, char(dirStr)), 'FontSize',9);
end
end
end
%%

if ~exist('Data','var')
    error('Variable Data does not exist. Please load Data into workspace first.');
```

```

end

use_recluster = false; % false=keep original 0/1, mark cleaned points as 255;
true_recluster kept points after cleaning
rng(1);

%% 1) Aggregate waveforms and build index mapping
allWF = [];
map = []; % For each global waveform -> [n, rowWithinN]
for n = 1:numel(Data)
    if ~isfield(Data(n), 'meanWaveform_good') || isempty(Data(n).meanWaveform_good)
        continue
    end
    wf = Data(n).meanWaveform_good;
    if isvector(wf), wf = wf(:)'; end
    if size(wf,2) ~= 56
        fprintf('Skip Data(%d): waveform columns=%d (need 56).\n', n, size(wf,2));
        continue
    end
    nRows = size(wf,1);
    allWF = [allWF; wf];
    map = [map; [repmat(n, nRows, 1), (1:nRows)']];
end
if isempty(allWF), error('No valid 56-point waveforms found.');
```

```

end
[N, L] = size(allWF); assert(L==56);

%% 2) Classification (call your classifier)
out = classify_waveform_40k(allWF, ...
    'Fs', 40000, 'Interp', 10, ...
    'TroughWin', [10 35], 'SlopeStart', 0.4, 'SlopeDur', 0.2, ...
    'OutlierNSD', 4, 'K', 2);

cell_type_raw = uint8(out.cell_type); % 0/1/255
is_bad_raw = false(N,1);
if isfield(out,'badind') && ~isempty(out.badind), is_bad_raw(out.badind) = true; end

```

```
%% 3) Write back raw features and labels
```

```
for n = 1:numel(Data)
    Data(n).wf_features      = [];
    Data(n).wf_cell_type    = [];
    Data(n).wf_badind       = [];
    Data(n).wf_cell_type_raw = [];
    Data(n).wf_badind_raw   = [];
end
for i = 1:N
    n = map(i,1); r = map(i,2);
    if isempty(Data(n).wf_features)
        nRows = size(Data(n).meanWaveform_good,1); if isvector(Data(n).meanWaveform_good),
nRows = 1; end
        Data(n).wf_features      = nan(nRows, 4);
        Data(n).wf_cell_type    = uint8(255*ones(nRows,1));
        Data(n).wf_badind       = false(nRows,1);
        Data(n).wf_cell_type_raw = uint8(255*ones(nRows,1));
        Data(n).wf_badind_raw   = false(nRows,1);
    end
    if r > size(Data(n).wf_features,1)
        k = r - size(Data(n).wf_features,1);
        Data(n).wf_features      = [Data(n).wf_features;      nan(k,4)];
        Data(n).wf_cell_type    = [Data(n).wf_cell_type;    uint8(255*ones(k,1))];
        Data(n).wf_badind       = [Data(n).wf_badind;       false(k,1)];
        Data(n).wf_cell_type_raw = [Data(n).wf_cell_type_raw; uint8(255*ones(k,1))];
        Data(n).wf_badind_raw   = [Data(n).wf_badind_raw;   false(k,1)];
    end
    Data(n).wf_features(r, :) = [ ...
        out.tp_width_ms(i), ...
        out.half_peak_width_ms(i), ...
        out.half_trough_width_ms(i), ...
        out.end_slope_norm_per_ms(i)];
    Data(n).wf_cell_type_raw(r) = cell_type_raw(i);
    Data(n).wf_badind_raw(r)   = is_bad_raw(i);
end
```

```
%% 4) Cleaning (Mahalanobis distance)
```

```
X = [out.half_peak_width_ms, out.tp_width_ms]; % [W_FWHM, PTD]
```

```
df = size(X,2);
```

```
valid = (cell_type_raw ~= 255) & all(~isnan(X),2);
```

```
label0 = false(N,1); label1 = false(N,1);
```

```
label0(valid) = (cell_type_raw(valid) == 0);
```

```
label1(valid) = (cell_type_raw(valid) == 1);
```

```
alpha = 0.99; useChi2 = true; qPrct = 97.5;
```

```
is_outlier_global = false(N,1);
```

```
centers = nan(2, df);
```

```
for c = 0:1
```

```
    idxc = (c==0)*label0 + (c==1)*label1; idxc = logical(idxc);
```

```
    Xi = X(idxc,:);
```

```
    if size(Xi,1) < df + 1, continue; end
```

```
    mu = mean(Xi,1,'omitnan');
```

```
    S = cov(Xi,'omitrows'); S = S + 1e-9*eye(df);
```

```
    iS = pinv(S);
```

```
    centers(c+1,:) = mu;
```

```
    Xm = Xi - mu;
```

```
    D2 = sum((Xm*iS).*Xm,2);
```

```

    thr = useChi2 * chi2inv(alpha, df) + (~useChi2) * prctile(D2, qPrct);
    out_mask = D2 > thr;
    tmp = false(sum(idxc),1); tmp(out_mask) = true;
    is_outlier_global(idxc) = tmp;
end

final_bad = is_bad_raw | is_outlier_global;
clean_good = (cell_type_raw ~= 255) & ~is_outlier_global & all(~isnan(X),2);

%% 5) Final labels+

if ~use_recluster
    final_label = cell_type_raw;
    final_label(is_outlier_global) = uint8(255);
else
    keep_idx = find(clean_good);
    X_keep = X(keep_idx,:);
    muZ = mean(X_keep,1,'omitnan'); sigZ = std(X_keep,0,1,'omitnan'); sigZ(sigZ==0)=1;
    Z = (X_keep - muZ)./sigZ;
    idx2 = kmeans(Z, 2, 'Start','plus', 'Replicates',10);
    m1 = mean(X_keep(idx2==1, 2), 'omitnan');
    m2 = mean(X_keep(idx2==2, 2), 'omitnan');
    lbl2 = zeros(size(idx2));
    if m1 >= m2, lbl2(idx2==1)=1; lbl2(idx2==2)=0; else, lbl2(idx2==1)=0; lbl2(idx2==2)=1;
end
    lbl2 = uint8(lbl2);
    final_label = uint8(255*ones(N,1));
    final_label(keep_idx) = lbl2;
end

% 5.1) Threshold-based post re-assignment (focus original cluster=0)
% Only reassign valid non-bad/non-outliers
is_valid = (final_label ~= 255) & ~final_bad;

% Mask for initial cluster=0 within valid samples
mask_c0 = is_valid & (final_label == 0);

% Two features needed: W_FWHM and PTD
W_FWHM_ms = out.half_peak_width_ms(:); % horizontal axis W_{FWHM} (ms)
PTD_ms = out.tp_width_ms(:); % vertical axis PTD (ms)

% Rule to remain in class 0: W_FWHM<0.3 and PTD<3
keep0 = mask_c0 & (W_FWHM_ms < 0.3) & (PTD_ms < 3);

% Those originally 0 but not satisfying thresholds -> set to 1
flip_to_1 = mask_c0 & ~keep0;

% Apply reassignment
final_label(flip_to_1) = uint8(1);
final_label(keep0) = uint8(0); % optional, for clarity

%% 6) Write back final results
for i = 1:N
    n = map(i,1); r = map(i,2);
    if ~isfield(Data(n),'wf_cell_type') || isempty(Data(n).wf_cell_type)
        nRows = size(Data(n).meanWaveform_good,1); if isvector(Data(n).meanWaveform_good),
nRows=1; end
        Data(n).wf_cell_type = uint8(255*ones(nRows,1));
    end
    if ~isfield(Data(n),'wf_badind') || isempty(Data(n).wf_badind)

```

```

        nRows = size(Data(n).meanWaveform_good,1); if isvector(Data(n).meanWaveform_good),
nRows=1; end
        Data(n).wf_badind = false(nRows,1);
    end
    Data(n).wf_cell_type(r) = final_label(i);
    Data(n).wf_badind(r)    = final_bad(i);
end

%% 7) Visualization (optional)
figure('Color','w','Name','After Cleaning');
hold on;
scatter(X(final_label==0,1), X(final_label==0,2), 24, [0 0.45 0.74], 'filled');
scatter(X(final_label==1,1), X(final_label==1,2), 24, [0.85 0.33 0.10], 'filled');
scatter(X(final_label==255,1), X(final_label==255,2), 16, [0.80 0.80 0.80], 'filled');
grid on; box on;
xlabel('W_{FWHM} (ms)'); ylabel('PTD (ms)');
title('Cleaned scatter');

%% 8) Summary outputs (compatible with Direction as char matrix/string/cell; with read
monitoring)
fprintf('\n[Monitor] Start summarizing outputs and self-check reading field
Direction...\n');

% 8.1 Extract 1x56 waveforms
waveforms56 = nan(N, 56);
for i = 1:N
    n = map(i,1); r = map(i,2);
    wf = Data(n).meanWaveform_good;
    if isvector(wf), wf = wf(:)'; end
    if size(wf,2)==56 && r<=size(wf,1)
        waveforms56(i,:) = wf(r,:);
    end
end
n_wf_ok = nnz(all(~isnan(waveforms56),2));
fprintf('[Monitor] Extracted complete 56-point waveforms: %d/%d.\n', n_wf_ok, N);

% 8.2 Read direction labels (prefer field name Direction, fallback to Dirction)
Dir_out = strings(N,1);
dir_fieldname = repmat("Direction", numel(Data), 1);
for n = 1:numel(Data)
    if ~(isfield(Data(n),'Direction') && ~isempty(Data(n).Direction)) ...
        && (isfield(Data(n),'Dirction') && ~isempty(Data(n).Dirction))
        dir_fieldname(n) = "Dirction";
    end
end
end

% Map each global waveform to Direction
for i = 1:N
    n = map(i,1); r = map(i,2);
    Dir_out(i) = get_direction_token(Data(n), r);
end

n_dir_ok = nnz(Dir_out ~= '');
fprintf('[Monitor] Direction label read success: %d/%d.\n', n_dir_ok, N);

if n_dir_ok < N
    miss_idx = find(Dir_out == '');
    miss_n = unique(map(miss_idx,1));
    fprintf(2, '[Warning] %d records failed to read Direction. Involving %d Data(n).
Example n (max 10):\n', numel(miss_idx), numel(miss_n));

```

```

disp(miss_n(1:min(10,end))');
for k = 1:min(5, numel(miss_n))
    n = miss_n(k);
    hasA = isfield(Data(n), 'Direction') && ~isempty(Data(n).Direction);
    hasB = isfield(Data(n), 'Dirction') && ~isempty(Data(n).Dirction);
    fprintf(' n=%d: has Direction=%d, has Dirction=%d\n', n, hasA, hasB);
    if hasA, preview_cell_or_str('Data(n).Direction', Data(n).Direction); end
    if hasB, preview_cell_or_str('Data(n).Dirction', Data(n).Dirction); end
end
fprintf('If Direction is a char matrix, ensure its row count >= corresponding
meanWaveform_good rows, and one label per row.\n');
end

```

% 8.3 Summarize features and labels

```

feat_PTD_ms = out.tp_width_ms(:);
feat_WFWM_ms = out.half_peak_width_ms(:);
feat_W_trough_ms = out.half_trough_width_ms(:);
feat_end_slope_perms = out.end_slope_norm_per_ms(:);

```

```

cluster_raw = uint8(out.cell_type(:)); % 0/1/255
cluster_final = uint8(final_label(:)); % 0/1/255
removed_flag = logical(final_bad(:)); % true indicates bad or outlier

```

% 8.4 Struct

```

Summary(N,1) = struct( ...
    'global_idx', [], ...
    'waveform56', [], ...
    'PTD_ms', [], ...
    'W_FWHM_ms', [], ...
    'W_trough_ms', [], ...
    'end_slope_per_ms', [], ...
    'cluster_raw', [], ...
    'cluster_final', [], ...
    'is_removed', [], ...
    'Direction', [], ...
    'source_n', [], ...
    'row_within_n', [] );
for i = 1:N
    Summary(i).global_idx = i;
    Summary(i).waveform56 = waveforms56(i,:);
    Summary(i).PTD_ms = feat_PTD_ms(i);
    Summary(i).W_FWHM_ms = feat_WFWM_ms(i);
    Summary(i).W_trough_ms = feat_W_trough_ms(i);
    Summary(i).end_slope_per_ms = feat_end_slope_perms(i);
    Summary(i).cluster_raw = cluster_raw(i);
    Summary(i).cluster_final = cluster_final(i);
    Summary(i).is_removed = removed_flag(i);
    Summary(i).Direction = Dir_out(i); % 'Up'/'Down'/'NoChange'
    Summary(i).source_n = map(i,1);
    Summary(i).row_within_n = map(i,2);
end

```

% 8.5 Table

```

SummaryTable = table( ...
    (1:N)', ...
    feat_PTD_ms, feat_WFWM_ms, feat_W_trough_ms, feat_end_slope_perms, ...
    cluster_raw, cluster_final, removed_flag, Dir_out, ...
    'VariableNames', {'global_idx','PTD_ms','W_FWHM_ms','W_trough_ms','end_slope_per_ms',
    ...
    'cluster_raw','cluster_final','is_removed','Direction'});

```

```

%%
figure('Color','w','Name','After Cleaning (Summary-based)');
hold on;

% Extract fields
PTD = [Summary.PTD_ms]'; % y-axis
Wfwhm = [Summary.W_FWHM_ms]'; % x-axis

% Class labels (0=PIN, 1=PPN, others=uncertain)
if isfield(Summary, 'cluster_final')
    y = [Summary.cluster_final]';
else
    error('cluster_final field missing in Summary.');
```

end

```

% Optional: remove samples marked as removed
if isfield(Summary, 'is_removed')
    keep = ~[Summary.is_removed]';
else
    keep = true(numel(Summary),1);
end

% Three index sets
idx0 = (y==0) & keep; % PIN
idx1 = (y==1) & keep; % PPN
idxU = ~(y==0 | y==1) & keep; % Uncertain/others

% Plot (color consistent with previous style)
scatter(Wfwhm(idx0), PTD(idx0), 24, [0 0.45 0.74], 'filled'); % PIN
scatter(Wfwhm(idx1), PTD(idx1), 24, [0.85 0.33 0.10], 'filled'); % PPN
% scatter(Wfwhm(idxU), PTD(idxU), 16, [0.80 0.80 0.80], 'filled'); % uncertain

grid on; box on;
xlabel('W_{FWHM} (ms)');
ylabel('PTD (ms)');
title('Cleaned scatter (from Summary)');
legend({'PIN (0)', 'PPN (1)'}, 'Location', 'best');
```

%%

```

assert(isfield(Summary, 'cluster_final'), 'Summary.cluster_final missing');
assert(isfield(Summary, 'Direction'), 'Summary.Direction missing');
```

```

cls = [Summary.cluster_final]'; % 0=PIN, 1=PPN
dir = string({Summary.Direction}'); % "Up"/"Down"/"NoChange"
```

```

% Optional remove excluded samples
if isfield(Summary, 'is_removed')
    keep = ~[Summary.is_removed]';
else
    keep = true(numel(Summary),1);
end

% Keep valid
validClass = (cls==0 | cls==1);
% Normalize direction case and trim
dir = strtrim(dir);
validDir = (dir=="Up" | dir=="Down" | dir=="NoChange");

valid = keep & validClass & validDir;
cls = cls(valid);
```

```

dir = dir(valid);

% Fixed order and colors
groupsDir = ["Up", "NoChange", "Down"];
colorsDir = [ ...
    0.30 0.75 0.93; % Up    - sky blue
    0.60 0.60 0.60; % NoChange - gray
    0.85 0.33 0.10]; % Down - orange red

groupsCls = [0, 1]; % 0=PIN, 1=PPN
nameCls    = ["PIN (0)", "PPN (1)"];
colorsCls  = [ ...
    0.00 0.45 0.74; % PIN  - blue
    0.85 0.33 0.10]; % PPN  - orange red

%% A) Pie charts: Direction within each class (PIN/PPN)
figure('Color', 'w', 'Name', 'Pie: Direction within Class');
for i = 1:numel(groupsCls)
    c = groupsCls(i);
    maskC = (cls==c);
    counts = zeros(1, numel(groupsDir));
    for j = 1:numel(groupsDir)
        counts(j) = sum(maskC & dir==groupsDir(j));
    end
    totalN = sum(counts);
    pct = 100 * counts / max(totalN, 1);

    subplot(1, numel(groupsCls), i);
    if totalN == 0
        % empty data -> show placeholder
        axis off; text(0.5, 0.5, sprintf('%s\nN=0', nameCls(i)),
'HorizontalAlignment', 'center', 'FontWeight', 'bold');
        continue;
    end

    hh = pie(counts);
    % Set colors and labels
    hPatch = hh(1:2:end); % patches
    hText  = hh(2:2:end); % labels
    for k = 1:numel(hPatch)
        set(hPatch(k), 'FaceColor', colorsDir(k,:), 'EdgeColor', 'w');
        set(hText(k), 'String', sprintf('%s: %.1f%%', groupsDir(k), pct(k)));
    end
    title(sprintf('Direction in %s (N=%d)', nameCls(i), totalN));
end

%% B) Pie charts: Class within each direction (Up/NoChange/Down)
figure('Color', 'w', 'Name', 'Pie: Class within Direction');
for i = 1:numel(groupsDir)
    d = groupsDir(i);
    maskD = (dir==d);
    counts = [sum(maskD & cls==0), sum(maskD & cls==1)]; % [PIN, PPN]
    totalN = sum(counts);
    pct = 100 * counts / max(totalN, 1);

    subplot(1, numel(groupsDir), i);
    if totalN == 0
        axis off; text(0.5, 0.5, sprintf('%s\nN=0', d),
'HorizontalAlignment', 'center', 'FontWeight', 'bold');
        continue;
    end
end

```

```

hh = pie(counts);
hPatch = hh(1:2:end);
hText = hh(2:2:end);

% Two sector colors fixed: PIN->blue, PPN->orange
set(hPatch(1), 'FaceColor', colorsCls(1,:), 'EdgeColor', 'w'); % PIN
set(hPatch(2), 'FaceColor', colorsCls(2,:), 'EdgeColor', 'w'); % PPN

set(hText(1), 'String', sprintf('PIN: %.1f%%', pct(1)));
set(hText(2), 'String', sprintf('PPN: %.1f%%', pct(2)));

title(sprintf('Class in %s (N=%d)', d, totalN));
end

%% Visualization: feature scatter based on Summary (W_FWHM vs PTD), color=class,
marker=direction
figure('Color','w','Name','After Cleaning (Summary-based)');
hold on;

% Extract fields
PTD = [Summary.PTD_ms]'; % y-axis
Wfwhm = [Summary.W_FWHM_ms]'; % x-axis

% Class labels (0=PIN, 1=PPN, others=uncertain)
assert(isfield(Summary,'cluster_final'),'cluster_final missing in Summary.');
```

```

y = [Summary.cluster_final]';

% Direction
assert(isfield(Summary,'Direction'),'Direction missing in Summary.');
```

```

dirs = string({Summary.Direction});
dirs = strtrim(dirs);

% Optional: remove samples marked as removed
if isfield(Summary,'is_removed')
    keep = ~[Summary.is_removed]';
else
    keep = true(numel(Summary),1);
end

% Keep only three directions
validDir = dirs=="Up" | dirs=="NoChange" | dirs=="Down";
keep = keep & validDir;

% Define colors (by class)
colPIN = [0 0.45 0.74];
colPPN = [0.85 0.33 0.10];
colU = [0.80 0.80 0.80];

% Define markers (by direction)
markerMap = struct('Up','^','NoChange','o','Down','v');
```

```

% Combined plotting
classes = {'PIN','PPN','Uncertain'};
classMask = {
    y==0 & keep, ...
    y==1 & keep, ...
    ~(y==0 | y==1) & keep ...
};
classColor = {colPIN, colPPN, colU};
```

```

dirLevels = {'Up', 'NoChange', 'Down'};

legendEntries = {};
for ci = 1:numel(classes)
    for di = 1:numel(dirLevels)
        mask = classMask{ci} & (dirs==dirLevels{di});
        if any(mask)
            scatter(Wfwhm(mask), PTD(mask), ...
                28, classColor{ci}, markerMap.(dirLevels{di}), ...
                'filled', 'MarkerFaceAlpha', 0.85, 'MarkerEdgeColor', 'k',
'MarkerEdgeAlpha', 0.2);
            legendEntries{end+1} = sprintf('%s - %s', classes{ci}, dirLevels{di});
        end
    end
end

grid on; box on;
xlabel('W_{FWHM} (ms)');
ylabel('PTD (ms)');
title('Cleaned scatter (from Summary): color=class, marker=direction');
if ~isempty(legendEntries)
    legend(legendEntries, 'Location', 'bestoutside');
end

%% Visualization: W_FWHM vs PTD
% Marker shape=class (PPN:o, PIN:v), color=direction (Up red / Down blue / NoChange gray)
figure('Color', 'w', 'Name', 'After Cleaning (Summary-based)');
hold on;

% Extract fields
PTD = [Summary.PTD_ms]'; % y-axis
Wfwhm = [Summary.W_FWHM_ms]'; % x-axis

% Class labels (0=PIN, 1=PPN; others=uncertain, not plotted)
assert(isfield(Summary, 'cluster_final'), 'cluster_final missing in Summary. ');
y = [Summary.cluster_final]';

% Direction
assert(isfield(Summary, 'Direction'), 'Direction missing in Summary. ');
dirs = string({Summary.Direction});
dirs = strtrim(dirs);

% Optional: remove samples marked as removed
if isfield(Summary, 'is_removed')
    keep = ~[Summary.is_removed]';
else
    keep = true(numel(Summary), 1);
end

% Keep only three directions
validDir = dirs=="Up" | dirs=="NoChange" | dirs=="Down";
keep = keep & validDir;

% Keep only determined cell types (PIN or PPN)
isPIN = (y==0);
isPPN = (y==1);
keep = keep & (isPIN | isPPN);

% Color map: by direction
colInc = [0.95 0.20 0.20]; % Up -> Increase red

```

```

colDec = [0.20 0.60 0.95]; % Down -> Decrease blue
colINC  = [0.60 0.60 0.60]; % NoChange -> gray
getColorByDir = @(d) ( strcmp(d,'Up')      * colInc + ...
                      strcmp(d,'Down')    * colDec + ...
                      strcmp(d,'NoChange')* colINC );

% Marker mapping by class
% PPN uses 'o'; PIN uses 'v'
markerByClass = @(isPPNflag) ( iff(isPPNflag,'o','v') );
function_out = []; % only to suppress local function warning

% Plot by six combinations of class × direction, hollow markers
ms = 52; % area
lw = 1.8; % edge line width
dirLevels = {'Up','Down','NoChange'};

% PPN (circle)
for di = 1:numel(dirLevels)
    d = dirLevels{di};
    mask = keep & isPPN & (dirs==d);
    if any(mask)
        scatter(Wfwhm(mask), PTD(mask), ms, ...
                'Marker', 'o', ...
                'MarkerEdgeColor', getColorByDir(d), ...
                'MarkerFaceColor', 'none', ...
                'LineWidth', lw);
    end
end

% PIN (倒三角)
for di = 1:numel(dirLevels)
    d = dirLevels{di};
    mask = keep & isPIN & (dirs==d);
    if any(mask)
        scatter(Wfwhm(mask), PTD(mask), ms, ...
                'Marker', 'v', ...
                'MarkerEdgeColor', getColorByDir(d), ...
                'MarkerFaceColor', 'none', ...
                'LineWidth', lw);
    end
end

% Axis style
ax = gca;
ax.Box = 'off';
ax.LineWidth = 2.2;
ax.TickDir = 'out';
ax.FontName = 'Arial';
ax.FontSize = 11;
grid(ax,'off');

xlabel('W_{FWHM} (ms)', 'FontName', 'Arial', 'FontSize', 12);
ylabel('PTD (ms)', 'FontName', 'Arial', 'FontSize', 12);
title('W_{FWHM} vs PTD', 'FontName', 'Arial', 'FontWeight', 'normal', 'FontSize', 12);

% Optional fixed ranges
% xlim([0.15 1.2]); ylim([0 0.8]); xticks(0.2:0.2:1.2); yticks(0:0.2:0.8);

% Build "line-only" legend (direction only)
x0 = NaN; y0 = NaN;
hInc = plot([x0 x0], [y0 y0], '-', 'Color', colInc, 'LineWidth', 3); % Increase

```

```

hDec = plot([x0 x0], [y0 y0], '-', 'Color', colDec, 'LineWidth', 3); % Decrease
hNC = plot([x0 x0], [y0 y0], '-', 'Color', colNC, 'LineWidth', 3); % No change
legend([hInc hDec hNC], {'Increase','Decrease','No change'}, ...
      'Location','northeastoutside','Box','off');

hold off;

%% function

function stim_info = batch_get_stim_info(rootDir, recursive)

% ----- Input args and defaults -----
if nargin < 1 || isempty(rootDir)
    rootDir = 'G:\A-B-D';
end
if nargin < 2 || isempty(recursive)
    recursive = true;
end
if ~isfolder(rootDir)
    error('rootDir does not exist: %s', rootDir);
end

% ----- Detection parameters (tunable) -----
thr_on = 3000;
thr_off = 2900;
minWidth_samp = 2;
maxWidth_samp = 20;
refractory_samp = 40;
minHold_samp = 4;
needLowCount = 2;
useSubSample = true;

% Scoring reference (only for choosing best channel, does not affect final outputs)
targetISI_ms = 50;
targetWidth_ms = [3 7];

% Pack params
params = struct('thr_on',thr_on,'thr_off',thr_off,'minWidth_samp',minWidth_samp, ...
    'maxWidth_samp',maxWidth_samp,'refractory_samp',refractory_samp, ...
    'minHold_samp',minHold_samp,'needLowCount',needLowCount, ...
    'useSubSample',useSubSample);

% ----- Gather files -----
files = listNexFiles(rootDir, recursive);
stim_info = struct('filename',{},'channelName',{},'t_on',{},'t_off',{},'delta_t',{});
if isempty(files)
    warning('No .nex files found in %s.', rootDir);
    return;
end

% ----- Environment check -----
if exist('readNexFile','file') ~= 2
    error('Function readNexFile not found; please add it to MATLAB path.');
```

```

        error('File contains no contvars.');
```

end

```

[det, ok] = selectBestStimChannel(nexData, params, targetISI_ms, targetWidth_ms);
if ~ok
    stim_info(end+1) = struct('filename', fpath, 'channelName', '', ...
        't_on', [], 't_off', [], 'delta_t', []); %#ok<AGROW>
else
    stim_info(end+1) = struct('filename', fpath, 'channelName', string(det.name),
        ...
        't_on', det.t_on(:), 't_off', det.t_off(:), 'delta_t', det.delta_t(:));
%#ok<AGROW>
end

fprintf('%d/%d] %s -> %s, n=%d\n', i, numel(files), fpath, ...
    ternary(ok,string(det.name),"N/A"), numel(det.t_on));

catch ME
    stim_info(end+1) = struct('filename', fpath, 'channelName', '', ...
        't_on', [], 't_off', [], 'delta_t', []); %#ok<AGROW>
    fprintf(2, '%d/%d] Failed: %s | %s\n', i, numel(files), fpath, ME.message);
end
end
end % main
```

```
function [groupNeuron,groupLFP] = extractNeuLFP(filename, dataKey, paramsExtr)
```

```
idx = 1; % idx: index for wanted neurons
```

```

groupNeu = [];
groupLFP = [];
% Save spike/events/waveform or not
addSpike = sum(strcmp(dataKey, 'spike'));
addEvents = sum(strcmp(dataKey, 'events'));
addWaveform = sum(strcmp(dataKey, 'waveform'));
addAI = sum(strcmp(dataKey, 'AI'));
filPerChl = paramsExtr.filPerChl;
exEvt = paramsExtr.exEvent;
evtFrom = paramsExtr.eventsFrom;
getEvt = paramsExtr.getEvents;
bestNlfp = paramsExtr.bestNlfp;
```

```

chnl = paramsExtr.chnl;
regionToLoad = paramsExtr.regionToLoad;
regionPos = cellfun(@(x) any(strcmp(x,regionToLoad)),chnl(:,1));
```

```
for i = 1:length(filename) % i: index for nex files
```

```

    tempPath = filename(i).folder;
    tempLabel = strsplit(tempPath, '/');
    % For each loop, reading only one nexfile to tempData
    if strcmp(filename(i).name(end),'5')
        curNex = readNex5File([tempPath, '/', filename(i).name]);
    else
        curNex = readNexFile([tempPath, '/', filename(i).name]);
    end
    % find the serial number of the animal and the date of experiment
    tempDate = filename(i).name(1:8);
```

```

    %tempAnimal = regexpi(filename(i).name, '[#v-]\d\d\d\d', 'match');
    % tempAnimal = tempAnimal{1}(2:5);

matchResult = regexpi(filename(i).name, '[#v]\d{4}-\d', 'match'); % Using regex to find
patterns starting with # or v,                                     % followed by 4 digits, a
                                                                    hyphen, then a digit. regexpi is case-insensitive.
if ~isempty(matchResult)
    % Ensure the match is a string, then take substring from the 2nd to 7th char
    tempAnimal = matchResult{1}(2:min(7, end)); % use min to avoid index overflow
else
    tempAnimal = ''; % Default if no match
end

% extract LFPs
% get continuous variables for LFPs into 'curLFP'
getLFP = any(strcmpi(dataKey, 'LFP'));
if getLFP
    try
        curContvars = [curNex.contvars{:,1}];
    catch
        disp(['lack LFP ', filename(i).name]);
        getLFP = false;
    end
end
if getLFP
    LFPpos = cellfun(@(x) contains(x, 'FP'), {curContvars.name});
    curLFP = curContvars(LFPpos);
    % find regions where LFP channels belong
    curLFPchnl = cellfun(@(x) str2double(x(5:6)), {curLFP.name});
    curRegPos = cellfun(@(x) ismember(curLFPchnl, x), chnl(:,2), 'UniformOutput', false);
    curRegPos2 = regionPos & cell2mat(curRegPos);
    [channelPos, idxReg] = max(curRegPos2); % channelPos: the logical array indicating
whether
    curLFPreg = chnl(idxReg,1);
    curLFPreg = curLFPreg(channelPos);
    curLFP = [curLFP(channelPos).data];
    % save average LFP waveforms for bestNlfp LFPs in each region
    tempReg = unique(curLFPreg);
    if ~isempty(tempReg)
        for kr = 1:length(tempReg) % this loop goes through the brain regions for LFP
            rgLFP = curLFP(:, strcmp(tempReg(kr), curLFPreg));
            bestLfpIdx = findBestLFP(rgLFP(1000:150:end,:), bestNlfp);
            tempLFP(kr).waveform = mean(rgLFP(:, bestLfpIdx), 2);
            tempLFP(kr).region = tempReg{kr};
        end
        groupLFP(i).animal = tempAnimal;
        groupLFP(i).date = tempDate;
        groupLFP(i).record = erase(filename(i).name(1:end-4), '.');
        groupLFP(i).LFPs = tempLFP;
    end
end

% extract waveform and timestamp information of neurons and AI
try
    curWave = [curNex.waves{:,1}];
catch
    disp(['error finding waves:', filename(i).name]);
    continue
end
curName = {curWave.name};

```

```

% AI is the channel for opto stimulation. It may affect all neurons.
AIpos = cellfun(@(x) contains(x, 'AI') & contains(x, 'wf'), curName);
curAI = curWave(AIpos);
templatePos = find(cellfun(@(x) contains(x, 'template') & contains(x, 'SPK'), curName));
wfPos = find(cellfun(@(x) contains(x, 'wf') & contains(x, 'SPK'), curName));
if isempty(wfPos)
    continue
end
neuronID = cellfun(@(x) x(end-5:end-3), curName(wfPos), 'UniformOutput', false);
curNeuChnl = cellfun(@(x) str2double(x(1:2)), neuronID);

curRegPos = cellfun(@(x) ismember(curNeuChnl, x), chnl(:, 2), 'UniformOutput', false);
curRegPos2 = regionPos & cell2mat(curRegPos);
[channelPos, idxReg] = max(curRegPos2);
curNeuReg = chnl(idxReg, 1);
wfPos = wfPos(channelPos);
if any(templatePos)
    templatePos = templatePos(channelPos);
end

% put data of the current file into tempTrialData
idxpost = idx + length(wfPos) - 1;
if idxpost >= idx
    [groupNeu(idx:idxpost).neuronID] = neuronID{channelPos};
    curNeuChnl = num2cell(curNeuChnl);
    [groupNeu(idx:idxpost).channel] = curNeuChnl{channelPos};
    [groupNeu(idx:idxpost).region] = curNeuReg{channelPos};
    [groupNeu(idx:idxpost).date] = deal(tempDate);
    [groupNeu(idx:idxpost).animal] = deal(tempAnimal);
    tempName = cellfun(@(x) erase([filename(i).name(1:end-4) '_'
x], '.'), neuronID(channelPos), 'UniformOutput', false);
    [groupNeu(idx:idxpost).name] = tempName{:};
    [groupNeu(idx:idxpost).record] = deal(erase(filename(i).name(1:end-4), '.'));
    [groupNeu(idx:idxpost).label] = deal(tempLabel{end});
    if addWaveform
        if any(templatePos) % if template was saved into nex files after neuron
sorting
            templates = {curWave(templatePos).waveforms}; % use the existing
templates
        else
            % In some files, template channels are corrupted, so we don't use them any more.
            templates = {curWave(wfPos).waveforms}; % else, use the mean of spike
waveforms as templates
            [groupNeu(idx:idxpost).Allwaveform] = templates{:};
            templates = cellfun(@(x) mean(x, 2), templates, 'UniformOutput', false);
        end
        % select the template from the filaments that got signals of largest
% amplitude as the final template
        if length(templates{1}) > 56
            pointPerFil = length(templates{1}) / filPerChl;
        else
            pointPerFil = length(templates{1});
            disp(['Only one channel in ', groupNeu(idx).record]);
        end
        bestFilaments = cellfun(@(x) ceil(find(x == min(x)) /
pointPerFil), templates, 'UniformOutput', false);
        try
            bestTemplates = cellfun(@(x, y) x(1 +
(y-1)*pointPerFil:y*pointPerFil), templates, bestFilaments, 'UniformOutput', false);
        catch
            bestTemplates = [];
    end
end

```



```

                cEvents{tempLightPos}.timestamps(end,3)
= diff(cEvents{tempLightPos}.timestamps(end,1:2))/(diffAIpos(kAITrial+1)-
diffAIpos(kAITrial)-1); %TrialData.events.timestamps(:,3): period (1/f) of the light
                end
            end
        end
        [groupNeu(idx:idxpost).events] = deal(cell2mat(cEvents));
    end
    idx = idxpost+1;
end

end

groupNeuron.TrialData = groupNeu;
end

function [templates, eventInfo, splitIdx] = processStereotrodeUnit(W, fs, params)

    if nargin < 2 || isempty(fs), fs = 40000; end
    if nargin < 3, params = struct(); end
    p = fillParams(params);

    % Basic sizes and split wires
    [S, m] = size(W);
    assert(mod(S, p.filPerChl)==0, 'Row length must be multiple of filPerChl. ');
    M = S / p.filPerChl;
    ch1 = W(1:M, :);
    ch2 = W(M+1:end, :);

    % Unify polarity: assume negative trough is main. If mean min is >0, flip.
    if mean(min(ch1)) > 0, ch1 = -ch1; end
    if mean(min(ch2)) > 0, ch2 = -ch2; end

    % Per-event features
    [A1, p1] = getPeakAndPos(ch1, p.useParabFit);
    [A2, p2] = getPeakAndPos(ch2, p.useParabFit);

    % Main wire selection (by amplitude) and reference peak pos
    useCh1 = A1 >= A2;
    mainCh = 2*ones(1,m); mainCh(useCh1) = 1;
    pref = p2; pref(useCh1) = p1(useCh1);

    % Quality and difference metrics
    dt = abs(p1 - p2) / fs;
    ratio = A1 ./ max(A2, eps);
    logR = log(ratio);
    logRz = robustZ(logR);

    % Inter-wire correlation (window around main peak)
    win = localWin(M, pref, fs);
    xc12 = zeros(1,m);
    for i = 1:m
        seg1 = ch1(win(i,1):win(i,2), i);
        seg2 = ch2(win(i,1):win(i,2), i);
        xc12(i) = corrN(seg1, seg2);
    end

    % Edge and suspect flags
    isEdge = (pref <= p.edgeSafe) | (pref >= M - p.edgeSafe);
    isSuspect = (dt > p.dtThr) | (xc12 < p.xcThr) | (abs(logRz) > p.ratioZThr) | isEdge;

```

```

% Stage 1: build main-wire template and compute main-wire correlations (no split)
% Alignment: rough align by each main wire's peak position, then median as template
(robust)
[tmplMain, xc_main, mainWireIdx] = buildMainWireTemplate(ch1, ch2, mainCh);

% Use non-suspect events to estimate dual-channel template (same as original)
keep = ~isSuspect;
if ~any(keep)
    warning('All events marked suspect; falling back to all for template.');
```

keep = true(1,m);

```

end
tmpl1 = mean(ch1(:, keep), 2);
tmpl2 = mean(ch2(:, keep), 2);

templates.best = [tmpl1(:)'; tmpl2(:)'];
templates.perCh = {tmpl1(:), tmpl2(:)};
templates.main = struct('wire', mainWireIdx, 'tmpl', tmplMain(:), 'xc_main', xc_main);

% Stage 2: attempt split (only if necessary) and strong validation
% 2.1 candidate split
[assignAB_cand, distA, distB] = assignByTemplates(ch1, ch2, tmpl1, tmpl2);
needSplitCand = shouldSplit(distA, distB, isSuspect);

% 2.2 Necessary conditions: sample size and group sizes
minSize = max(p.minGroupSize, ceil(p.minGroupFrac * m));
meetsSize = m >= p.minN;

% 2.3 If satisfied, refine templates and get candidate assignment
templates.split = {};
assignAB = repmat('A', 1, m);
if needSplitCand && meetsSize
    for iter = 1:2
        Aidx = assignAB_cand == 'A';
        Bidx = assignAB_cand == 'B';
        if any(Aidx)
            tmpl1A = mean(ch1(:, Aidx), 2);
            tmpl2A = mean(ch2(:, Aidx), 2);
        else
            tmpl1A = tmpl1; tmpl2A = tmpl2;
        end
        if any(Bidx)
            tmpl1B = mean(ch1(:, Bidx), 2);
            tmpl2B = mean(ch2(:, Bidx), 2);
        else
            tmpl1B = tmpl1; tmpl2B = tmpl2;
        end
        [assignAB_cand, distA, distB] = assignByTemplates(ch1, ch2, tmpl1A, tmpl2A,
tmpl1B, tmpl2B);
    end

% 2.4 Strong validation
Aidx = find(assignAB_cand=='A');
Bidx = find(assignAB_cand=='B');
accept = validateSplit(ch1, ch2, Aidx, Bidx, p);

% 2.5 Group size lower bound
if numel(Aidx) < minSize || numel(Bidx) < minSize
    accept = false;
end

if accept
```

```

    assignAB = assignAB_cand;
    templates.split = { [mean(ch1(:,Aidx),2)'; mean(ch2(:,Aidx),2)'], ...
                       [mean(ch1(:,Bidx),2)'; mean(ch2(:,Bidx),2)'] };
    if p.verbose
        fprintf('[split] ACCEPT: m=%d | A=%d, B=%d\n', m, numel(Aidx), numel(Bidx));
    end
else
    if p.verbose
        fprintf('[split] REJECT: m=%d | A=%d, B=%d\n', m, numel(Aidx), numel(Bidx));
    end
end
else
    if p.verbose
        fprintf('[split] SKIP: needSplit=%d, meetsSize=%d, m=%d\n', needSplitCand,
meetsSize, m);
    end
end

% Output event info
eventInfo = struct( ...
    'A1', num2cell(A1), 'A2', num2cell(A2), ...
    'p1', num2cell(p1), 'p2', num2cell(p2), ...
    'mainCh', num2cell(mainCh), 'pref', num2cell(pref), ...
    'dt', num2cell(dt), 'ratio', num2cell(ratio), ...
    'logRatioZ', num2cell(logRz), 'xc', num2cell(xc12), ...
    'isEdge', num2cell(isEdge), 'isSuspect', num2cell(isSuspect), ...
    'xc_main', num2cell(xc_main) ...
);

if ~isempty(templates.split)
    assign = assignAB;
else
    assign = repmat('A', 1, m);
end
for i = 1:m
    eventInfo(i).assign = assign(i);
end

splitIdx.A = find(assign=='A');
splitIdx.B = find(assign=='B');
end

function p = fillParams(p)
    def.filPerCh1 = 2;
    def.dtThr = 0.0002; % 0.2 ms
    def.xcThr = 0.5;
    def.ratioZThr = 3;
    def.edgeSafe = 3; % samples
    def.minPeakSep= 8; % samples
    def.useParabFit = true;
    % Conservative split defaults
    def.minN = 60;
    def.minGroupSize = 20;
    def.minGroupFrac = 0.05;
    def.xc_reject = 0.85;
    def.energyFrac_reject = 0.10;
    def.requireWithinImprove = 0.05;
    def.verbose = false;

    f = fieldnames(def);
    for k = 1:numel(f)

```

```

        if ~isfield(p, f{k}) || isempty(p.(f{k}))
            p.(f{k}) = def.(f{k});
        end
    end
end
end

```

```

function [A, pos] = getPeakAndPos(X, useParab)
    [mins, posI] = min(X, [], 1);
    A = -mins; % use absolute of negative trough
    pos = posI;
    if useParab
        [M, m] = size(X);
        pos = double(posI);
        for i = 1:m
            p0 = posI(i);
            if p0>1 && p0<M
                y1 = X(p0-1,i); y2 = X(p0,i); y3 = X(p0+1,i);
                denom = (y1 - 2*y2 + y3);
                if abs(denom) > eps
                    delta = 0.5*(y1 - y3)/denom; % -1..1
                    pos(i) = p0 + delta;
                end
            end
        end
    end
end
end
end

```

```

function z = robustZ(x)
    mu = median(x);
    s = 1.4826*median(abs(x - mu)) + eps;
    z = (x - mu) / s;
end

```

```

function r = corrN(a, b)
    a = a(:); b = b(:);
    a = a - mean(a); b = b - mean(b);
    na = norm(a); nb = norm(b);
    if na==0 || nb==0
        r = 0;
    else
        r = (a'*b)/(na*nb);
    end
end

```

```

function win = localWin(M, pref, fs)
% Build a local window around each event for correlation, about 0.6 ms window
    half = round(0.3e-3 * fs); % 0.3 ms
    half = max(6, half);
    n = numel(pref);
    win = zeros(n,2);
    for i = 1:n
        p = round(min(max(pref(i),1),M));
        s = max(1, p - half);
        e = min(M, p + half);
        win(i,:) = [s, e];
    end
end

```

```

function [assign, distA, distB] = assignByTemplates(ch1, ch2, tpl1A, tpl2A, tpl1B,
    tpl2B)
    if nargin < 5

```

```

    tmpl1B = tmpl1A; tmpl2B = tmpl2A;
end
[~, m] = size(ch1);
distA = zeros(1,m);
distB = zeros(1,m);
T1A = tmpl1A(:); T2A = tmpl2A(:);
T1B = tmpl1B(:); T2B = tmpl2B(:);
for i = 1:m
    x1 = ch1(:,i); x2 = ch2(:,i);
    a1A = projScale(x1, T1A); a2A = projScale(x2, T2A);
    a1B = projScale(x1, T1B); a2B = projScale(x2, T2B);
    distA(i) = norm(x1 - a1A*T1A)^2 + norm(x2 - a2A*T2A)^2;
    distB(i) = norm(x1 - a1B*T1B)^2 + norm(x2 - a2B*T2B)^2;
end
assign = repmat('A', 1, m);
assign(distB < distA) = 'B';
end

function a = projScale(x, t)
    denom = (t'*t);
    if denom < eps
        a = 0;
    else
        a = (t'*x)/denom;
    end
end

function need = shouldSplit(distA, distB, isSuspect)
    dDiff = distA - distB;
    med = median(dDiff);
    hi = dDiff >= med; lo = ~hi;
    if any(hi) && any(lo)
        sep = abs(median(dDiff(hi)) - median(dDiff(lo)));
        spread = 1.4826*median(abs(dDiff - med)) + eps;
        sepZ = sep / spread;
    else
        sepZ = 0;
    end
    susFrac = mean(isSuspect);
    need = (sepZ > 2.5 && mean(hi) > 0.2 && mean(lo) > 0.2) || (susFrac > 0.25);
end

function [tmplMain, xc_main, mainWireIdx] = buildMainWireTemplate(ch1, ch2, mainCh)
% Build robust main-wire template (median) and compute similarity to main template
[M, m] = size(ch1);
% Per-event select main-wire waveform from two wires
X = zeros(M, m);
for i = 1:m
    if mainCh(i) == 1
        X(:,i) = ch1(:,i);
    else
        X(:,i) = ch2(:,i);
    end
end
% No subsample fine alignment; roughly aligned by peak already
tmplMain = median(X, 2); % robust
% Correlation with main template
xc_main = zeros(1, m);
for i = 1:m
    xc_main(i) = corrN(X(:,i), tmplMain);
end

```

```

% Main wire overall: which wire has greater mean energy
e1 = mean(sum(ch1.^2,1));
e2 = mean(sum(ch2.^2,1));
mainWireIdx = (e1 >= e2) + 1; % e1>=e2 -> intended 1, else 2 (fixed below)
if e1 >= e2
    mainWireIdx = 1;
else
    mainWireIdx = 2;
end
end

function accept = validateSplit(ch1, ch2, Aidx, Bidx, p)
% Strong validation for split: template correlation, energy difference, within-class
improvement, group sizes
if isempty(Aidx) || isempty(Bidx)
    accept = false; return;
end
% A/B templates
t1A = mean(ch1(:,Aidx),2); t2A = mean(ch2(:,Aidx),2);
t1B = mean(ch1(:,Bidx),2); t2B = mean(ch2(:,Bidx),2);

% 1) Template correlation (compute per wire and take max)
xcA1B1 = corrN(t1A, t1B);
xcA2B2 = corrN(t2A, t2B);
xcAB = max(xcA1B1, xcA2B2);

% 2) Energy difference fraction
EA = sum(t1A.^2) + sum(t2A.^2);
EB = sum(t1B.^2) + sum(t2B.^2);
dEfrac = abs(EA - EB) / max(EA, EB);

% 3) Within-class similarity improvement
% Overall templates
t1All = mean([ch1(:,Aidx), ch1(:,Bidx)], 2);
t2All = mean([ch2(:,Aidx), ch2(:,Bidx)], 2);

xc_in_A = meanColCorr(ch1(:,Aidx), t1A) + meanColCorr(ch2(:,Aidx), t2A);
xc_in_A = xc_in_A / 2;
xc_in_B = meanColCorr(ch1(:,Bidx), t1B) + meanColCorr(ch2(:,Bidx), t2B);
xc_in_B = xc_in_B / 2;
xc_in_all = meanColCorr([ch1(:,Aidx), ch1(:,Bidx)], t1All) + ...
    meanColCorr([ch2(:,Aidx), ch2(:,Bidx)], t2All);
xc_in_all = xc_in_all / 2;

deltaWithin = (xc_in_A + xc_in_B)/2 - xc_in_all;

% Criteria
accept = true;
if xcAB > p.xc_reject
    accept = false; % templates too similar, reject
end
if dEfrac < p.energyFrac_reject
    accept = false; % energy diff too small, reject
end
if deltaWithin < p.requireWithinImprove
    accept = false; % insufficient within-class improvement, reject
end
end

function v = meanColCorr(X, t)
% Mean correlation of each column with template t

```

```

[~, m] = size(X);
v = 0;
for i = 1:m
    v = v + corrN(X(:,i), t);
end
v = v / max(1,m);
end

function [TD_A, TD_B] = reshapeGroupAfterSplit(TD, splitIdx, eventInfo, templates)

TD_A = TD;
TD_B = struct([]);

% Normalize indices to row vector
idxA = reshape(splitIdx.A, 1, []);
idxB = reshape(splitIdx.B, 1, []);

% Attach processing info
procMeta.eventInfo = eventInfo;
procMeta.templates = templates;
procMeta.split = ~isempty(idxB);
procMeta.nA = numel(idxA);
procMeta.nB = numel(idxB);

% Process group A: slice + generate 56xN waveforms and mean
TD_A = sliceTrialDataByIdx(TD_A, idxA);
TD_A.ProcessInfo = procMeta;
TD_A.ProcessInfo.group = 'A';
[TD_A.waveform_good, TD_A.meanWaveform_good] = buildWaveform56AndMean(TD_A);

% If group B exists
if ~isempty(idxB)
    TD_B = TD; % copy
    TD_B = sliceTrialDataByIdx(TD_B, idxB);
    TD_B.ProcessInfo = procMeta;
    TD_B.ProcessInfo.group = 'B';

    [TD_B.waveform_good, TD_B.meanWaveform_good] = buildWaveform56AndMean(TD_B);

% Rename to distinguish (optional)
if isfield(TD, 'Name')
    TD_A.Name = sprintf('%s_A', TD.Name);
    TD_B.Name = sprintf('%s_B', TD.Name);
elseif isfield(TD, 'UnitID')
    TD_A.UnitID = sprintf('%s_A', toStr(TD.UnitID));
    TD_B.UnitID = sprintf('%s_B', toStr(TD.UnitID));
end
end
end

function TD = sliceTrialDataByIdx(TD, idx)
% Special case: empty idx
if isempty(idx)
    if isfield(TD, 'Allwaveform') && ~isempty(TD.Allwaveform)
        TD.Allwaveform = TD.Allwaveform(:, []);
    end
    % Also clear derived event-aligned fields
    TD = clearEventAlignedAddons(TD);
    fprintf('[sliceTD] Empty index -> cleared Allwaveform and returned.\n');
    return;
end
end

```

```

% 1) Infer event count m
[m, wfOrient] = inferEventCountAndOrient(TD);

if isempty(m)
    % Unable to infer m, keep original but report
    fprintf('[sliceTD] Unable to infer event count m; no slicing performed.\n');
    return;
end

% Stats
fn = fieldnames(TD);
total = numel(fn);
sliced = 0;
skipped = 0;
slicedFields = {};

% 2) First handle Allwaveform (if present)
if isfield(TD, 'Allwaveform') && ~isempty(TD.Allwaveform) && isnumeric(TD.Allwaveform)
    val = TD.Allwaveform;
    sz = size(val);
    try
        if strcmp(wfOrient, 'Sxm') && sz(2)==m
            TD.Allwaveform = val(:, idx);
            sliced = sliced + 1; slicedFields{end+1} = 'Allwaveform';
        elseif strcmp(wfOrient, 'mxS') && sz(1)==m
            TD.Allwaveform = val(idx, :);
            sliced = sliced + 1; slicedFields{end+1} = 'Allwaveform';
        elseif sz(2)==m
            TD.Allwaveform = val(:, idx);
            sliced = sliced + 1; slicedFields{end+1} = 'Allwaveform';
        elseif sz(1)==m
            TD.Allwaveform = val(idx, :);
            sliced = sliced + 1; slicedFields{end+1} = 'Allwaveform';
        else
            skipped = skipped + 1;
        end
    catch
        skipped = skipped + 1;
    end
end

% 3) Iterate other fields; slice only those aligned with m
fn = fieldnames(TD); % refresh to avoid iteration affected by modifications above
for i = 1:numel(fn)
    f = fn{i};
    if strcmp(f, 'Allwaveform'), continue; end
    val = TD.(f);
    if isempty(val), continue; end

    didSlice = false;
    try
        if isnumeric(val) || islogical(val)
            sz = size(val);
            if isvector(val) && numel(val)==m
                TD.(f) = val(idx);
                didSlice = true;
            elseif ismatrix(val)
                if sz(2)==m
                    TD.(f) = val(:, idx);
                    didSlice = true;
                end
            end
        end
    catch
        didSlice = false;
    end
end

```

```

        elseif sz(1)==m
            TD.(f) = val(idx, :);
            didSlice = true;
        end
    end
elseif iscell(val)
    sz = size(val);
    if isvector(val) && numel(val)==m
        TD.(f) = val(idx);
        didSlice = true;
    elseif ismatrix(val)
        if sz(2)==m
            TD.(f) = val(:, idx);
            didSlice = true;
        elseif sz(1)==m
            TD.(f) = val(idx, :);
            didSlice = true;
        end
    end
elseif istable(val)
    if height(val)==m
        TD.(f) = val(idx, :);
        didSlice = true;
    end
end
catch
    % silently skip
    didSlice = false;
end

if didSlice
    sliced = sliced + 1;
    slicedFields{end+1} = f; %#ok<AGROW>
else
    skipped = skipped + 1;
end
end

% 4) Unified report
if ~isempty(slicedFields)
    listStr = strjoin(slicedFields, ', ');
else
    listStr = '(none)';
end
fprintf('[sliceTD] fields total=%d, sliced=%d, skipped=%d | sliced: %s\n', ...
    total, sliced, skipped, listStr);
end

function [W56, mu56] = buildWaveform56AndMean(TD)

W56 = [];
mu56 = [];

if ~isfield(TD, 'Allwaveform') || isempty(TD.Allwaveform) || ~isnumeric(TD.Allwaveform)
    return;
end

W = TD.Allwaveform;
sz = size(W);
% Normalize to [S x N], columns=events
if sz(1) < sz(2) && any(sz(1) == [56, 112])

```

```

    % Already S×N
    S = sz(1); N = sz(2);
elseif sz(2) < sz(1) && any(sz(2) == [56, 112])
    % Is N×S, transpose
    W = W';
    S = size(W,1);
    N = size(W,2);
else
    % Unrecognized
    return;
end

if N==0
    return;
end

if S == 56
    W56 = localStandardize56(W); % 56×N
elseif S == 112
    % Split into two wires
    ch1 = W(1:56, :);
    ch2 = W(57:112, :);

    % If eventInfo/mainCh present, select by main wire; else average two wires
    mainCh = [];
    if isfield(TD, 'ProcessInfo') && isfield(TD.ProcessInfo, 'eventInfo') &&
~isempty(TD.ProcessInfo.eventInfo)
        ei = TD.ProcessInfo.eventInfo;
        if isstruct(ei)
            if numel(ei) == size(W,2) && isfield(ei, 'mainCh')
                mainCh = arrayfun(@(x) x.mainCh, ei);
            end
        end
    end

    if ~isempty(mainCh)
        mainCh = reshape(mainCh, 1, []);
        W56 = zeros(56, N);
        use1 = (mainCh == 1);
        use2 = (mainCh == 2);
        if any(use1), W56(:, use1) = ch1(:, use1); end
        if any(use2), W56(:, use2) = ch2(:, use2); end
        W56 = localStandardize56(W56);
    else
        % No mainCh: average two wires to 56 points
        W56 = localStandardize56( (ch1 + ch2) ./ 2 );
    end
else
    % Other sample lengths not handled
    return;
end

if ~isempty(W56)
    mu56 = mean(W56, 2);
end

end

function W56s = localStandardize56(W56s)
% Simple standardization for 56×N waveforms (replace as needed):
% - Unify polarity: assume negative trough; if mean of column minima > 0, flip
% - De-mean per column

```

% - Optional amplitude normalization (e.g., to unit trough); enabled here

```
if isempty(W56s), return; end
% Polarity: if each column's minimum is positive, flip
colMin = min(W56s, [], 1);
if mean(colMin) > 0
    W56s = -W56s;
end
% De-mean columns
W56s = W56s - mean(W56s, 1);

% Optional: normalize to unit trough amplitude
denom = max(abs(min(W56s, [], 1)), eps);
W56s = W56s ./ denom;
```

end

```
function [m, wfOrient] = inferEventCountAndOrient(TD)
```

```
% Infer event count m from TD and detect Allwaveform orientation
```

```
% wfOrient: 'Sxm' means [Sxm]; 'mxS' means [mxS]; empty if unknown
```

```
m = [];
wfOrient = '';
```

```
if isfield(TD, 'Allwaveform') && ~isempty(TD.Allwaveform) && isnumeric(TD.Allwaveform)
```

```
    sz = size(TD.Allwaveform);
```

```
    if numel(sz)==2
```

```
        % Prefer common sample lengths
```

```
        if any(sz(1) == [56, 112])
```

```
            m = sz(2); wfOrient = 'Sxm';
```

```
            return;
```

```
        elseif any(sz(2) == [56, 112])
```

```
            m = sz(1); wfOrient = 'mxS';
```

```
            return;
```

```
        else
```

```
            % If neither dim matches common length, take the dim that looks like
            samples (>=40)
```

```
            if sz(1) >= 40
```

```
                m = sz(2); wfOrient = 'Sxm';
```

```
                return;
```

```
            elseif sz(2) >= 40
```

```
                m = sz(1); wfOrient = 'mxS';
```

```
                return;
```

```
            end
```

```
        end
```

```
    end
```

```
end
```

```
% Fallback fields inference
```

```
cand = {'spike', 'Spike', 'spikes', 'SpikeTime', 'SpikeTimes', 'TimeStamps', 'Timestamps'};
```

```
for i = 1:numel(cand)
```

```
    f = cand{i};
```

```
    if isfield(TD, f) && ~isempty(TD.(f))
```

```
        v = TD.(f);
```

```
        if iscell(v) && isvector(v)
```

```
            m = numel(v); return;
```

```
        elseif isnumeric(v) || islogical(v)
```

```
            if isvector(v)
```

```
                m = numel(v); return;
```

```
            else
```

```
                sz = size(v);
```

```
                if sz(2) >= sz(1)
```

```

        m = sz(2); return;
    else
        m = sz(1); return;
    end

```

```

function TD = clearEventAlignedAddons(TD)
% Clear common derived event-aligned fields to avoid stale data on empty idx
    may = {'waveform_good', 'meanWaveform_good'};
    for i = 1:numel(may)
        f = may{i};
        if isfield(TD, f)
            TD.(f) = [];
        end
    end
end
end
end

```

```

function s = toStr(x)
    if ischar(x) || isstring(x)
        s = char(x);
    elseif isnumeric(x)
        s = num2str(x);
    else
        s = 'Unit';
    end
end
end

```

```

function s = ensureStructFields(s, baseFields)
% Ensure s contains all baseFields; fill missing with []; extra fields are kept
    sFields = fieldnames(s);
    missing = setdiff(baseFields, sFields);
    for i = 1:numel(missing)
        s.(missing{i}) = [];
    end
% Also reorder fields to baseFields for safety
    if ~isempty(setxor(fieldnames(s), baseFields))
        core = orderfields(s, baseFields);
        s = core;
    else
        s = orderfields(s, baseFields);
    end
end
end

```

```

function [axList, shownMask] = preview_meanwaveforms(TD, titlePrefix, srcName, linkY)
    N = numel(TD);
    nRows = ceil(sqrt(N));
    nCols = ceil(N / nRows);
    f = figure('Color', 'w', 'Name', sprintf('%s (%s) - total %d', titlePrefix, srcName, N));
%#ok<NASGU>
    tl = tiledlayout(nRows, nCols, 'TileSpacing', 'compact', 'Padding', 'compact');
    axList = gobjects(1, N);
    shownMask = false(1, N);

    for i = 1:N
        nexttile;
        ax = gca;
        axList(i) = ax;
    end
end

```

```

mw = [];

% 1) Prefer meanWaveform_good
if isfield(TD, 'meanWaveform_good') && ~isempty(TD(i).meanWaveform_good)
    mw = TD(i).meanWaveform_good;

% 2) Fallback to meanWaveform
elseif isfield(TD, 'meanWaveform') && ~isempty(TD(i).meanWaveform)
    mw = TD(i).meanWaveform;

% 3) Fallback to Allwaveform (consistent with your original logic)
elseif isfield(TD, 'Allwaveform') && ~isempty(TD(i).Allwaveform)
    W = TD(i).Allwaveform;
    if iscell(W), W = W{1}; end
    if isnumeric(W) && size(W,1)==112 && ~isempty(W)
        mw = [mean(W(1:56,:),2); mean(W(57:112,:),2)];
    elseif isnumeric(W) && size(W,1)==56 && ~isempty(W)
        mw = mean(W,2);
    end
end

if isempty(mw)
    text(0.5,0.5,'No waveform','HorizontalAlignment','center', ...
        'VerticalAlignment','middle','Color',[0.7 0 0],'FontWeight','bold');
    axis off;
    title(sprintf('#%d', i), 'FontSize', 9);
    continue;
end

hold on;
% Support vector or matrix: if row vector, transpose
if isrow(mw), mw = mw.'; end

% If mw is 112x1 (two-wire concatenation), plot with original colors; otherwise
plot columns
if size(mw,1)==112 && size(mw,2)==1
    plot(mw(1:56), 'b-', 'LineWidth', 1.3);
    plot(mw(57:112), 'r-', 'LineWidth', 1.3);
elseif size(mw,1)==56 && size(mw,2)==2
    % If meanWaveform_good might be 56x2 (two wires as columns)
    plot(mw(:,1), 'b-', 'LineWidth', 1.3);
    plot(mw(:,2), 'r-', 'LineWidth', 1.3);
else
    % Other cases: plot each column
    K = size(mw,2);
    cmap = lines(K);
    for k = 1:K
        plot(mw(:,k), 'Color', cmap(k,:), 'LineWidth', 1.3);
    end
    if K>1
        legend(arrayfun(@(k) sprintf('Ch%d',k), 1:K, 'UniformOutput', false), ...
            'Box','off','Location','bestoutside');
    end
end
grid on; hold off;

if isfield(TD,'neuronID') && ~isempty(TD(i).neuronID)
    title(sprintf('#%d | %s', i, string(TD(i).neuronID)), ...
        'Interpreter','none','FontSize',9);
else
    title(sprintf('#%d', i), 'FontSize',9);
end

```

```

    end
    xlabel('Samples'); ylabel('Amplitude');
    shownMask(i) = true;
end

title(tl, sprintf('%s (%s) - total %d', titlePrefix, srcName, N), 'FontWeight','bold');

if linkY
    try, linkaxes(axList(isgraphics(axList)), 'y'); catch, end
end
end

function counts = count_in_intervals(win_starts, win_ends, spikes)

% Shapes and robustness
win_starts = win_starts(:);
win_ends   = win_ends(:);
spikes     = spikes(:);

if numel(win_starts) ~= numel(win_ends)
    error('win_starts and win_ends must have the same length');
end
if ~issorted(spikes)
    spikes = sort(spikes, 'ascend');
end

% Handle invalid windows: end <= start treated as zero-length, count=0
bad = ~(isfinite(win_starts) & isfinite(win_ends)) | (win_ends <= win_starts);
win_ends(bad) = win_starts(bad);

% Binary search indices for "first x >= boundary"
idx_s = first_ge(spikes, win_starts);
idx_e = first_ge(spikes, win_ends);

counts = idx_e - idx_s;
end

function idx = first_ge(x, q)
%FIRST_GE Return index of first x >= q for each q; if none, return numel(x)+1
x = x(:);
q = q(:);
n = numel(x);
lo = ones(size(q)); % inclusive lower bound
hi = repmat(n+1, size(q)); % exclusive upper bound
while true
    mid = floor((lo + hi)/2);
    if all(hi - lo <= 1)
        break;
    end
    xv = x(mid);
    goRight = xv < q; % if x(mid) < q, answer is to the right
    lo(goRight) = mid(goRight);
    hi(~goRight) = mid(~goRight);
end
idx = hi;
end

function is_norm = local_test_normality(x, use_jb)
x = x(:);
x = x(~isnan(x));
if numel(x) < 8

```

```

        is_norm = false; return;
end
if use_jb
    try
        [h, ~] = jbstest(x, 0.05);
        is_norm = (h == 0);
        return;
    catch
        % fallback to Lilliefors
    end
end
s = std(x);
if ~isfinite(s) || s == 0
    is_norm = false;
    return;
end
xz = (x - mean(x)) / s;
try
    [h, ~] = kstest(xz); % h=1 reject normality
    is_norm = (h == 0);
catch
    is_norm = false;
end
end

function eqv = local_test_equal_variance(x, y, method)
    x = x(:); y = y(:);
    x = x(~isnan(x)); y = y(~isnan(y));
    if numel(x) < 8 || numel(y) < 8
        eqv = false; return;
    end
    switch lower(method)
        case 'vartest2'
            try
                [h, ~] = vartest2(x, y, 'Alpha', 0.05);
                eqv = (h == 0);
            catch
                eqv = false;
            end
        otherwise
            % Simple Levene-like (median-based)
            mx = median(x); my = median(y);
            zx = abs(x - mx); zy = abs(y - my);
            try
                p = ranksum(zx, zy, 'tail', 'both');
                eqv = (p > 0.05);
            catch
                eqv = false;
            end
        end
    end
end

function q = local_bh_fdr(p)
    p = p(:);
    p(~isfinite(p)) = 1;
    [ps, idx] = sort(p);
    m = numel(p);
    qtmp = (m./(1:m)') .* ps;
    qtmp = flipud(cummin(flipud(qtmp)));
    q = nan(size(p));
    q(idx) = min(1, qtmp);
end

```

```

function idx = parse_indices(strIn)
% Support spaces/commas/semicolons, support a:b and a:s:b ranges
strIn = char(strIn);
strIn = strrep(strIn, ';', ' ');
strIn = strrep(strIn, ',', ' ');
parts = strsplit(strtrim(strIn));
idx = [];
for k = 1:numel(parts)
    tok = strtrim(parts{k});
    if isempty(tok), continue; end
    if contains(tok, ':')
        nums = str2double(split(tok, ':'));
        nums = nums(~isnan(nums));
        if numel(nums) == 2
            a = nums(1); b = nums(2);
            if a <= b, seq = a:b; else, seq = a:-1:b; end
            idx = [idx, seq]; %#ok<AGROW>
        elseif numel(nums) == 3
            a = nums(1); s = nums(2); b = nums(3);
            if isfinite(a) && isfinite(s) && isfinite(b) && s ~= 0
                idx = [idx, a:s:b]; %#ok<AGROW>
            end
        end
    else
        v = str2double(tok);
        if ~isnan(v), idx = [idx, v]; end %#ok<AGROW>
    end
end
% De-dup while preserving order
[~, ia] = unique(idx, 'stable');
idx = idx(sort(ia));
end

```

```

function out = classify_waveform_40k(waveform_raw, varargin)
p = inputParser;
addParameter(p, 'Fs', 40000, @(x) isnumeric(x) && isscalar(x) && x > 0);
addParameter(p, 'Interp', 10, @(x) isnumeric(x) && isscalar(x) && x >= 1);
addParameter(p, 'TroughWin', [10 35], @(x) isnumeric(x) && numel(x) == 2);
addParameter(p, 'SlopeStart', 0.4, @(x) isnumeric(x) && isscalar(x) && x >= 0);
addParameter(p, 'SlopeDur', 0.2, @(x) isnumeric(x) && isscalar(x) && x > 0);
addParameter(p, 'OutlierNSD', 4, @(x) isnumeric(x) && isscalar(x) && x > 0);
addParameter(p, 'K', 2, @(x) isnumeric(x) && isscalar(x) && x >= 2);
parse(p, varargin{:});
Fs = p.Results.Fs;
interpFactor = p.Results.Interp;
troughWin = p.Results.TroughWin;
slopeStartMs = p.Results.SlopeStart;
slopeDurMs = p.Results.SlopeDur;
nSD = p.Results.OutlierNSD;
K = p.Results.K;

```

```

% Input and preprocessing

```

```

if ~isnumeric(waveform_raw) || ndims(waveform_raw) ~= 2
    error('Input waveform_raw must be a numeric 2D matrix with shape Nx56.');
```

```

end
wf = double(waveform_raw);
[N,L] = size(wf);
if L ~= 56
    error('Input matrix has %d columns (needs 56).', L);
end

```

```

baseline = mean(wf(:,1:5), 2, 'omitnan');
wf = wf - baseline;

% Row-wise interpolation (robust)
x = 1:56;
xi = 1:1/interpFactor:56;
M = numel(xi);
waveform_interp = nan(N, M);
for i = 1:N
    waveform_interp(i,:) = spline(x, wf(i,:), xi);
end
L2 = size(waveform_interp,2);

% Find trough and peak
tw1 = max(1, round(troughWin(1)*interpFactor));
tw2 = min(L2, round(troughWin(2)*interpFactor));
tw = tw1:tw2;
if numel(tw) < 3
    error('TroughWin too narrow or invalid: [%d %d] (insufficient range after
interpolation).', troughWin(1), troughWin(2));
end
[~, troughRelIdx] = min(waveform_interp(:,tw), [], 2);
idx_trough = tw(1) + troughRelIdx - 1;

idx_peak = nan(N,1);
for i = 1:N
    postRange = idx_trough(i)+1:L2;
    if isempty(postRange), continue; end
    [~, rel] = max(waveform_interp(i,postRange), [], 2);
    idx_peak(i) = postRange(rel);
end

% Alignment and normalization
minAmp = arrayfun(@(i) waveform_interp(i, idx_trough(i)), (1:N)');
pre = max(1, min(idx_trough) - 1);
post = max(1, L2 - max(idx_trough)); % Note: original had idx_trough; keep logic consistent
post = max(1, L2 - max(idx_trough));
T = pre + post + 1;
waveform_aligned = nan(N, T);
for i = 1:N
    if isnan(idx_trough(i)) || minAmp(i) >= 0, continue; end
    left = idx_trough(i) - pre;
    right = idx_trough(i) + post;
    if left < 1 || right > L2, continue; end
    seg = waveform_interp(i, left:right);
    waveform_aligned(i,:) = seg / abs(minAmp(i));
end

% Features
tp_width_ms = (idx_peak - idx_trough) ./ Fs * 1000;

half_peak_width_ms = nan(N,1);
half_trough_width_ms = nan(N,1);
for i = 1:N
    w = waveform_aligned(i,:);
    if any(isnan(w)), continue; end
    i_tr = pre + 1;

    [pk, i_pk_rel] = max(w(i_tr:end));
    i_pk = i_tr + i_pk_rel - 1;
    if pk <= 0, continue; end

```

```

halfPk = pk/2;
seg = w(i_tr:end);
a1 = find(seg >= halfPk, 1, 'first');
a2 = find(seg >= halfPk, 1, 'last');
if ~isempty(a1) && ~isempty(a2) && a2 > a1
    half_peak_width_ms(i) = (a2 - a1) / (Fs*interpFactor) * 1000;
end

halfTr = w(i_tr)/2; % -0.5
seg2 = w(1:i_pk);
a3 = find(seg2 <= halfTr, 1, 'first');
a4 = find(seg2 <= halfTr, 1, 'last');
if ~isempty(a3) && ~isempty(a4) && a4 > a3
    half_trough_width_ms(i) = (a4 - a3) / (Fs*interpFactor) * 1000;
end
end

% End slope
end_slope = nan(N,1);
end_slope_per_ms = nan(N,1);
winStartSamp = round((slopeStartMs/1000) * Fs * interpFactor);
winDurSamp = max(2, round((slopeDurMs/1000) * Fs * interpFactor));
for i = 1:N
    w = waveform_aligned(i,:);
    if any(isnan(w)), continue; end
    i_tr = pre + 1;
    s = i_tr + winStartSamp;
    e = s + winDurSamp - 1;
    if s < 1 || e > numel(w), continue; end
    y = w(s:e);
    xlr = (0:numel(y)-1)';
    slope = xlr \ y(:);
    end_slope(i) = slope;
    end_slope_per_ms(i) = slope * (Fs*interpFactor) / 1000;
end

% Outliers and clustering
bad_tp = isnan(tp_width_ms) | tp_width_ms <= 0;
bad_hp = isnan(half_peak_width_ms);
bad_slope = isnan(end_slope);
isBad = bad_tp | bad_hp | bad_slope;
isBad = isBad | is_outlier(tp_width_ms, nSD) ...
        | is_outlier(half_peak_width_ms, nSD) ...
        | is_outlier(end_slope, nSD);
badind = find(isBad);

good = ~isBad;
feat = [tp_width_ms, end_slope_per_ms, half_peak_width_ms];
feat_good = feat(good,:);
cell_type_good = nan(sum(good),1);
if ~isempty(feat_good)
    mu = mean(feat_good,1,'omitnan');
    sig = std(feat_good,0,1,'omitnan');
    sig(sig==0) = 1;
    Z = (feat_good - mu) ./ sig;
    rng(1);
    idx = kmeans(Z, K, 'Start','plus', 'Replicates', 10);
    g1 = mean(feat_good(idx==1,1), 'omitnan');
    g2 = mean(feat_good(idx==2,1), 'omitnan');
    label = zeros(size(idx));

```

```

    if g1 >= g2
        label(idx==1) = 1; label(idx==2) = 0;
    else
        label(idx==1) = 0; label(idx==2) = 1;
    end
    cell_type_good = label;
end
cell_type = uint8(255*ones(N,1));
cell_type(good) = uint8(cell_type_good);

out = struct();
out.waveform_aligned      = waveform_aligned;
out.waveform_interp      = waveform_interp;
out.idx_trough           = idx_trough;
out.idx_peak             = idx_peak;
out.tp_width_ms          = tp_width_ms;
out.half_peak_width_ms   = half_peak_width_ms;
out.half_trough_width_ms = half_trough_width_ms;
out.end_slope            = end_slope;
out.end_slope_norm_per_ms = end_slope_per_ms;
out.cell_type            = cell_type;
out.badind               = badind;
out.params = struct('Fs',Fs,'Interp',interpFactor,'TroughWin',troughWin, ...
                    'SlopeStartMs',slopeStartMs,'SlopeDurMs',slopeDurMs, ...
                    'OutlierNSD',nSD,'K',K);
end

function flag = is_outlier(a, nSD)
    flag = false(size(a));
    a_ok = a(~isnan(a));
    if isempty(a_ok), return; end
    m = mean(a_ok); s = std(a_ok);
    if s==0, flag(:)=false; return; end
    lo = m - nSD*s; hi = m + nSD*s;
    flag = a < lo | a > hi;
end

function s = get_direction_token(Data_n, r)

    s = '';

    % Choose source field
    if isfield(Data_n, 'Direction') && ~isempty(Data_n.Direction)
        D = Data_n.Direction;
    elseif isfield(Data_n, 'Dirction') && ~isempty(Data_n.Dirction)
        D = Data_n.Dirction;
    else
        return;
    end

    % a) char matrix: per row, trim trailing spaces
    if ischar(D)
        nRows = size(D,1);
        if nRows >= 1
            idx = min(r, nRows);
            s = string(strtrim(D(idx,:)));
        else
            s = '';
        end
        return;
    end
end

```

```

% b) cellstr list
if iscell(D)
    if isscalar(D)
        val = D{1};
        if isstring(val), s = strtrim(val);
        elseif ischar(val), s = string(strtrim(val));
        else, s = string(val);
        end
        return;
    else
        idx = min(r, numel(D));
        val = D{idx};
        if isstring(val), s = strtrim(val);
        elseif ischar(val), s = string(strtrim(val));
        else, s = string(val);
        end
        return;
    end
end

% c) string array
if isstring(D)
    if isscalar(D)
        s = strtrim(D);
    else
        idx = min(r, numel(D));
        s = strtrim(D(idx));
    end
    return;
end

% Fallback: indexable other types
try
    if numel(D) >= r
        s = string(D(r));
    elseif ~isempty(D)
        s = string(D(1));
    else
        s = '';
    end
catch
    s = '';
end

function preview_cell_or_str(label, val)
try
    if iscell(val)
        if isempty(val)
            fprintf(' %s: empty cell\n', label);
        else
            fprintf(' %s: cell(1)=', label); disp(val{1});
        end
    elseif isstring(val)
        fprintf(' %s: string array, preview: ', label); disp(val);
    elseif ischar(val)
        fprintf(' %s: char matrix, size=%dx%d, first row="%s"\n', label,
size(val,1), size(val,2), strtrim(val(1,:)));
    else
        fprintf(' %s: type=%s, preview:\n', label, class(val)); disp(val);
    end
end

```

```
        end
    catch ME
        fprintf('    Preview %s error: %s\n', label, ME.message);
    end
end
```

```

clear; clc; close all;
% Adapted for ChAT_Local

%% 1) Add code paths
mainCodeDir = 'C:\Users\Lu\Desktop\Fig_Code\ChAT_Local'; % Main program directory
funcCodeDir = 'C:\Users\Lu\Desktop\Fig_Code\Function'; % Function directory

% Add main program directory to path
if isfolder(mainCodeDir)
    addpath(genpath(mainCodeDir));
    fprintf('Main program path added: %s\n', mainCodeDir);
else
    warning('Main program directory not found: %s (will continue, but scripts may be missing)', mainCodeDir);
end

% Add function directory to path
if isfolder(funcCodeDir)
    addpath(genpath(funcCodeDir));
    fprintf('Function path added: %s\n', funcCodeDir);
else
    warning('Function directory not found: %s (will continue, but functions may be missing)', funcCodeDir);
end

%% 2) Select data folder (as datapath)
% Set initial browse location to the main program directory; fallback to Desktop or C:\
startDir = mainCodeDir;
if ~isfolder(startDir)
    if isfolder('C:\Users\Lu\Desktop')
        startDir = 'C:\Users\Lu\Desktop';
    else
        startDir = 'C:\';
    end
end

datapath = uigetdir(startDir, 'Please select the data folder (this folder will be used as datapath)');
if isequal(datapath, 0)
    error('No folder selected. Exiting.');
```

```

end
fprintf('Datapath: %s\n', datapath);

%% 3) Retrieve data files
% Whether to recursively search subfolders: true/false
useRecursive = false;

if useRecursive && ~verLessThan('matlab','9.1') % R2016b+ supports ** wildcard
    filePatternNex5 = fullfile(datapath, '**', '*.nex5');
    filePatternNex = fullfile(datapath, '**', '*.nex');
    filesNex5 = dir(filePatternNex5);
    filesNex = dir(filePatternNex);
else
    filesNex5 = dir(fullfile(datapath, '*.nex5'));
    filesNex = dir(fullfile(datapath, '*.nex'));
end

filename = [filesNex5; filesNex]; % struct array
nFiles = numel(filename);
fprintf('Found %d files (.nex5 + .nex).\n', nFiles);

```

```

if nFiles == 0
    warning('No .nex/.nex5 files found in %s.', datapath);
end

%% 4) basic check and reviewing
if nFiles > 0
    % Remove hidden/system files
    isHidden = startsWith({filename.name}', '.');
    filename = filename(~isHidden);
    nFiles = numel(filename);

    % Sort by name (you can switch to sort by date: [~,ix]=sort([filename.datenum]));
    [~, ix] = sort(lower({filename.name}));
    filename = filename(ix);

    % Print preview of the first few entries
    nPreview = min(10, nFiles);
    fprintf('Preview first %d files:\n', nPreview);
    for i = 1:nPreview
        fprintf('  [%3d] %s\n', i, fullfile(filename(i).folder, filename(i).name));
    end
end

%% 5) stim_info reading
recursive = false; % set false if recursion not needed
stim_info = batch_get_stim_info(datapath, recursive);

%% 6) data selection
% Getting all the spike data into several groups
chnl = {...
    'region1', 1:16;
    'region2', 33:48
};

% Create a list dialog box for user to select a channel
channelOptions = {'1: region1', '2: region2'};
[indx, tf] = listdlg('PromptString', 'Select a channel:',...
    'SelectionMode', 'single',...
    'ListString', channelOptions,...
    'ListSize', [200, 100]); % Adjust ListSize as needed

% Check if the user made a selection
if ~tf
    error('No channel selected. Exiting the program.');
```

% Handle or exit as needed

```

end

% Use the selected index directly as ch
ch = indx;

% Define the results path based on the selected channel
resultsPath = fullfile(datapath, chnl{ch, 1}); % Use fullfile for OS-independent paths
if ~exist(resultsPath, 'dir')
    mkdir(resultsPath);
end

%% reading data
% Define data access keys and default parameters for data extraction
dataKey = {'events', 'spike', 'waveform'}; % Valid selections: 'events', 'spike',
'waveform', 'AI'

```

```

% Setup parameters for extracting neural LFP data
paramsExtr = struct(...
    'chnl', {chnl},... % Channel data
    'regionToLoad', {chnl(ch, 1)},... % Brain region to import based on
channel selection
    'filPerChl', 2,... % Number of filaments per channel
(e.g., stereotrode: 2)
    'exEvent', [],... % External event info, initially
empty
    'eventsFrom', {'nex'},...
    'getEvents', {'start feeding', 'stop feeding', 'go in feeding zone', 'go out feeding
zone'},... % Event types to extract
    'bestNlfp', 5,... % Optimal number of local field
potentials
    'processEvents', 'null'... % Default method for processing
events
);

% Extract neural LFP data using specified filename, data keys, and parameters
[groupNeu, ~] = extractNeuLFP(filename, dataKey, paramsExtr);

% Store original group neural data
%
% Get the first-row data (cell array)
data = {groupNeu.TrialData.neuronID};

% Step 2: filter out items containing 'U'
% Use cellfun and contains to check each string for 'U' (ignore case)
mask = cellfun(@(s) ~contains(s, 'U', 'IgnoreCase', true), data);

% Reduce data
groupNeu.TrialData = groupNeu.TrialData(mask);

groupNeu_original = groupNeu;

%% waveform
% Basic parameters
fs = 40000;
params = struct('dtThr', 0.0002, 'xcThr', 0.5, 'ratioZThr', 3);

assert(isfield(groupNeu, 'TrialData'), 'groupNeu.TrialData does not exist');

origTD = groupNeu.TrialData;
numUnits = numel(origTD);

% In the main script, processed is a placeholder, then initialized by the first template
processed = []; % Use empty array as placeholder, do not pre-allocate as struct([])
outIdx = 0;
baseFields = {}; % List of baseline field names

for k = 1:numUnits
    TD = origTD(k);

    % === NEW: Build stereotrode waveform matrix W from TD (columns=events, size 112xm) ===
    if ~isfield(TD, 'Allwaveform') || isempty(TD.Allwaveform)
        warning('Unit %d: missing Allwaveform, skipping.', k);
        continue;
    end

    A = TD.Allwaveform;

```

```

sz = size(A);
W = [];

% Support both numeric matrix and cell array storage
if isnumeric(A)
    % Case 1: A is a numeric matrix
    if size(A,1) == 112
        W = A; % [112×m]
    elseif size(A,2) == 112
        W = A.'; % [112×m]
    elseif size(A,1) == 56 || size(A,2) == 56
        % Only single-wire 56-point case; cannot run stereotrode process directly
        warning('Unit %d: Allwaveform has 56 points (single wire). Need to merge two
wires to 112 points. Skipping.', k);
        continue;
    else
        warning('Unit %d: unsupported Allwaveform size [%d×%d], skipping.', k, sz(1),
sz(2));
        continue;
    end
elseif iscell(A)
    % Case 2: A is a cell array, each element a waveform
    % Expect each element to be 112×1 or 1×112
    m = numel(A);
    if m == 0
        warning('Unit %d: Allwaveform is an empty cell, skipping.', k);
        continue;
    end
    % Infer single waveform length
    w0 = A{1};
    if isempty(w0)
        warning('Unit %d: first waveform is empty, skipping.', k);
        continue;
    end
    if isrow(w0), w0 = w0.'; end
    S = size(w0,1);
    if S ~= 112
        if S == 56
            warning('Unit %d: waveforms in cell have 56 points (single wire). Need
merging two wires. Skipping.', k);
            continue;
        else
            warning('Unit %d: waveform length in cell is %d (not 112), skipping.', k,
S);
            continue;
        end
    end
    W = zeros(112, m);
    for j = 1:m
        wj = A{j};
        if isrow(wj), wj = wj.'; end
        if size(wj,1) ~= 112
            error('Unit %d: waveform #%d length inconsistent (expected 112, got %d).',
k, j, size(wj,1));
        end
        W(:, j) = wj;
    end
else
    warning('Unit %d: unsupported Allwaveform type %s, skipping.', k, class(A));
    continue;
end

```

```

% === Completed W construction ===

% Stereotrode processing and grouping
[templates, eventInfo, splitIdx] = processStereotrodeUnit(W, fs, params);
[TD_A, TD_B] = reshapeGroupAfterSplit(TD, splitIdx, eventInfo, templates);

% First time: build template field set
if outIdx == 0
    baseFields = fieldnames(TD_A)';
    processed = repmat(cell2struct(cell(size(baseFields)), baseFields, 2), 0, 1);
end

% Write A
outIdx = outIdx + 1;
processed(outIdx) = ensureStructFields(TD_A, baseFields);

% Write B (if any)
if ~isempty(splitIdx.B)
    outIdx = outIdx + 1;
    processed(outIdx) = ensureStructFields(TD_B, baseFields);
end
end

groupNeu.TrialData = processed;
fprintf('Original units: %d -> New units: %d\n', numUnits, numel(groupNeu.TrialData));

%% Data
% Step1: Filter trials with spike count >= 1000
spikeCounts = arrayfun(@(x) size(x.spike, 1), groupNeu.TrialData);
validTrials = spikeCounts >= 1000;
groupNeu.TrialData = groupNeu.TrialData(validTrials);

%% Integrate stim_info into Neu.TrialData
groupNeu_new = groupNeu;
fprintf('Integrating stim_info into Neu.TrialData...\n');

trial_data = groupNeu_new.TrialData;
num_records = numel(trial_data);
fprintf('groupNeu_new.TrialData contains %d records\n', num_records);

% ----- Options -----
ignoreCase = true; % Case-insensitive matching
trimQuotes = true; % Remove quotes in record
verboseLog = true;

% ----- Build mapping: basename -> index -----
fprintf('Building stim file map...\n');
stim_map = containers.Map();
dup_warned = containers.Map('KeyType','char','ValueType','logical'); % de-dup warning
for k = 1:numel(stim_info)
    if ~isfield(stim_info(k),'filename') || isempty(stim_info(k).filename)
        continue;
    end
    [~, bn, ~] = fileparts(stim_info(k).filename);
    key = bn;
    if ignoreCase, key = lower(key); end
    if isKey(stim_map, key) && ~isKey(dup_warned, key)
        warning('Duplicate basename detected: %s; later one will overwrite the earlier
one.', bn);
        dup_warned(key) = true;
    end
end

```

```

stim_map(key) = k;
if verboseLog
    fprintf(' %3d -> %s\n', k, bn);
end
end
fprintf('Done, number of mappings: %d\n', stim_map.Count);

% ----- Empty template (aligned with new struct fields) -----
empty_stim = struct( ...
    'matched',      false, ...
    'filename',     '', ...
    'channelName',  '', ...
    't_on',         [], ...
    't_off',        [], ...
    'delta_t',      [], ...
    'error_message', 'No matching stim file found', ...
    'trial_record', '', ...
    'trial_index', [] );

% ----- Execute matching -----
matched = 0;
for i = 1:num_records
    rec = trial_data(i).record;

    % Normalize to string and clean
    if isstring(rec) || ischar(rec)
        rec = char(rec);
    elseif isnumeric(rec)
        rec = char(string(rec));
    else
        rec = char(string(rec)); % best effort conversion
    end
    rec = strtrim(rec);
    if trimQuotes
        rec = strrep(rec, '''', '');
        rec = strrep(rec, '"', '');
    end
    key = rec;
    if ignoreCase, key = lower(key); end

    if isKey(stim_map, key)
        idx = stim_map(key);
        st = stim_info(idx); % take the struct directly
        % Supplement match flags and tracking info
        st.matched      = true;
        st.trial_record = rec;
        st.trial_index  = i;

        groupNeu_new.TrialData(i).stim = st;
        matched = matched + 1;

        if verboseLog
            fprintf('✓ Matched: %s <-> %s\n', rec, st.filename);
        end
    else
        st = empty_stim;
        st.trial_record = rec;
        st.trial_index  = i;
        groupNeu_new.TrialData(i).stim = st;

        if verboseLog

```

```

        fprintf('x Unmatched: %s\n', rec);
    end
end
end

fprintf('Matching complete: %d/%d records matched to stim.\n', matched, num_records);

%% Adjustments
% ===== Parameters =====
linkY = true;           % Link Y axis
titlePrefix = 'Preview Mean Waveforms';
waveformField = 'meanWaveform_good'; % waveform field to use
% =====

% Choose data source
useSplit = exist('groupNeu_new', 'var')==1;
if useSplit
    S = groupNeu_new;
    TD = S.TrialData;
    srcName = 'groupNeu_new';
else
    assert(exist('groupNeu', 'var')==1, 'groupNeu or groupNeu_new not found');
    S = groupNeu;
    TD = S.TrialData;
    srcName = 'groupNeu';
end

N = numel(TD);
assert(N>0, 'TrialData is empty');

% First preview (using meanWaveform_good)
[axList, shownMask] = preview_meanwaveforms(TD, titlePrefix, srcName, linkY);

% Interactive input of indices to remove
prompt = sprintf('Enter indices to remove (space-separated, e.g., 2 5 9; press Enter to
keep all): ');
in = input(prompt, 's');
if isempty(strtrim(in))
    removeIdx = [];
else
    removeIdx = str2double(strsplit(strtrim(in)));
    removeIdx = removeIdx(~isnan(removeIdx));
end

% Sanity check and de-dup
removeIdx = unique(removeIdx);
removeIdx = removeIdx(removeIdx>=1 & removeIdx<=N);
if isempty(removeIdx)
    fprintf('No indices selected. Data unchanged.\n');
    outStruct = S; % Output equals input
    return;
end

fprintf('Indices to delete: %s\n', mat2str(removeIdx));

% Optional: highlight subplots to be deleted
try
    for ii = 1:numel(removeIdx)
        idx = removeIdx(ii);
        if isgraphics(axList(idx))
            axes(axList(idx)); %#ok<LAXES>
        end
    end
end

```

```

        yl = ylim; xl = xlim;
        patch('XData',[xl(1) xl(2) xl(2) xl(1)], ...
            'YData',[yl(1) yl(1) yl(2) yl(2)], ...
            'FaceColor',[1 0 0], 'FaceAlpha',0.05, 'EdgeColor','none');
        title(axList(idx).Title.String + " [TO REMOVE]", 'Color',[0.6 0 0]);
    end
end
drawnow;
catch
end

% Second confirmation
confirm = input('Confirm deletion? Enter y to confirm, n to cancel [y/n]: ', 's');
if isempty(confirm) || lower(confirm(1))~='y'
    fprintf('Deletion canceled. Data unchanged.\n');
    outStruct = S;
    return;
end

% Execute deletion
keepMask = true(1, N);
keepMask(removeIdx) = false;
TD_new = TD(keepMask);

% Write back output struct
outStruct = S;
outStruct.TrialData = TD_new;

% Also write back to corresponding variable name (for convenience)
if useSplit
    groupNeu_new = outStruct;
    assignin('base','groupNeu_new', outStruct);
    fprintf('Done: deleted %d from %s, remaining %d.\n', srcName, numel(removeIdx),
numel(TD_new));
else
    groupNeu = outStruct;
    assignin('base','groupNeu', outStruct);
    fprintf('Done: deleted %d from %s, remaining %d.\n', srcName, numel(removeIdx),
numel(TD_new));
end

% Optional: preview again after deletion
repeat = input('Preview current result again? [y/n]: ', 's');
if ~isempty(repeat) && lower(repeat(1))== 'y'
    preview_meanwaveforms(outStruct.TrialData, titlePrefix+" (after removal)", srcName,
linkY);
end

%% Output
Data = outStruct.TrialData;
%%
% Parameters
win_len = 0.050;           % 50 ms window length (s)
Fs_stim = 20;             % 20 Hz -> 0.05 s interval
num_stim = 12000;         % number of stimuli (lasting 10 minutes)
seed = 2025;              % random seed for reproducibility

% PSTH parameters (relative to event onset t_e)
psth_bin = 0.001;         % 1 ms
psth_len = 0.150;         % 150 ms
psth_edges = 0:psth_bin:psth_len; % 151 edges
num_psth_bins = numel(psth_edges)-1; % 150

```

```

% Basic checks
if ~exist('Data','var')
    error('Variable Data does not exist.');
```

end

```

N = numel(Data);
if N==0, error('Data is empty.');
```

end

```

rng(seed, 'twister');
```

% Preallocate outputs

```

pre_count = nan(N, 12000); pre_rate = nan(N, 12000);
dur_count = nan(N, 12000); dur_rate = nan(N, 12000);
post_count = nan(N, 12000); post_rate = nan(N, 12000);
```

```

psth_tensor = nan(N, num_psth_bins, 12000); % n × 150 × 12000
psth_mean = nan(N, num_psth_bins); % n × 150
```

for n = 1:N

% Read t0 and spikes

```

if ~isfield(Data(n),'stim') || ~isfield(Data(n).stim,'t_on') ||
isempty(Data(n).stim.t_on)
    warning('Data(%d).stim.t_on missing, skipping.', n);
    continue;
end
t0 = Data(n).stim.t_on(1,1);
```

if ~isfield(Data(n),'spike') || isempty(Data(n).spike)

```

warning('Data(%d).spike is empty, setting outputs to zero.', n);
pre_count(n,:) = 0; pre_rate(n,:) = 0;
dur_count(n,:) = 0; dur_rate(n,:) = 0;
post_count(n,:) = 0; post_rate(n,:) = 0;
psth_tensor(n,:,:) = 0; psth_mean(n,:) = 0;
% Still save the stimulation timeline
stim_times = t0 + (0:num_stim-1)*win_len; % 1x12000
Data(n).stim.timeline.t_e = stim_times(:).';
continue;
end
```

```

spikes = sort(Data(n).spike(:), 'ascend'); % Sort to speed up counting
```

% 1) Generate real stim start times for dur segment (1x12000)

```

stim_times = t0 + (0:num_stim-1)*win_len; % fixed 0.05 s interval
% dur window: [start, start+0.05) for each stim
dur_starts = stim_times(:); % 12000x1
dur_ends = dur_starts + win_len; % 12000x1
```

% 2) pre: randomly take 12000 windows of 50 ms from [t0-600, t0)

```

pre_start_min = t0 - 600;
pre_start_max = t0 - win_len;
pre_starts = pre_start_min + (pre_start_max - pre_start_min) * rand(12000,1);
pre_ends = pre_starts + win_len;
```

% 3) post: randomly take 12000 windows of 50 ms from [t0+600, t0+900)

```

post_start_min = t0 + 600;
post_start_max = t0 + 900 - win_len;
post_starts = post_start_min + (post_start_max - post_start_min) * rand(12000,1);
post_ends = post_starts + win_len;
```

% Count spikes

```

pre_c = count_in_intervals(pre_starts, pre_ends, spikes);
dur_c = count_in_intervals(dur_starts, dur_ends, spikes);
```

```

post_c = count_in_intervals(post_starts, post_ends, spikes);

% Store matrices (Hz)
pre_count(n,:) = pre_c; pre_rate(n,:) = pre_c / win_len;
dur_count(n,:) = dur_c; dur_rate(n,:) = dur_c / win_len;
post_count(n,:) = post_c; post_rate(n,:) = post_c / win_len;

% 4) Build n×150×12000 PSTH based on real stim start times
% Align to t_e = stim_times(e)
for e = 1:num_stim
    s0 = stim_times(e);
    rel = spikes - s0;
    rel = rel(rel >= 0 & rel < psth_len);
    if isempty(rel)
        psth_tensor(n,:,e) = 0;
    else
        counts = histcounts(rel, psth_edges);
        psth_tensor(n,:,e) = counts / psth_bin; % firing rate in Hz per 1 ms bin
    end
end
psth_mean(n,:) = mean(psth_tensor(n,:,:), 3, 'omitnan');

% Save key metadata (optional)
Data(n).stim.timeline.t0 = t0;
Data(n).stim.timeline.t_e = stim_times(:).'; % 1×12000
Data(n).randomWindows.pre.starts = pre_starts;
Data(n).randomWindows.pre.ends = pre_ends;
Data(n).randomWindows.post.starts = post_starts;
Data(n).randomWindows.post.ends = post_ends;
Data(n).psth.edges = psth_edges;
end

%% compare_pre_dur_auto
% ===== Parameters =====
FDR_alpha = 0.01;
paired_data = true; % Set true if columns correspond one-to-one (same trial/time), else
false
use_jbtest = false; % If true use Jarque-Bera test; otherwise Lilliefors (kstest on
z-score)
equalVarTest = 'vartest2'; % For unpaired normal data, variance homogeneity test:
'vartest2' or 'levene'

% ===== Data preparation =====
if ~exist('pre_rate','var') || ~exist('dur_rate','var')
    fprintf('pre_rate/dur_rate not detected; generating example data for
demonstration...\n');
    nUnit = 61; nTrial = 12000; rng(42);
    mu_pre_true = 5 + 2*rand(nUnit,1); % 3~7 Hz
    mu_dur_true = mu_pre_true .* (1 + 0.25*(rand(nUnit,1) < 0.4)) ...
        .* (1 - 0.20*(rand(nUnit,1) < 0.15)); % some increase, some
decrease
    % Generate per-trial firing rates (truncated at non-negative)
    pre_rate = max(0, mu_pre_true + randn(nUnit, nTrial));
    dur_rate = max(0, mu_dur_true + 1.2*randn(nUnit, nTrial));
else
    [nUnit, nTrial] = size(pre_rate);
    assert(all(size(dur_rate)==[nUnit, nTrial]), 'pre_rate and dur_rate sizes do not
match. ');
end

```

```

[nUnit, nTrial] = size(pre_rate);
fprintf('Data dimensions: %d units x %d trials\n', nUnit, nTrial);

% ===== Main loop: auto test per neuron =====
pvals = nan(nUnit,1);
test_used = strings(nUnit,1);
dir_effect = zeros(nUnit,1); % -1 decrease, 0 no change, +1 increase
effect_meanDiff = nan(nUnit,1);
effect_RR = nan(nUnit,1);
mu_pre = nan(nUnit,1);
mu_dur = nan(nUnit,1);

for i = 1:nUnit
    x0 = pre_rate(i,:); % pre
    x1 = dur_rate(i,:); % dur

    mu_pre(i) = mean(x0, 'omitnan');
    mu_dur(i) = mean(x1, 'omitnan');
    effect_meanDiff(i) = mu_dur(i) - mu_pre(i);
    effect_RR(i) = (mu_dur(i) + eps) / (mu_pre(i) + eps);

% Normality
norm0 = local_test_normality(x0, use_jbtest);
norm1 = local_test_normality(x1, use_jbtest);

if paired_data
    dx = x1 - x0;
    dx = dx(~isnan(dx));
    if numel(dx) < 5
        pvals(i) = 1; test_used(i) = "insufficient"; dir_effect(i) = 0; continue;
    end
    % Paired scenario: test normality of differences
    norm_dx = local_test_normality(dx, use_jbtest);
    if norm_dx
        % Paired t-test (two-sided)
        try
            [~, p] = ttest(x1, x0, 'Tail','both');
            pvals(i) = p; test_used(i) = "paired_t";
        catch
            pvals(i) = 1; test_used(i) = "paired_t_fail";
        end
    else
        % Paired nonparametric: signrank (two-sided)
        try
            pvals(i) = signrank(x1, x0, 'tail','both');
            test_used(i) = "signrank";
        catch
            pvals(i) = 1; test_used(i) = "signrank_fail";
        end
    end
else
    % Unpaired scenario: test normality and equal variance
    if norm0 && norm1
        eqv = local_test_equal_variance(x1, x0, equalVarTest);
        try
            if eqv
                [~, p] = ttest2(x1, x0, 'Vartype','equal', 'Tail','both');
                test_used(i) = "ttest2_equalVar";
            else
                [~, p] = ttest2(x1, x0, 'Vartype','unequal', 'Tail','both'); % Welch
                test_used(i) = "ttest2_unequalVar";
            end
        catch
            pvals(i) = 1; test_used(i) = "ttest2_fail";
        end
    else
        pvals(i) = 1; test_used(i) = "unpaired_fail";
    end
end
end

```

```

        end
        pvals(i) = p;
    catch
        % Fallback nonparametric
        try
            pvals(i) = ranksum(x1, x0, 'tail','both');
            test_used(i) = "ranksum_fallback";
        catch
            pvals(i) = 1; test_used(i) = "ranksum_fail";
        end
    end
end
else
    try
        pvals(i) = ranksum(x1, x0, 'tail','both');
        test_used(i) = "ranksum";
    catch
        pvals(i) = 1; test_used(i) = "ranksum_fail";
    end
end
end

% Direction decision (based on raw mean difference)
if effect_meanDiff(i) > 0
    dir_effect(i) = 1;      % increase
elseif effect_meanDiff(i) < 0
    dir_effect(i) = -1;    % decrease
else
    dir_effect(i) = 0;     % no change
end
end

% FDR correction -> final significance and direction
qvals = local_bh_fdr(pvals);
signif = qvals < FDR_alpha;

% Final classification: based on significance and direction
% 1=significant increase, -1=significant decrease, 0=no change
final_class = zeros(nUnit,1);
final_class(signif & dir_effect>0) = 1;
final_class(signif & dir_effect<0) = -1;
final_class(~signif | dir_effect==0) = 0;

% ===== Output and summary =====
n_up   = sum(final_class==1);
n_down = sum(final_class==-1);
n_ns   = sum(final_class==0);

% Build result table
Direction = strings(nUnit,1);
Direction(final_class==1) = "Up";
Direction(final_class==-1) = "Down";
Direction(final_class==0) = "NoChange";

T = table((1:nUnit)', test_used, pvals, qvals, mu_pre, mu_dur, ...
        effect_meanDiff, effect_RR, Direction, ...
        'VariableNames',
        {'Unit', 'TestUsed', 'p', 'q', 'mu_pre', 'mu_dur', 'meanDiff', 'RR', 'Direction'});
% T = sortrows(T, 'q');
disp(T(1:min(15,height(T)), :));

```

```

%%
% Pre-check
assert(numel(Data) == height(T), 'Number of elements in Data must equal number of rows in T.');
```

% 1) Normalize table variable names to valid struct field names

```

origNames = T.Properties.VariableNames;
validNames = matlab.lang.makeValidName(origNames, 'ReplacementStyle','delete');
```

% If duplicates appear after normalization, append incremental suffixes

```

[~, ia] = unique(validNames, 'stable');
if numel(ia) < numel(validNames)
    for k = 1:numel(validNames)
        dupCount = sum(strcmp(validNames{k}, validNames(1:k)));
        if dupCount > 1
            validNames{k} = sprintf('%s_%d', validNames{k}, dupCount);
        end
    end
end
```

% 2) Write table columns into top-level fields of Data

```

for v = 1:numel(validNames)
    vn = validNames{v}; % target field
    col = T.(origNames{v}); % original column

    % Type normalization: convert string/categorical for easier saving
    if isstring(col)
        col = cellstr(col); % string -> cellstr
    elseif iscategorical(col)
        col = cellstr(col); % categorical -> cellstr (display labels)
    end

    % Assign per element to Data(i).vn
    if iscell(col)
        % For cell columns (e.g., cellstr or per-row container/vector)
        for i = 1:numel(Data)
            Data(i).(vn) = col{i}; % store cell content directly
        end
    else
        % For numeric/logical/time scalar columns
        for i = 1:numel(Data)
            Data(i).(vn) = col(i);
        end
    end
end
```

%%

% Pre-check

```

n = numel(Data);
assert(ismatrix(pre_count) && size(pre_count,1) == n, 'First dim of pre_count should be numel(Data)');
assert(ismatrix(dur_count) && size(dur_count,1) == n, 'First dim of dur_count should be numel(Data)');
assert(ismatrix(post_count) && size(post_count,1) == n, 'First dim of post_count should be numel(Data)');
assert(ismatrix(pre_rate) && size(pre_rate,1) == n, 'First dim of pre_rate should be numel(Data)');
assert(ismatrix(dur_rate) && size(dur_rate,1) == n, 'First dim of dur_rate should be numel(Data)');
```

```

assert(ismatrix(post_rate) && size(post_rate,1) == n, 'First dim of post_rate should be
numel(Data)');
assert(ismatrix(psth_mean) && size(psth_mean,1) == n, 'First dim of psth_mean should be
numel(Data)');
assert(ndims(psth_tensor) == 3 && size(psth_tensor,1) == n, 'First dim of psth_tensor
should be numel(Data)');

% Optional: list field names to auto-handle 2D matrices (assign row-wise)
mat2d_names =
{'pre_count', 'dur_count', 'post_count', 'pre_rate', 'dur_rate', 'post_rate', 'psth_mean'};

for i = 1:n
    % 2D matrices: take the i-th row and save in Data(i).field
    for k = 1:numel(mat2d_names)
        name = mat2d_names{k};
        Data(i).(name) = eval([name '(i,:)']); % 1xM row vector
        % If you prefer column vector: Data(i).(name) = eval([name '(i,:).''']);
    end

    % 3D tensor: take slice i (first dim) to get 150x12000 matrix
    Data(i).psth_tensor = squeeze(psth_tensor(i,:,:)); % 150x12000
    % Note: squeeze won't change 150x12000 unless a dimension is 1.
end

%%
% Preview + interactive deletion + re-preview

% ----- First preview -----
N = numel(Data);

% Compute a reasonable subplot grid (approx square)
nRow = floor(sqrt(N));
nCol = ceil(N / nRow);

figure('Color','w');
tiledlayout(nRow, nCol, 'Padding','compact','TileSpacing','compact');

for n = 1:N
    nexttile;

    % Take waveform and convert to column vector
    wf = Data(n).meanWaveform_good;
    wf = wf(:);

    % Color by group
    if isfield(Data, 'Direction')
        dir = Data(n).Direction;
    else
        dir = ''; % default black if field missing
    end

    % Normalize to string for comparison
    dirStr = string(dir);
    switch dirStr
        case "Up"
            c = [0.85 0.1 0.1]; % red
        case "Down"
            c = [0.1 0.3 0.9]; % blue
        otherwise
            c = [0 0 0]; % black
    end
end

```

```

plot(wf, 'Color', c, 'LineWidth', 1.2);
hold on;

% Optional: zero line
yline(0, ':', 'Color', [0.7 0.7 0.7]);

% Axis styling and title
axis tight;
box off;
set(gca, 'TickDir', 'out', 'FontSize', 8);

% Title shows unit index and group (if Unit field exists)
if isfield(Data, 'Unit')
    title(sprintf('#%d Unit %s (%s)', n, num2str(Data(n).Unit), char(dirStr)),
'FontSize', 9);
else
    title(sprintf('#%d (%s)', n, char(dirStr)), 'FontSize', 9);
end
end

drawnow;

% ----- Interactive input of indices to delete -----
raw = input(sprintf('\nEnter indices to delete (based on preview #n):\nExamples: 5 7 12
or 3:8 or 1 4 10:15 20,22 Enter=none\n> '), 's');

% If just Enter, no deletion and exit
if isempty(strtrim(raw))
    fprintf('No index entered, Data unchanged.\n');
    return;
end

% Parse input string to index array
ids = parse_indices(raw);

% Validate and de-duplicate
idx_del = unique(round(ids));
idx_del = idx_del(idx_del >= 1 & idx_del <= N);

if isempty(idx_del)
    fprintf('No valid indices after parsing, Data unchanged.\n');
    return;
end

% Confirm operation
fprintf('Indices to delete: %s\n', mat2str(idx_del));
ok = input('Confirm deletion? (y/N): ', 's');
if isempty(ok) || ~ismember(lower(ok), {'y', 'yes'})
    fprintf('Deletion canceled, Data unchanged.\n');
    return;
end

% ----- Delete and rebuild Data -----
idx_keep = setdiff(1:N, idx_del, 'stable');
Data = Data(idx_keep);

fprintf('Total %d, deleted %d, kept %d.\n', N, numel(idx_del), numel(idx_keep));

% ----- Second preview (updated Data) -----
N2 = numel(Data);

```

```

if N2 == 0
    warning('All data deleted, nothing to preview.');
```

return;

```
end

nRow = floor(sqrt(N2));
nCol = ceil(N2 / nRow);

figure('Color','w');
tiledlayout(nRow, nCol, 'Padding','compact','TileSpacing','compact');
```

for n = 1:N2

```
    nexttile;

    wf = Data(n).meanWaveform_good;
    wf = wf(:);

    if isfield(Data, 'Direction')
        dir = Data(n).Direction;
    else
        dir = '';
    end
    dirStr = string(dir);
    switch dirStr
        case "Up"
            c = [0.85 0.1 0.1];
        case "Down"
            c = [0.1 0.3 0.9];
        otherwise
            c = [0 0 0];
    end

    plot(wf, 'Color', c, 'LineWidth', 1.2); hold on;
    yline(0, ':', 'Color', [0.7 0.7 0.7]);
    axis tight; box off; set(gca,'TickDir','out','FontSize',8);

    if isfield(Data, 'Unit')
        title(sprintf('#%d Unit %s (%s)', n, num2str(Data(n).Unit), char(dirStr)),
'FontSize',9);
    else
        title(sprintf('#%d (%s)', n, char(dirStr)), 'FontSize',9);
    end
end
end
%% function

function stim_info = batch_get_stim_info(rootDir, recursive)

% ----- Input args and defaults -----
if nargin < 1 || isempty(rootDir)
    rootDir = 'G:\A-B-D';
end
if nargin < 2 || isempty(recursive)
    recursive = true;
end
if ~isfolder(rootDir)
    error('rootDir does not exist: %s', rootDir);
end

% ----- Detection parameters (tunable) -----
thr_on = 3000;
thr_off = 2900;
```

```

minWidth_samp    = 2;
maxWidth_samp    = 20;
refractory_samp  = 40;
minHold_samp     = 4;
needLowCount     = 2;
useSubSample     = true;

% Scoring reference (only for choosing best channel, does not affect final output fields)
targetISI_ms     = 50;
targetWidth_ms   = [3 7];

% Pack parameters
params = struct('thr_on',thr_on,'thr_off',thr_off,'minWidth_samp',minWidth_samp, ...
    'maxWidth_samp',maxWidth_samp,'refractory_samp',refractory_samp, ...
    'minHold_samp',minHold_samp,'needLowCount',needLowCount, ...
    'useSubSample',useSubSample);

% ----- Collect files -----
files = listNexFiles(rootDir, recursive);
stim_info = struct('filename',{},'channelName',{},'t_on',{},'t_off',{},'delta_t',{});
if isempty(files)
    warning('No .nex files found in %s.', rootDir);
    return;
end

% ----- Environment check -----
if exist('readNexFile','file') ~= 2
    error('Function readNexFile not found. Please add it to MATLAB path.');
```

```

end

% ----- Main loop -----
for i = 1:numel(files)
    fpath = files{i};
    try
        nexData = readNexFile(fpath);
        if ~isstruct(nexData) || ~isfield(nexData,'contvars')
            error('File contains no contvars.');
```

```

        end

        [det, ok] = selectBestStimChannel(nexData, params, targetISI_ms, targetWidth_ms);
        if ~ok
            stim_info(end+1) = struct('filename', fpath, 'channelName', '', ...
                't_on', [], 't_off', [], 'delta_t', []); %#ok<AGROW>
        else
            stim_info(end+1) = struct('filename', fpath, 'channelName', string(det.name),
                ...
                't_on', det.t_on(:), 't_off', det.t_off(:), 'delta_t', det.delta_t(:));
        %#ok<AGROW>
    end

    fprintf('%d/%d] %s -> %s, n=%d\n', i, numel(files), fpath, ...
        ternary(ok,string(det.name),"N/A"), numel(det.t_on));

    catch ME
        stim_info(end+1) = struct('filename', fpath, 'channelName', '', ...
            't_on', [], 't_off', [], 'delta_t', []); %#ok<AGROW>
        fprintf(2, '%d/%d] Failed: %s | %s\n', i, numel(files), fpath, ME.message);
    end
end

end % main

```

```

function [groupNeuron,groupLFP] = extractNeuLFP(filename, dataKey, paramsExtr)

idx = 1; % idx: index for wanted neurons

groupNeu = [];
groupLFP = [];
% Save spike/events/waveform or not
addSpike = sum(strcmp(dataKey, 'spike'));
addEvents = sum(strcmp(dataKey, 'events'));
addWaveform = sum(strcmp(dataKey, 'waveform'));
addAI = sum(strcmp(dataKey, 'AI'));
filPerChl = paramsExtr.filPerChl;
exEvt = paramsExtr.exEvent;
evtFrom = paramsExtr.eventsFrom;
getEvt = paramsExtr.getEvents;
bestNlfp = paramsExtr.bestNlfp;

chnl = paramsExtr.chnl;
regionToLoad = paramsExtr.regionToLoad;
regionPos = cellfun(@(x) any(strcmp(x,regionToLoad)),chnl(:,1));

for i = 1:length(filename) % i: index for nex files

    tempPath = filename(i).folder;
    tempLabel = strsplit(tempPath, '/');
    % For each loop, reading only one nexfile to tempData
    if strcmp(filename(i).name(end),'5')
        curNex = readNex5File([tempPath, '/', filename(i).name]);
    else
        curNex = readNexFile([tempPath, '/', filename(i).name]);
    end
    % find the serial number of the animal and the date of experiment
    tempDate = filename(i).name(1:8);
    %tempAnimal = regexpi(filename(i).name,'#v-\d\d\d\d','match');
    % tempAnimal = tempAnimal{1}(2:5);

    matchResult = regexpi(filename(i).name, '#v\d{4}-\d', 'match');% Using regex to find
    pattern starting with # or v, % followed by 4 digits, a
    hyphen, then a digit. regexpi is case-insensitive.
    if ~isempty(matchResult)
        % Ensure the match is a string, then take substring from 2nd to 7th char
        tempAnimal = matchResult{1}(2:min(7, end)); % Use min to avoid indexing beyond string
    else
        tempAnimal = ''; % Default if no match
    end

    % extract LFPs
    % get continuous variables for LFPs into 'curLFP'
    getLFP = any(strcmpi(dataKey, 'LFP'));
    if getLFP
        try
            curContvars = [curNex.contvars{:,1}];
        catch
            disp(['lack LFP ',filename(i).name]);
            getLFP = false;
        end
    end
end

```

```

if getLFP
    LFPpos = cellfun(@(x) contains(x, 'FP'), {curContvars.name});
    curLFP = curContvars(LFPpos);
    % find regions where LFP channels belong
    curLFPchnl = cellfun(@(x) str2double(x(5:6)), {curLFP.name});
    curRegPos = cellfun(@(x) ismember(curLFPchnl, x), chnl(:, 2), 'UniformOutput', false);
    curRegPos2 = regionPos & cell2mat(curRegPos);
    [channelPos, idxReg] = max(curRegPos2); % channelPos: logical array indicating
whether
    curLFPreg = chnl(idxReg, 1);
    curLFPreg = curLFPreg(channelPos);
    curLFP = [curLFP(channelPos).data];
    % save average LFP waveforms for bestNlfp LFPs in each region
    tempReg = unique(curLFPreg);
    if ~isempty(tempReg)
        for kr = 1:length(tempReg) % loop through brain regions for LFP
            rgLFP = curLFP(:, strcmp(tempReg(kr), curLFPreg));
            bestLfpIdx = findBestLFP(rgLFP(1000:150:end, :), bestNlfp);
            tempLFP(kr).waveform = mean(rgLFP(:, bestLfpIdx), 2);
            tempLFP(kr).region = tempReg{kr};
        end
        groupLFP(i).animal = tempAnimal;
        groupLFP(i).date = tempDate;
        groupLFP(i).record = erase(filename(i).name(1:end-4), '.');
        groupLFP(i).LFPs = tempLFP;
    end
end

% extract waveform and timestamp information of neurons and AI
try
    curWave = [curNex.waves{:}, 1];
catch
    disp(['error finding waves:', filename(i).name]);
    continue
end
curName = {curWave.name};
% AI is the channel for opto stimulation. It may affect all neurons.
AIpos = cellfun(@(x) contains(x, 'AI') & contains(x, 'wf'), curName);
curAI = curWave(AIpos);
templatePos = find(cellfun(@(x) contains(x, 'template') & contains(x, 'SPK'), curName));
wfPos = find(cellfun(@(x) contains(x, 'wf') & contains(x, 'SPK'), curName));
if isempty(wfPos)
    continue
end
neuronID = cellfun(@(x) x(end-5:end-3), curName(wfPos), 'UniformOutput', false);
curNeuChnl = cellfun(@(x) str2double(x(1:2)), neuronID);

curRegPos = cellfun(@(x) ismember(curNeuChnl, x), chnl(:, 2), 'UniformOutput', false);
curRegPos2 = regionPos & cell2mat(curRegPos);
[channelPos, idxReg] = max(curRegPos2);
curNeuReg = chnl(idxReg, 1);
wfPos = wfPos(channelPos);
if any(templatePos)
    templatePos = templatePos(channelPos);
end

% put data of the current file into tempTrialData
idxpost = idx + length(wfPos) - 1;
if idxpost >= idx
    [groupNeu(idx:idxpost).neuronID] = neuronID{channelPos};
    curNeuChnl = num2cell(curNeuChnl);

```

```

[groupNeu(idx:idxpost).channel] = curNeuChnl{channelPos};
[groupNeu(idx:idxpost).region] = curNeuReg{channelPos};
[groupNeu(idx:idxpost).date] = deal(tempDate);
[groupNeu(idx:idxpost).animal] = deal(tempAnimal);
tempName = cellfun(@(x) erase([filename(i).name(1:end-4) '_'
x], '.'), neuronID(channelPos), 'UniformOutput', false);
[groupNeu(idx:idxpost).name] = tempName{:};
[groupNeu(idx:idxpost).record] = deal(erase(filename(i).name(1:end-4), '.'));
[groupNeu(idx:idxpost).label] = deal(tempLabel{end});
if addWaveform
%       if any(templatePos) % if template was saved into nex files after neuron
sorting
%           templates = {curWave(templatePos).waveforms}; % use the existing
templates
%       else
%       In some files, template channels are corrupted, so we don't use them any more.
%           templates = {curWave(wfPos).waveforms}; % else, use the mean of spike
waveforms as templates
            [groupNeu(idx:idxpost).Allwaveform] = templates{:};
            templates = cellfun(@(x) mean(x,2), templates, 'UniformOutput', false);
%       end
%       % select the template from the filaments that got signals of largest
%       % amplitude as the final template
if length(templates{1})>56
    pointPerFil = length(templates{1})/filPerChl;
else
    pointPerFil = length(templates{1});
    disp(['Only one channel in ', groupNeu(idx).record]);
end
    bestFilaments = cellfun(@(x) ceil(find(x==min(x))/
pointPerFil), templates, 'UniformOutput', false);
    try
        bestTemplates = cellfun(@(x,y) x(1+
(y-1)*pointPerFil:y*pointPerFil), templates, bestFilaments, 'UniformOutput', false);
    catch
        bestTemplates = [];
        display(['error finding templates:', filename(i).name]);
    end
    [groupNeu(idx:idxpost).waveform] = bestTemplates{:};
end
if addSpike
    [groupNeu(idx:idxpost).spike] = curWave(wfPos).timestamps;
end
if addAI
    [groupNeu(idx:idxpost).AI] = deal({curAI.timestamps});
end
if addEvents
    if any(strcmp(evtFrom, 'nex'))
        cEventsNex = curNex.events;
        for kevt = 1:length(cEventsNex)
            cEventsNex{kevt}.condition = [];
            if isfield(cEventsNex{kevt}, 'varNex5Version')
                cEventsNex{kevt} = rmfield(cEventsNex{kevt}, 'varNex5Version');
            end
            if isfield(cEventsNex{kevt}, 'varVersion')
                cEventsNex{kevt} = rmfield(cEventsNex{kevt}, 'varVersion');
            end
        end
    else
        cEventsNex = cell(0,0);
    end
end

```

```

        if any(strcmp(evtFrom, 'exl'))
            evtTemp = exEvt(strcmp({exEvt.date}, tempDate) &
                strcmp({exEvt.animal}, tempAnimal));
            nCond = length(evtTemp);
            nEvt = length(getEvt);
            cEventsExl = cell(nEvt*nCond, 1);
            for kcond = 1:nCond
                for kevt = 1:nEvt
                    idxEvt = (kcond-1)*nEvt + kevt;
                    cEventsExl{idxEvt}.name = getEvt{kevt};
                    cEventsExl{idxEvt}.timestamps = evtTemp(kcond).(getEvt{kevt});
                    cEventsExl{idxEvt}.condition = evtTemp(kcond).condition;
                end
            end
        else
            cEventsExl = cell(0, 0);
        end
        cEvents = [cEventsNex; cEventsExl];
        dim = size(cEvents);
        cEvents = reshape(cEvents, max(dim), min(dim));
        if any(AIpos)
            tempLightPos = cellfun(@(x) strcmpi(x.name, 'light'), cEvents);
            cEvents(tempLightPos) = [];
            tempLightPos = length(cEvents)+1;
            cEvents{tempLightPos} = struct('name', 'light', 'timestamps', [], 'condition',
                []);

            for kAI = 1:length(curAI)
                diffAI = reshape(diff(curAI(kAI).timestamps), 1, []);
                diffAIpos = [0, find(diffAI>1), length(diffAI)+1];
                for kAITrial = 1:length(diffAIpos)-1
                    cEvents{tempLightPos}.timestamps(end+1, 1) =
                        curAI(kAI).timestamps(diffAIpos(kAITrial)+1); %TrialData.events.timestamps(:,1): start time
                    cEvents{tempLightPos}.timestamps(end, 2) =
                        curAI(kAI).timestamps(diffAIpos(kAITrial+1)); %TrialData.events.timestamps(:,2): stop time
                    cEvents{tempLightPos}.timestamps(end, 3)
                    = diff(cEvents{tempLightPos}.timestamps(end, 1:2))/(diffAIpos(kAITrial+1)-
                        diffAIpos(kAITrial)-1); %TrialData.events.timestamps(:,3): period (1/f) of the light
                end
            end
        end
        [groupNeu(idx:idxpost).events] = deal(cell2mat(cEvents));
    end
    idx = idxpost+1;
end

groupNeuron.TrialData = groupNeu;
end

function [templates, eventInfo, splitIdx] = processStereotrodeUnit(W, fs, params)

if nargin < 2 || isempty(fs), fs = 40000; end
if nargin < 3, params = struct(); end
p = fillParams(params);

% Basic dimensions and splitting wires
[S, m] = size(W);
assert(mod(S, p.filPerChl)==0, 'Row length must be a multiple of filPerChl. ');
M = S / p.filPerChl;
ch1 = W(1:M, :);

```

```

ch2 = W(M+1:end, :);

% Unify polarity: assume negative trough is main. Flip if the mean minima are positive.
if mean(min(ch1)) > 0, ch1 = -ch1; end
if mean(min(ch2)) > 0, ch2 = -ch2; end

% Per-event features
[A1, p1] = getPeakAndPos(ch1, p.useParabFit);
[A2, p2] = getPeakAndPos(ch2, p.useParabFit);

% Main-wire selection (based on amplitude) and reference peak position
useCh1 = A1 >= A2;
mainCh = 2*ones(1,m); mainCh(useCh1) = 1;
pref = p2; pref(useCh1) = p1(useCh1);

% Quality and difference metrics
dt = abs(p1 - p2) / fs;
ratio = A1 ./ max(A2, eps);
logR = log(ratio);
logRz = robustZ(logR);

% Inter-wire correlation (window around main peak)
win = localWin(M, pref, fs);
xc12 = zeros(1,m);
for i = 1:m
    seg1 = ch1(win(i,1):win(i,2), i);
    seg2 = ch2(win(i,1):win(i,2), i);
    xc12(i) = corrN(seg1, seg2);
end

% Edge and suspect flags
isEdge = (pref <= p.edgeSafe) | (pref >= M - p.edgeSafe);
isSuspect = (dt > p.dtThr) | (xc12 < p.xcThr) | (abs(logRz) > p.ratioZThr) | isEdge;

% Stage 1: build main-wire template and compute correlation (no split)
% Alignment: roughly align by each main-wire's peak position, then take median as
template (more robust)
[tplMain, xc_main, mainWireIdx] = buildMainWireTemplate(ch1, ch2, mainCh);

% Estimate dual-channel template using non-suspect events (consistent with original
logic)
keep = ~isSuspect;
if ~any(keep)
    warning('All events marked suspect; falling back to all for template.');
```

```

    keep = true(1,m);
end
tpl1 = mean(ch1(:, keep), 2);
tpl2 = mean(ch2(:, keep), 2);

templates.best = [tpl1(:)'; tpl2(:)'];
templates.perCh = {tpl1(:), tpl2(:)};
templates.main = struct('wire', mainWireIdx, 'tpl', tplMain(:), 'xc_main', xc_main);

% Stage 2: attempt split (only when necessary conditions are met) with strong validation
% 2.1 candidate split
[assignAB_cand, distA, distB] = assignByTemplates(ch1, ch2, tpl1, tpl2);
needSplitCand = shouldSplit(distA, distB, isSuspect);

% 2.2 Necessary conditions: sample size and potential group size
minSize = max(p.minGroupSize, ceil(p.minGroupFrac * m));
meetsSize = m >= p.minN;
```

% 2.3 If candidate and size conditions are satisfied, iteratively refine templates and candidate assignments

```
templates.split = {};  
assignAB = repmat('A', 1, m);  
if needSplitCand && meetsSize  
    for iter = 1:2  
        Aidx = assignAB_cand == 'A';  
        Bidx = assignAB_cand == 'B';  
        if any(Aidx)  
            tpl1A = mean(ch1(:, Aidx), 2);  
            tpl2A = mean(ch2(:, Aidx), 2);  
        else  
            tpl1A = tpl1; tpl2A = tpl2;  
        end  
        if any(Bidx)  
            tpl1B = mean(ch1(:, Bidx), 2);  
            tpl2B = mean(ch2(:, Bidx), 2);  
        else  
            tpl1B = tpl1; tpl2B = tpl2;  
        end  
        [assignAB_cand, distA, distB] = assignByTemplates(ch1, ch2, tpl1A, tpl2A,  
tpl1B, tpl2B);  
    end
```

% 2.4 Strong validation

```
Aidx = find(assignAB_cand=='A');  
Bidx = find(assignAB_cand=='B');  
accept = validateSplit(ch1, ch2, Aidx, Bidx, p);
```

% 2.5 Minimum group size requirement

```
if numel(Aidx) < minSize || numel(Bidx) < minSize  
    accept = false;  
end  
  
if accept  
    assignAB = assignAB_cand;  
    templates.split = { [mean(ch1(:,Aidx),2)'; mean(ch2(:,Aidx),2)'], ...  
                        [mean(ch1(:,Bidx),2)'; mean(ch2(:,Bidx),2)'] };  
    if p.verbose  
        fprintf('[split] ACCEPT: m=%d | A=%d, B=%d\n', m, numel(Aidx), numel(Bidx));  
    end  
else  
    if p.verbose  
        fprintf('[split] REJECT: m=%d | A=%d, B=%d\n', m, numel(Aidx), numel(Bidx));  
    end  
end  
else  
    if p.verbose  
        fprintf('[split] SKIP: needSplit=%d, meetsSize=%d, m=%d\n', needSplitCand,  
meetsSize, m);  
    end  
end
```

% Output event info

```
eventInfo = struct( ...  
    'A1', num2cell(A1), 'A2', num2cell(A2), ...  
    'p1', num2cell(p1), 'p2', num2cell(p2), ...  
    'mainCh', num2cell(mainCh), 'pref', num2cell(pref), ...  
    'dt', num2cell(dt), 'ratio', num2cell(ratio), ...  
    'logRatioZ', num2cell(logRz), 'xc', num2cell(xc12), ...
```

```

        'isEdge', num2cell(isEdge), 'isSuspect', num2cell(isSuspect), ...
        'xc_main', num2cell(xc_main) ...
    );

    if ~isempty(templates.split)
        assign = assignAB;
    else
        assign = repmat('A', 1, m);
    end
    for i = 1:m
        eventInfo(i).assign = assign(i);
    end

    splitIdx.A = find(assign=='A');
    splitIdx.B = find(assign=='B');
end

function p = fillParams(p)
    def.filPerChl = 2;
    def.dtThr     = 0.0002; % 0.2 ms
    def.xcThr     = 0.5;
    def.ratioZThr = 3;
    def.edgeSafe  = 3;      % samples
    def.minPeakSep= 8;      % samples
    def.useParabFit = true;
    % Conservative split defaults
    def.minN = 60;
    def.minGroupSize = 20;
    def.minGroupFrac = 0.05;
    def.xc_reject = 0.85;
    def.energyFrac_reject = 0.10;
    def.requireWithinImprove = 0.05;
    def.verbose = false;

    f = fieldnames(def);
    for k = 1:numel(f)
        if ~isfield(p, f{k}) || isempty(p.(f{k}))
            p.(f{k}) = def.(f{k});
        end
    end
end

function [A, pos] = getPeakAndPos(X, useParab)
    [mins, posI] = min(X, [], 1);
    A = -mins; % absolute of negative trough
    pos = posI;
    if useParab
        [M, m] = size(X);
        pos = double(posI);
        for i = 1:m
            p0 = posI(i);
            if p0>1 && p0<M
                y1 = X(p0-1,i); y2 = X(p0,i); y3 = X(p0+1,i);
                denom = (y1 - 2*y2 + y3);
                if abs(denom) > eps
                    delta = 0.5*(y1 - y3)/denom; % -1..1
                    pos(i) = p0 + delta;
                end
            end
        end
    end
end

```

```

end

function z = robustZ(x)
    mu = median(x);
    s = 1.4826*median(abs(x - mu)) + eps;
    z = (x - mu) / s;
end

function r = corrN(a, b)
    a = a(:); b = b(:);
    a = a - mean(a); b = b - mean(b);
    na = norm(a); nb = norm(b);
    if na==0 || nb==0
        r = 0;
    else
        r = (a'*b)/(na*nb);
    end
end

function win = localWin(M, pref, fs)
% Build a local window for each event for cross-correlation, about 0.6 ms window
    half = round(0.3e-3 * fs); % 0.3 ms
    half = max(6, half);
    n = numel(pref);
    win = zeros(n,2);
    for i = 1:n
        p = round(min(max(pref(i),1),M));
        s = max(1, p - half);
        e = min(M, p + half);
        win(i,:) = [s, e];
    end
end

function [assign, distA, distB] = assignByTemplates(ch1, ch2, tpl1A, tpl2A, tpl1B,
tpl2B)
    if nargin < 5
        tpl1B = tpl1A; tpl2B = tpl2A;
    end
    [~, m] = size(ch1);
    distA = zeros(1,m);
    distB = zeros(1,m);
    T1A = tpl1A(:); T2A = tpl2A(:);
    T1B = tpl1B(:); T2B = tpl2B(:);
    for i = 1:m
        x1 = ch1(:,i); x2 = ch2(:,i);
        a1A = projScale(x1, T1A); a2A = projScale(x2, T2A);
        a1B = projScale(x1, T1B); a2B = projScale(x2, T2B);
        distA(i) = norm(x1 - a1A*T1A)^2 + norm(x2 - a2A*T2A)^2;
        distB(i) = norm(x1 - a1B*T1B)^2 + norm(x2 - a2B*T2B)^2;
    end
    assign = repmat('A', 1, m);
    assign(distB < distA) = 'B';
end

function a = projScale(x, t)
    denom = (t'*t);
    if denom < eps
        a = 0;
    else
        a = (t'*x)/denom;
    end
end

```

```

end

function need = shouldSplit(distA, distB, isSuspect)
    dDiff = distA - distB;
    med = median(dDiff);
    hi = dDiff >= med; lo = ~hi;
    if any(hi) && any(lo)
        sep = abs(median(dDiff(hi)) - median(dDiff(lo)));
        spread = 1.4826*median(abs(dDiff - med)) + eps;
        sepZ = sep / spread;
    else
        sepZ = 0;
    end
    susFrac = mean(isSuspect);
    need = (sepZ > 2.5 && mean(hi) > 0.2 && mean(lo) > 0.2) || (susFrac > 0.25);
end

function [tplMain, xc_main, mainWireIdx] = buildMainWireTemplate(ch1, ch2, mainCh)
% Build a robust main-wire template (median) and compute similarity to the main template
[M, m] = size(ch1);
% For each event, take main-wire waveform from two wires
X = zeros(M, m);
for i = 1:m
    if mainCh(i) == 1
        X(:,i) = ch1(:,i);
    else
        X(:,i) = ch2(:,i);
    end
end
% No sub-sample fine alignment; roughly aligned by peak (p1/p2 used for pref; not
reused here)
tplMain = median(X, 2); % more robust
% Correlation with main template
xc_main = zeros(1, m);
for i = 1:m
    xc_main(i) = corrN(X(:,i), tplMain);
end
% Which wire has larger mean energy overall
e1 = mean(sum(ch1.^2,1));
e2 = mean(sum(ch2.^2,1));
mainWireIdx = (e1 >= e2) + 1; % e1>=e2 -> 1 intended; fix next
if e1 >= e2
    mainWireIdx = 1;
else
    mainWireIdx = 2;
end
end

function accept = validateSplit(ch1, ch2, Aidx, Bidx, p)
% Strong validation for split: template correlation, energy difference, within-class
similarity improvement, size, etc.
if isempty(Aidx) || isempty(Bidx)
    accept = false; return;
end
% A/B templates
t1A = mean(ch1(:,Aidx),2); t2A = mean(ch2(:,Aidx),2);
t1B = mean(ch1(:,Bidx),2); t2B = mean(ch2(:,Bidx),2);

% 1) Template cross-correlation (per wire; take max)
xcA1B1 = corrN(t1A, t1B);
xcA2B2 = corrN(t2A, t2B);

```

```

xcAB = max(xcA1B1, xcA2B2);

% 2) Energy difference fraction
EA = sum(t1A.^2) + sum(t2A.^2);
EB = sum(t1B.^2) + sum(t2B.^2);
dEfrac = abs(EA - EB) / max(EA, EB);

% 3) Within-class similarity improvement
% Overall templates
t1All = mean([ch1(:,Aidx), ch1(:,Bidx)], 2);
t2All = mean([ch2(:,Aidx), ch2(:,Bidx)], 2);

xc_in_A = meanColCorr(ch1(:,Aidx), t1A) + meanColCorr(ch2(:,Aidx), t2A);
xc_in_A = xc_in_A / 2;
xc_in_B = meanColCorr(ch1(:,Bidx), t1B) + meanColCorr(ch2(:,Bidx), t2B);
xc_in_B = xc_in_B / 2;
xc_in_all = meanColCorr([ch1(:,Aidx), ch1(:,Bidx)], t1All) + ...
            meanColCorr([ch2(:,Aidx), ch2(:,Bidx)], t2All);
xc_in_all = xc_in_all / 2;

deltaWithin = (xc_in_A + xc_in_B)/2 - xc_in_all;

% Criteria
accept = true;
if xcAB > p.xc_reject
    accept = false; % templates too similar
end
if dEfrac < p.energyFrac_reject
    accept = false; % energy difference too small
end
if deltaWithin < p.requireWithinImprove
    accept = false; % insufficient within-class improvement
end
end

function v = meanColCorr(X, t)
% Mean correlation of each column with template t
[~, m] = size(X);
v = 0;
for i = 1:m
    v = v + corrN(X(:,i), t);
end
v = v / max(1,m);
end

function [TD_A, TD_B] = reshapeGroupAfterSplit(TD, splitIdx, eventInfo, templates)

TD_A = TD;
TD_B = struct([]);

% Normalize indices to row vector
idxA = reshape(splitIdx.A, 1, []);
idxB = reshape(splitIdx.B, 1, []);

% Attach processing info
procMeta.eventInfo = eventInfo;
procMeta.templates = templates;
procMeta.split = ~isempty(idxB);
procMeta.nA = numel(idxA);
procMeta.nB = numel(idxB);

```

```

% Process group A: slice + generate 56xN waveform and mean
TD_A = sliceTrialDataByIdx(TD_A, idxA);
TD_A.ProcessInfo = procMeta;
TD_A.ProcessInfo.group = 'A';
[TD_A.waveform_good, TD_A.meanWaveform_good] = buildWaveform56AndMean(TD_A);

% If group B exists
if ~isempty(idxB)
    TD_B = TD; % copy
    TD_B = sliceTrialDataByIdx(TD_B, idxB);
    TD_B.ProcessInfo = procMeta;
    TD_B.ProcessInfo.group = 'B';

    [TD_B.waveform_good, TD_B.meanWaveform_good] = buildWaveform56AndMean(TD_B);

% Optional: rename to distinguish
if isfield(TD, 'Name')
    TD_A.Name = sprintf('%s_A', TD.Name);
    TD_B.Name = sprintf('%s_B', TD.Name);
elseif isfield(TD, 'UnitID')
    TD_A.UnitID = sprintf('%s_A', toStr(TD.UnitID));
    TD_B.UnitID = sprintf('%s_B', toStr(TD.UnitID));
end
end
end

function TD = sliceTrialDataByIdx(TD, idx)

% Special case: idx empty
if isempty(idx)
    if isfield(TD, 'Allwaveform') && ~isempty(TD.Allwaveform)
        TD.Allwaveform = TD.Allwaveform(:, []);
    end
    % Also clear possible derived event-aligned fields
    TD = clearEventAlignedAddons(TD);
    fprintf('[sliceTD] Empty index -> cleared Allwaveform and returned.\n');
    return;
end

% 1) Infer event count m
[m, wfOrient] = inferEventCountAndOrient(TD);

if isempty(m)
    % Unable to infer m; keep original but report
    fprintf('[sliceTD] Unable to infer event count m; no slicing performed.\n');
    return;
end

% Stats
fn = fieldnames(TD);
total = numel(fn);
sliced = 0;
skipped = 0;
slicedFields = {};

% 2) First handle Allwaveform (if present)
if isfield(TD, 'Allwaveform') && ~isempty(TD.Allwaveform) && isnumeric(TD.Allwaveform)
    val = TD.Allwaveform;
    sz = size(val);
    try
        if strcmp(wfOrient, 'Sxm') && sz(2)==m

```

```

        TD.Allwaveform = val(:, idx);
        sliced = sliced + 1; slicedFields{end+1} = 'Allwaveform';
elseif strcmp(wfOrient, 'mXS') && sz(1)==m
    TD.Allwaveform = val(idx, :);
    sliced = sliced + 1; slicedFields{end+1} = 'Allwaveform';
elseif sz(2)==m
    TD.Allwaveform = val(:, idx);
    sliced = sliced + 1; slicedFields{end+1} = 'Allwaveform';
elseif sz(1)==m
    TD.Allwaveform = val(idx, :);
    sliced = sliced + 1; slicedFields{end+1} = 'Allwaveform';
else
    skipped = skipped + 1;
end
catch
    skipped = skipped + 1;
end
end

```

% 3) Iterate other fields; only slice those aligned with m

```

fn = fieldnames(TD); % refresh
for i = 1:numel(fn)
    f = fn{i};
    if strcmp(f, 'Allwaveform'), continue; end
    val = TD.(f);
    if isempty(val), continue; end

    didSlice = false;
    try
        if isnumeric(val) || islogical(val)
            sz = size(val);
            if isvector(val) && numel(val)==m
                TD.(f) = val(idx);
                didSlice = true;
            elseif ismatrix(val)
                if sz(2)==m
                    TD.(f) = val(:, idx);
                    didSlice = true;
                elseif sz(1)==m
                    TD.(f) = val(idx, :);
                    didSlice = true;
                end
            end
        elseif iscell(val)
            sz = size(val);
            if isvector(val) && numel(val)==m
                TD.(f) = val(idx);
                didSlice = true;
            elseif ismatrix(val)
                if sz(2)==m
                    TD.(f) = val(:, idx);
                    didSlice = true;
                elseif sz(1)==m
                    TD.(f) = val(idx, :);
                    didSlice = true;
                end
            end
        elseif istable(val)
            if height(val)==m
                TD.(f) = val(idx, :);
                didSlice = true;
            end
        end
    end
end

```

```

        end
    end
catch
    % silently skip
    didSlice = false;
end

if didSlice
    sliced = sliced + 1;
    slicedFields{end+1} = f; %#ok<AGROW>
else
    skipped = skipped + 1;
end
end

% 4) Unified report
if ~isempty(slicedFields)
    listStr = strjoin(slicedFields, ', ');
else
    listStr = '(none)';
end
fprintf('[sliceTD] fields total=%d, sliced=%d, skipped=%d | sliced: %s\n', ...
        total, sliced, skipped, listStr);
end

function [W56, mu56] = buildWaveform56AndMean(TD)

W56 = [];
mu56 = [];

if ~isfield(TD, 'Allwaveform') || isempty(TD.Allwaveform) || ~isnumeric(TD.Allwaveform)
    return;
end

W = TD.Allwaveform;
sz = size(W);
% Normalize to [S x N], columns = events
if sz(1) < sz(2) && any(sz(1) == [56, 112])
    % Already SxN
    S = sz(1); N = sz(2);
elseif sz(2) < sz(1) && any(sz(2) == [56, 112])
    % Is NxS, transpose
    W = W';
    S = size(W,1);
    N = size(W,2);
else
    % Unrecognized
    return;
end

if N==0
    return;
end

if S == 56
    W56 = localStandardize56(W); % 56xN
elseif S == 112
    % Split into two wires
    ch1 = W(1:56, :);
    ch2 = W(57:112, :);

```

```

    % If eventInfo/mainCh available, select by main wire; else average two wires
    mainCh = [];
    if isfield(TD, 'ProcessInfo') && isfield(TD.ProcessInfo, 'eventInfo') &&
~isempty(TD.ProcessInfo.eventInfo)
        ei = TD.ProcessInfo.eventInfo;
        if isstruct(ei)
            if numel(ei) == size(W,2) && isfield(ei, 'mainCh')
                mainCh = arrayfun(@(x) x.mainCh, ei);
            end
        end
    end

    if ~isempty(mainCh)
        mainCh = reshape(mainCh, 1, []);
        W56 = zeros(56, N);
        use1 = (mainCh == 1);
        use2 = (mainCh == 2);
        if any(use1), W56(:, use1) = ch1(:, use1); end
        if any(use2), W56(:, use2) = ch2(:, use2); end
        W56 = localStandardize56(W56);
    else
        % No mainCh: average two wires to 56 points
        W56 = localStandardize56( (ch1 + ch2) ./ 2 );
    end
end
else
    % Other sample lengths not handled
    return;
end
end

if ~isempty(W56)
    mu56 = mean(W56, 2);
end
end
end

```

```
function W56s = localStandardize56(W56s)
```

```

    if isempty(W56s), return; end
    % Polarity (rough): if each column's minimum is positive, flip
    colMin = min(W56s, [], 1);
    if mean(colMin) > 0
        W56s = -W56s;
    end
    % Demean columns
    W56s = W56s - mean(W56s, 1);

    % Optional: normalize trough amplitude to 1 (for stable comparison)
    denom = max(abs(min(W56s, [], 1)), eps);
    W56s = W56s ./ denom;
end

```

```
function [m, wfOrient] = inferEventCountAndOrient(TD)
```

```

    m = [];
    wfOrient = '';

    if isfield(TD, 'Allwaveform') && ~isempty(TD.Allwaveform) && isnumeric(TD.Allwaveform)
        sz = size(TD.Allwaveform);
        if numel(sz)==2
            % Prefer common sample lengths
            if any(sz(1) == [56, 112])
                m = sz(2); wfOrient = 'Sxm';
                return;
            end
        end
    end

```

```

elseif any(sz(2) == [56, 112])
    m = sz(1); wfOrient = 'mxS';
    return;
else
    % If neither dimension matches common lengths, choose the one more like
samples (assume >=40)
    if sz(1) >= 40
        m = sz(2); wfOrient = 'Sxm';
        return;
    elseif sz(2) >= 40
        m = sz(1); wfOrient = 'mxS';
        return;
    end
end
end
end

% Fallback inference by other fields
cand = {'spike', 'Spike', 'spikes', 'SpikeTime', 'SpikeTimes', 'TimeStamps', 'Timestamps'};
for i = 1:numel(cand)
    f = cand{i};
    if isfield(TD, f) && ~isempty(TD.(f))
        v = TD.(f);
        if iscell(v) && isvector(v)
            m = numel(v); return;
        elseif isnumeric(v) || islogical(v)
            if isvector(v)
                m = numel(v); return;
            else
                sz = size(v);
                if sz(2) >= sz(1)
                    m = sz(2); return;
                else
                    m = sz(1); return;
                end
            end
        end
    end
end
end
end

function TD = clearEventAlignedAddons(TD)
% Clear common derived event-aligned fields to avoid residue with empty idx
may = {'waveform_good', 'meanWaveform_good'};
for i = 1:numel(may)
    f = may{i};
    if isfield(TD, f)
        TD.(f) = [];
    end
end
end

function s = toStr(x)
if ischar(x) || isstring(x)
    s = char(x);
elseif isnumeric(x)
    s = num2str(x);
else
    s = 'Unit';
end
end
end

```

```

function s = ensureStructFields(s, baseFields)
% Ensure s contains all fields in baseFields; fill missing with []; extra fields retained
    sFields = fieldnames(s);
    missing = setdiff(baseFields, sFields);
    for i = 1:numel(missing)
        s.(missing{i}) = [];
    end
    % Reorder fields to match baseFields (MATLAB requires same field set; order for safety)
    if ~isempty(setxor(fieldnames(s), baseFields))
        % If s has extra fields, create a slim copy containing only baseFields, then
reassign as needed
        core = orderfields(s, baseFields);
        s = core;
    else
        s = orderfields(s, baseFields);
    end
end
function [axList, shownMask] = preview_meanwaveforms(TD, titlePrefix, srcName, linkY)
    N = numel(TD);
    nRows = ceil(sqrt(N));
    nCols = ceil(N / nRows);
    f = figure('Color','w','Name',sprintf('%s (%s) - total %d', titlePrefix, srcName, N));
%#ok<NASGU>
    tl = tiledlayout(nRows, nCols, 'TileSpacing','compact','Padding','compact');
    axList = gobjects(1, N);
    shownMask = false(1, N);

    for i = 1:N
        nexttile;
        ax = gca;
        axList(i) = ax;

        mw = [];

        % 1) Prefer meanWaveform_good
        if isfield(TD, 'meanWaveform_good') && ~isempty(TD(i).meanWaveform_good)
            mw = TD(i).meanWaveform_good;

        % 2) Fallback to meanWaveform
        elseif isfield(TD, 'meanWaveform') && ~isempty(TD(i).meanWaveform)
            mw = TD(i).meanWaveform;

        % 3) Fallback to Allwaveform (consistent with original logic)
        elseif isfield(TD, 'Allwaveform') && ~isempty(TD(i).Allwaveform)
            W = TD(i).Allwaveform;
            if iscell(W), W = W{1}; end
            if isnumeric(W) && size(W,1)==112 && ~isempty(W)
                mw = [mean(W(1:56,:),2); mean(W(57:112,:),2)];
            elseif isnumeric(W) && size(W,1)==56 && ~isempty(W)
                mw = mean(W,2);
            end
        end
    end

    if isempty(mw)
        text(0.5,0.5,'No waveform','HorizontalAlignment','center', ...
            'VerticalAlignment','middle','Color',[0.7 0 0],'FontWeight','bold');
        axis off;
        title(sprintf('#%d', i), 'FontSize', 9);
        continue;
    end
end

```

```

hold on;
% Support vector or matrix: if row vector, transpose
if isrow(mw), mw = mw.'; end

% If mw is 112x1 (dual-wire concatenated), plot with original color scheme;
otherwise plot by column
if size(mw,1)==112 && size(mw,2)==1
    plot(mw(1:56), 'b-', 'LineWidth', 1.3);
    plot(mw(57:112), 'r-', 'LineWidth', 1.3);
elseif size(mw,1)==56 && size(mw,2)==2
    % If meanWaveform_good stored as 56x2 (two wires as columns)
    plot(mw(:,1), 'b-', 'LineWidth', 1.3);
    plot(mw(:,2), 'r-', 'LineWidth', 1.3);
else
    % Other cases: plot each column
    K = size(mw,2);
    cmap = lines(K);
    for k = 1:K
        plot(mw(:,k), 'Color', cmap(k,:), 'LineWidth', 1.3);
    end
    if K>1
        legend(arrayfun(@(k) sprintf('Ch%d',k), 1:K, 'UniformOutput', false), ...
            'Box','off','Location','bestoutside');
    end
end
grid on; hold off;

if isfield(TD,'neuronID') && ~isempty(TD(i).neuronID)
    title(sprintf('#%d | %s', i, string(TD(i).neuronID)), ...
        'Interpreter','none','FontSize',9);
else
    title(sprintf('#%d', i), 'FontSize',9);
end
xlabel('Samples'); ylabel('Amplitude');
shownMask(i) = true;
end

title(tl, sprintf('%s (%s) - total %d', titlePrefix, srcName, N), 'FontWeight','bold');

if linkY
    try, linkaxes(axList(isgraphics(axList)), 'y'); catch, end
end
end

function counts = count_in_intervals(win_starts, win_ends, spikes)

% Shapes and robustness
win_starts = win_starts(:);
win_ends   = win_ends(:);
spikes     = spikes(:);

if numel(win_starts) ~= numel(win_ends)
    error('win_starts and win_ends lengths do not match');
end
if ~issorted(spikes)
    spikes = sort(spikes, 'ascend');
end

% Handle invalid windows: end <= start treated as zero-length, count=0 (avoid numeric
issues)

```

```

bad = ~(isfinite(win_starts) & isfinite(win_ends)) | (win_ends <= win_starts);
win_ends(bad) = win_starts(bad);

% Use binary search to locate the first index with x >= boundary
idx_s = first_ge(spikes, win_starts);
idx_e = first_ge(spikes, win_ends);

counts = idx_e - idx_s;
end

function idx = first_ge(x, q)
%FIRST_GE Return the index of the first x >= q for each q; if none, return numel(x)+1
x = x(:);
q = q(:);
n = numel(x);
lo = ones(size(q)); % inclusive lower bound
hi = repmat(n+1, size(q)); % exclusive upper bound
while true
    mid = floor((lo + hi)/2);
    if all(hi - lo <= 1)
        break;
    end
    xv = x(mid);
    goRight = xv < q; % if x(mid) < q, answer is to the right
    lo(goRight) = mid(goRight);
    hi(~goRight) = mid(~goRight);
end
idx = hi;
end

function is_norm = local_test_normality(x, use_jb)
x = x(:);
x = x(~isnan(x));
if numel(x) < 8
    is_norm = false; return;
end
if use_jb
    try
        [h, ~] = jbtest(x, 0.05);
        is_norm = (h == 0);
        return;
    catch
        % continue with Lilliefors
    end
end
s = std(x);
if ~isfinite(s) || s == 0
    is_norm = false;
    return;
end
xz = (x - mean(x)) / s;
try
    [h, ~] = kstest(xz); % h=1 rejects normality
    is_norm = (h == 0);
catch
    is_norm = false;
end
end

function eqv = local_test_equal_variance(x, y, method)
x = x(:); y = y(:);

```

```

x = x(~isnan(x)); y = y(~isnan(y));
if numel(x) < 8 || numel(y) < 8
    eqv = false; return;
end
switch lower(method)
    case 'vartest2'
        try
            [h, ~] = vartest2(x, y, 'Alpha', 0.05);
            eqv = (h == 0);
        catch
            eqv = false;
        end
    otherwise
        % Simple Levene (median-based approximation)
        mx = median(x); my = median(y);
        zx = abs(x - mx); zy = abs(y - my);
        try
            p = ranksum(zx, zy, 'tail', 'both');
            eqv = (p > 0.05);
        catch
            eqv = false;
        end
end
end
function q = local_bh_fdr(p)
    p = p(:);
    p(~isfinite(p)) = 1;
    [ps, idx] = sort(p);
    m = numel(p);
    qtmp = (m./(1:m)') .* ps;
    qtmp = flipud(cummin(flipud(qtmp)));
    q = nan(size(p));
    q(idx) = min(1, qtmp);
end
function idx = parse_indices(strIn)
% Support spaces/commas/semicolons; support a:b and a:s:b ranges
strIn = char(strIn);
strIn = strrep(strIn, ';', ' ');
strIn = strrep(strIn, ',', ' ');
parts = strsplit(strtrim(strIn));
idx = [];
for k = 1:numel(parts)
    tok = strtrim(parts{k});
    if isempty(tok), continue; end
    if contains(tok, ':')
        nums = str2double(split(tok, ':'));
        nums = nums(~isnan(nums));
        if numel(nums) == 2
            a = nums(1); b = nums(2);
            if a <= b, seq = a:b; else, seq = a:-1:b; end
            idx = [idx, seq]; %#ok<AGROW>
        elseif numel(nums) == 3
            a = nums(1); s = nums(2); b = nums(3);
            if isfinite(a) && isfinite(s) && isfinite(b) && s ~= 0
                idx = [idx, a:s:b]; %#ok<AGROW>
            end
        end
    end
else
    v = str2double(tok);
    if ~isnan(v), idx = [idx, v]; end %#ok<AGROW>
end

```

```
        end
    end
    % De-duplicate while preserving order
    [~, ia] = unique(idx, 'stable');
    idx = idx(sort(ia));
end
```

```

% Step2: ChAT-Tagging and model construction
%% response latency

% Parameters for computing response latency

zThr = 2;           % significance threshold for increase; tunable 2~3
K = 1;             % minimum consecutive significant bins; 1 means not required; can
use 2 or 3
binSize_ms = 1;    % bin size = 1 ms
baseIdx = 1:50;    % baseline
stimIdx = 51:100;  % stimulation window; search only within this range

isUp = strcmpi(string({Data.Direction}), 'Up'); % compute only for the "Up" group
idxUp = find(isUp);

for k = 1:numel(idxUp)
    n = idxUp(k);
    X = Data(n).psth_tensor;      % 150 x 12000

    % Mean firing rate at each time point (across repeats/trials)
    fr_t = mean(X, 2, 'omitnan'); % 150 x 1

    % Baseline stats
    mu0 = mean(fr_t(baseIdx), 'omitnan');
    sd0 = std(fr_t(baseIdx), 0, 'omitnan');
    if ~isfinite(sd0) || sd0 == 0
        sd0 = max(1e-6, abs(mu0)*1e-3);
    end
    % z-score
    z = (fr_t - mu0) ./ sd0;

    % Decision only within the stimulation window
    sigMask = z > zThr;
    s = sigMask(stimIdx); % length 50

    if K <= 1
        relIdx = find(s, 1, 'first');
    else
        % Find the start index of a run of True of length >= K
        runLen = zeros(size(s));
        for i = 1:numel(s)
            if s(i)
                runLen(i) = (i==1) + (i>1)* (runLen(i-1)+1);
            else
                runLen(i) = 0;
            end
        end
        relIdx = find(runLen >= K, 1, 'first');
        if ~isempty(relIdx)
            relIdx = relIdx - K + 1; % start index of the segment (relative)
        end
    end

    if ~isempty(relIdx)
        absIdx = stimIdx(relIdx); % 51..100
        Data(n).responseTime_idx = absIdx; % global index
        Data(n).responseTime_fromStim_ms = (absIdx - stimIdx(1)) * binSize_ms; % relative
to stim onset
        Data(n).responseTime_z = z(absIdx);
    else
        Data(n).responseTime_idx = NaN;
    end
end

```

```

        Data(n).responseTime_fromStim_ms = NaN;
        Data(n).responseTime_z = NaN;
    end
end

%%
Fs = 40e3;           % Hz
baseline_win = 600; % s
dt_ms = 1e3 / Fs;

% Select features for clustering (editable)
features_to_use =
{'PTD_ms', 'W_FWHM_ms', 'amp_asymmetry', 'slope_ratio', 'FR_baseline_Hz', 'ptp_amp'};

% Standardization and PCA
do_zscore = true;
pca_var_explained = 0.95; % cumulative variance to retain
pca_min_comp = 2;        % minimum number of PCs to retain
pca_max_comp = 6;        % maximum number of PCs to retain

% K-means parameters
K = 2;
kmeans_reps = 100;
kmeans_maxIter = 2000;
kmeans_distance = 'sqeuclidean';
seed = 42;

% ===== Buffering policy (switch + params) =====
buffer.enable = true; % false: no buffer; true: enable buffer
% Mode A: ratio of two-cluster distances (recommended)
buffer.use_ratio = true; % use dmin/dmax to decide "extreme"
buffer.ratio_thresh = 0.6; % dmin/dmax < 0.6 => "extreme" (kept); otherwise Ambiguous
% Mode B: per-cluster distance quantiles (can be combined with A)
buffer.use_quantile = false; % use within-cluster dmin quantile threshold
buffer.quantile_thresh = 0.6; % keep closest 60% (small dmin) within each cluster; else
Ambiguous
% Combine logic
combine_logic = 'AND'; % 'AND' / 'OR'

% Output and visualization
save_csv = false;
csv_name = 'pca_kmeans_buffer.csv';
do_plot = true;

% ===== Basic checks =====
if ~exist('Data', 'var') || isempty(Data)
    error('Variable Data not detected. Please provide a Data struct array containing unit
data in the workspace.');
```

```

end

% ===== Feature computation (valley-then-peak convention) =====
N = numel(Data);
unit_id = (1:N).';

% Pre-allocate Direction / mu_pre / mu_dur and read from Data
% Direction may be numeric or char/string:
% - If all numeric -> numeric column (missing as NaN)
% - If any non-numeric -> convert to string column (missing as "")
isDirectionNumeric = true;
for i = 1:N
    if isfield(Data(i), 'Direction') && ~isempty(Data(i).Direction)

```

```

        if ~isnumeric(Data(i).Direction)
            isDirectionNumeric = false; break;
        end
    end
end
if isDirectionNumeric
    Direction = nan(N,1);
else
    Direction = strings(N,1);
end
mu_pre = nan(N,1);
mu_dur = nan(N,1);

% Missing counts
miss_dir = 0; miss_pre = 0; miss_dur = 0;

FR_baseline_Hz = nan(N,1);
PTD_ms = nan(N,1);
W_FWHM_ms = nan(N,1);
slope_ratio = nan(N,1);
amp_asymmetry = nan(N,1);
neg_amp = nan(N,1);
pos_amp = nan(N,1);
ptp_amp = nan(N,1);

for i = 1:N
    % Read Direction / mu_pre / mu_dur
    if isfield(Data(i), 'Direction') && ~isempty(Data(i).Direction)
        if isDirectionNumeric
            try
                Direction(i) = double(Data(i).Direction);
            catch
                % Fallback to string column when mixed types
                if isnumeric(Direction)
                    Direction_str = strings(N,1);
                    for k = 1:i-1
                        Direction_str(k) = string(Direction(k));
                    end
                    Direction = Direction_str;
                    isDirectionNumeric = false;
                end
                Direction(i) = string(Data(i).Direction);
            end
        else
            Direction(i) = string(Data(i).Direction);
        end
    else
        if isDirectionNumeric
            Direction(i) = NaN; miss_dir = miss_dir + 1;
        else
            Direction(i) = ''; miss_dir = miss_dir + 1;
        end
    end

    if isfield(Data(i), 'mu_pre') && ~isempty(Data(i).mu_pre)
        mu_pre(i) = double(Data(i).mu_pre);
    else
        mu_pre(i) = NaN; miss_pre = miss_pre + 1;
    end

    if isfield(Data(i), 'mu_dur') && ~isempty(Data(i).mu_dur)

```

```

    mu_dur(i) = double(Data(i).mu_dur);
else
    mu_dur(i) = NaN; miss_dur = miss_dur + 1;
end

% Baseline firing rate
if ~isfield(Data(i), 'stim') || ~isfield(Data(i).stim, 't_on') ||
isempty(Data(i).stim.t_on)
    error('Data(%d).stim.t_on is missing or empty.', i);
end
t0 = Data(i).stim.t_on(1,1);
spk = [];
if isfield(Data(i), 'spike') && ~isempty(Data(i).spike), spk = Data(i).spike(:); end
if ~isempty(spk)
    inwin = spk >= (t0 - baseline_win) & spk < t0;
    FR_baseline_Hz(i) = sum(inwin) / baseline_win;
else
    FR_baseline_Hz(i) = 0;
end

% Waveform features (valley-then-peak)
if isfield(Data(i), 'meanWaveform_good') && ~isempty(Data(i).meanWaveform_good)
    wf = Data(i).meanWaveform_good(:);
    wf = wf - mean(wf, 'omitnan');
    Nw = numel(wf);

    [~, imin0] = min(wf);
    [~, imax0] = max(wf);

    wf_use = wf; imin = imin0; imax = imax0;

    if imax <= imin
        wf_try = -wf;
        [~, imin1] = min(wf_try);
        [~, imax1] = max(wf_try);
        if imax1 > imin1
            wf_use = wf_try; imin = imin1; imax = imax1;
        else
            win = min(20, Nw - imin);
            if win >= 2
                [~, rel] = max(wf_use(imin+1:imin+win));
                imax = imin + rel;
            end
        end
    end
end

% PTD
if imax > imin
    PTD_ms(i) = (imax - imin) * dt_ms;
else
    PTD_ms(i) = NaN;
end

% FWHM around the valley
try
    mn = wf_use(imin);
    half = mn / 2;
    iL = imin;
    while iL > 1 && wf_use(iL) < half, iL = iL - 1; end
    iR = imin;
    while iR < Nw && wf_use(iR) < half, iR = iR + 1; end
end

```

```

        if iR > iL
            W_FWHM_ms(i) = (iR - iL) * dt_ms;
        else
            W_FWHM_ms(i) = NaN;
        end
    catch
        W_FWHM_ms(i) = NaN;
    end

    % Amplitude-related
    mn_use = min(wf_use);
    mx_use = max(wf_use);
    neg_amp(i) = -min(wf_use);
    pos_amp(i) = max(wf_use);
    ptp_amp(i) = pos_amp(i) + neg_amp(i);
    denom = (abs(mx_use) + abs(mn_use));
    if denom > 0
        amp_asymmetry(i) = (abs(mx_use) - abs(mn_use)) / denom;
    else
        amp_asymmetry(i) = NaN;
    end

    % Slope ratio
    d = diff(wf_use) * Fs;
    preMaxRise = NaN; postMaxFall = NaN;
    if imax > 1, preMaxRise = max(d(1:max(imax-1,1))); end
    if imax < Nw, postMaxFall = -min(d(min(imax, numel(d)):end)); end
    if isfinite(preMaxRise) && isfinite(postMaxFall) && postMaxFall > 0
        slope_ratio(i) = abs(preMaxRise) / postMaxFall;
    else
        slope_ratio(i) = NaN;
    end
end
else
    PTD_ms(i)          = NaN;
    W_FWHM_ms(i)       = NaN;
    slope_ratio(i)     = NaN;
    amp_asymmetry(i)   = NaN;
    neg_amp(i)         = NaN;
    pos_amp(i)         = NaN;
    ptp_amp(i)         = NaN;
end
end

% Summary feature table
featuresTbl = table(unit_id, FR_baseline_Hz, PTD_ms, W_FWHM_ms, slope_ratio, amp_asymmetry,
neg_amp, pos_amp, ptp_amp);

% Append Direction / mu_pre / mu_dur to the table (preserve column types)
if isDirectionNumeric
    featuresTbl.Direction = Direction; % double column
else
    featuresTbl.Direction = string(Direction); % string column
end
featuresTbl.mu_pre = mu_pre;
featuresTbl.mu_dur = mu_dur;

if miss_dir>0 || miss_pre>0 || miss_dur>0
    fprintf('Missing counts -> Direction: %d, mu_pre: %d, mu_dur: %d\n', miss_dir,
miss_pre, miss_dur);
end

```

```

% ===== Build feature matrix =====
X = featuresTbl{:, features_to_use};

% Impute missing values (column median)
for j = 1:size(X,2)
    col = X(:,j);
    m = median(col(~isnan(col)));
    if isempty(m) || isnan(m), m = 0; end
    col(isnan(col)) = m;
    X(:,j) = col;
end

% Standardize
if do_zscore
    mu = mean(X,1);
    sg = std(X,[],1); sg(sg==0) = 1;
    Xz = (X - mu) ./ sg;
else
    Xz = X;
end

% PCA (retain specified variance proportion)
[coeff, score, latent, ~, explained] = pca(Xz, 'Centered', false);
cumExpl = cumsum(explained)/100;
nComp = find(cumExpl >= pca_var_explained, 1, 'first');
if isempty(nComp), nComp = size(score,2); end
nComp = max(pca_min_comp, min([nComp, pca_max_comp, size(score,2)]));
PC = score(:,1:nComp);

fprintf('PCA: retained %d PCs, cumulative variance explained %.1f%%\n', nComp,
100*cumExpl(nComp));

% ===== K-means clustering =====
rng(seed);
[idx, C] = kmeans(PC, K, ...
    'Distance', kmeans_distance, ...
    'Replicates', kmeans_reps, ...
    'MaxIter', kmeans_maxIter, ...
    'OnlinePhase', 'off', ...
    'Display', 'final');

% ===== Hard binary labels =====
D = pdist2(PC, C, 'euclidean'); % N x 2
[~, lab] = min(D, [], 2); % lab ∈ {1,2}
dmin = min(D, [], 2);
dmax = max(D, [], 2);
ratio = dmin ./ max(dmax, eps);

% Initial labels (no buffer)
featuresTbl.cluster_kmeans = lab;
featuresTbl.dmin = dmin;
featuresTbl.dmax = dmax;
featuresTbl.ratio = ratio;

% ===== Buffering (true/false switch) =====
if buffer.enable
    keep_by_ratio = true(size(lab));
    keep_by_quant = true(size(lab));

    if buffer.use_ratio
        keep_by_ratio = ratio < buffer.ratio_thresh;
    end
end

```

```

end

if buffer.use_quantile
    q1 = NaN; q2 = NaN;
    if any(lab==1), q1 = quantile(dmin(lab==1), buffer.quantile_thresh); end
    if any(lab==2), q2 = quantile(dmin(lab==2), buffer.quantile_thresh); end
    keep_by_quant = false(size(lab));
    keep_by_quant(lab==1) = dmin(lab==1) <= q1;
    keep_by_quant(lab==2) = dmin(lab==2) <= q2;
end

switch upper(string(combine_logic))
    case "AND"
        keep_final = keep_by_ratio & keep_by_quant;
    case "OR"
        keep_final = keep_by_ratio | keep_by_quant;
    otherwise
        warning('Unknown combine_logic=%s, falling back to AND.',
string(combine_logic));
        keep_final = keep_by_ratio & keep_by_quant;
end

lab_buf = lab;
lab_buf(~keep_final) = 0; % 0 = Ambiguous
else
    lab_buf = lab;
end

featuresTbl.cluster_buf = lab_buf;

% ===== Map to PPN / PIN =====
ptd1 = mean(PTD_ms(lab==1), 'omitnan');
ptd2 = mean(PTD_ms(lab==2), 'omitnan');

if ptd1 >= ptd2
    map.k1 = "PPN";
    map.k2 = "PIN";
else
    map.k1 = "PIN";
    map.k2 = "PPN";
end

label_pp_hard = strings(N,1);
label_pp_hard(lab==1) = map.k1;
label_pp_hard(lab==2) = map.k2;

label_pp_soft = strings(N,1);
label_pp_soft(lab_buf==1) = map.k1;
label_pp_soft(lab_buf==2) = map.k2;
label_pp_soft(lab_buf==0) = "Ambiguous";

featuresTbl.label1 = label_pp_soft; % with buffer
featuresTbl.label2 = label_pp_hard; % hard labels
featuresTbl.label_binary = label_pp_hard;

nPPN_soft = sum(featuresTbl.label1=="PPN");
nPIN_soft = sum(featuresTbl.label1=="PIN");
nAmb      = sum(featuresTbl.label1=="Ambiguous");
nPPN_hard = sum(featuresTbl.label2=="PPN");
nPIN_hard = sum(featuresTbl.label2=="PIN");

```

```

fprintf('Semantic mapping: K1 -> %s, K2 -> %s | Hard: PPN=%d, PIN=%d | With buffer: PPN=%d,
PIN=%d, Ambiguous=%d (N=%d)\n', ...
    map.k1, map.k2, nPPN_hard, nPIN_hard, nPPN_soft, nPIN_soft, nAmb, N);

% Optional save
if save_csv
    writetable(featuresTbl, csv_name);
    fprintf('Saved: %s\n', csv_name);
end

% ===== Visualization =====
if do_plot
    try
        figure('Color','w','Name','PCA + K-means (two clusters, with buffer)');
        if size(PC,2) >= 2
            % Subplot 1: PCA space (hard labels)
            g1 = (lab==1); g2 = (lab==2);
            subplot(2,2,1);
            hold on;
            scatter(PC(g1,1), PC(g1,2), 20, [0.2 0.5 1.0], 'filled');
            scatter(PC(g2,1), PC(g2,2), 20, [1.0 0.3 0.2], 'filled');
            scatter(C(:,1), C(:,2), 80, 'k', 'pentagram', 'filled');
            legend({'K1','K2','Centers'}, 'Location','best');
            xlabel('PC1'); ylabel('PC2'); title('PCA space (hard)'); grid on; axis equal;
            hold off;

            % Subplot 2: PCA space (with buffer)
            subplot(2,2,2);
            hold on;
            keepK1 = (lab_buf==1); keepK2 = (lab_buf==2); amb = (lab_buf==0);
            scatter(PC(keepK1,1), PC(keepK1,2), 20, [0.2 0.5 1.0], 'filled');
            scatter(PC(keepK2,1), PC(keepK2,2), 20, [1.0 0.3 0.2], 'filled');
            if any(amb)
                scatter(PC(amb,1), PC(amb,2), 16, [0.5 0.5 0.5], 'filled',
'MarkerFaceAlpha', 0.6);
            end
            scatter(C(:,1), C(:,2), 80, 'k', 'pentagram', 'filled');
            legend({'K1 kept','K2 kept','Ambiguous','Centers'}, 'Location','best');
            xlabel('PC1'); ylabel('PC2'); title(sprintf('PCA space (buffer=%s)',
string(buffer.enable)));
            grid on; axis equal;
            hold off;

            % Subplot 3: ratio histogram
            subplot(2,2,3);
            hold on;
            histogram(ratio(lab==1), 'BinWidth',0.05,
'DisplayStyle','stairs','LineWidth',1.5, 'EdgeColor',[0.2 0.5 1.0]);
            histogram(ratio(lab==2), 'BinWidth',0.05,
'DisplayStyle','stairs','LineWidth',1.5, 'EdgeColor',[1.0 0.3 0.2]);
            if buffer.use_ratio
                xline(buffer.ratio_thresh, '--k', 'ratio\_thresh');
            end
            xlabel('d_{min}/d_{max}'); ylabel('Count'); grid on; title('Softness (ratio)');
            legend({'K1','K2'});
            hold off;

            % Subplot 4: pie chart (final labels)
            subplot(2,2,4);
            counts = [sum(featuresTbl.label1=="PPN"), sum(featuresTbl.label1=="PIN"),
sum(featuresTbl.label1=="Ambiguous")];

```

```

    labels = ["PPN","PIN","Ambiguous"] + " (" + string(counts) + ")";
    pie(counts, labels);
    title('Final labels (label1)');
else
    % If only 1 PC dimension retained, draw line plots
    subplot(1,2,1); hold on;
    scatter(PC(lab==1,1), zeros(sum(lab==1),1), 20, [0.2 0.5 1.0], 'filled');
    scatter(PC(lab==2,1), zeros(sum(lab==2),1), 20, [1.0 0.3 0.2], 'filled');
    xlabel('PC1'); title('Hard labels'); grid on; hold off;

    subplot(1,2,2); hold on;
    amb = (lab_buf==0);
    scatter(PC(lab_buf==1,1), zeros(sum(lab_buf==1),1), 20, [0.2 0.5 1.0],
'filled');
    scatter(PC(lab_buf==2,1), zeros(sum(lab_buf==2),1), 20, [1.0 0.3 0.2],
'filled');
    if any(amb)
        scatter(PC(amb,1), zeros(sum(amb),1), 16, [0.5 0.5 0.5], 'filled',
'MarkerFaceAlpha', 0.6);
    end
    xlabel('PC1'); title('Buffer labels'); grid on; hold off;
end
catch ME
    warning('Plotting failed: %s', ME.message);
end
end

% ===== Tips =====
% - Direction/mu_pre/mu_dur have been appended to featuresTbl and will be saved with CSV.
% - If Direction contains both numeric and text, it will be auto-converted to a string
column.
% - Disable buffer: buffer.enable = false. Then label1==label2 (no Ambiguous).
% - Adjust buffer strength: ratio_thresh / quantile_thresh + combine_logic.
% - Semantic mapping: in hard labels, the cluster with larger mean PTD -> PPN; the other ->
PIN.

%%

N = min(numel(Data), height(featuresTbl));
if ~ismember('response_latency_ms', featuresTbl.Properties.VariableNames)
    featuresTbl.response_latency_ms = nan(height(featuresTbl),1);
end
for n = 1:N
    if isfield(Data, 'responseTime_fromStim_ms') &&
~isempty(Data(n).responseTime_fromStim_ms)
        featuresTbl.response_latency_ms(n) = double(Data(n).responseTime_fromStim_ms);
    else
        featuresTbl.response_latency_ms(n) = NaN;
    end
end

%% 1) Define gold standard: PIN-ChAT
assert(istable(featuresTbl), 'featuresTbl must be a table');
reqCols = {'response_latency_ms','label2', ...

'PTD_ms','W_FWHM_ms','slope_ratio','amp_asymmetry','neg_amp','pos_amp','ptp_amp'};
miss = reqCols(~ismember(reqCols, featuresTbl.Properties.VariableNames));
assert(isempty(miss), 'Missing columns: %s', strjoin(miss, ', '));

```

```

T = featuresTbl;

lat = T.response_latency_ms;
lab2 = string(T.label2);
isPIN = strcmpi(lab2, 'PIN');
isPIN_ChAT = ~isnan(lat) & (lat < 15) & isPIN;
T.isPIN_ChAT = isPIN_ChAT;

fprintf('Total samples: %d\n', height(T));
fprintf('PIN-ChAT positives: %d (%.1f%%)\n', sum(isPIN_ChAT), 100*mean(isPIN_ChAT));

if sum(isPIN_ChAT) < 5
    warning('Very few positive samples; evaluation may be unstable. Consider enlarging data
or relaxing criteria.');
```

```

end

y = double(isPIN_ChAT);

if numel(unique(y)) < 2
    error('Only one class present; cannot train. Please check if there are samples with
label2==PIN and latency<15ms.');
```

```

end

%% 2) Feature preparation (waveform geometry)
waveCols =
{'PTD_ms', 'W_FWHM_ms', 'slope_ratio', 'amp_asymmetry', 'neg_amp', 'pos_amp', 'ptp_amp'};
X_raw = T{:, waveCols};

% Missing value imputation (column median)
for j = 1:size(X_raw,2)
    col = X_raw(:,j);
    if any(isnan(col))
        med = median(col(~isnan(col)));
        if isempty(med) || isnan(med), med = 0; end
        col(isnan(col)) = med;
        X_raw(:,j) = col;
    end
end

% Standardize
mu_base = mean(X_raw,1);
sd_base = std(X_raw,[],1); sd_base(sd_base==0) = 1;
X = (X_raw - mu_base) ./ sd_base;

%% 3) Cross-validated training and evaluation (logistic regression)
K = min(5, max(2, sum(y))); % at least 2 folds; reduce folds if positives are too few
cv = cvpartition(y, 'KFold', K);
prob_oof = nan(numel(y),1);

for k = 1:K
    tr = training(cv,k); te = test(cv,k);
    mdl_k = fitclinear(X(tr,:), y(tr), 'Learner','logistic', 'ClassNames',[0 1]);
    [~, S] = predict(mdl_k, X(te,:));
    prob_oof(te) = 1 ./ (1 + exp(-S(:,2)));
end

% AUC and threshold
[FPR, TPR, TH, AUC] = perfcurve(y, prob_oof, 1);
[~, idxJ] = max(TPR - FPR);
th_opt = TH(idxJ);

```

```

fprintf('[CV] AUC (PIN-ChAT, latency<15ms) = %.3f\n', AUC);
fprintf('Recommended threshold (Youden J): %.3f\n', th_opt);

%% 4) Refit final model on full data and save
mdl_all = fitclinear(X, y, 'Learner','logistic', 'ClassNames',[0 1]);
[~, S_all] = predict(mdl_all, X);
p_fit = 1 ./ (1 + exp(-S_all(:,2)));

pin15_model = struct();
pin15_model.mdl = mdl_all;
pin15_model.waveCols = waveCols;
pin15_model.mu_base = mu_base;
pin15_model.sd_base = sd_base;
pin15_model.th_opt = th_opt;

save('pin_chat_15ms_model.mat','pin15_model');
fprintf('Model saved to pin_chat_15ms_model.mat\n');

%% 5) Visualization QC
try
    figure('Color','w','Name','PIN-ChAT @ <15ms - QC','Position',[100 100 1200 450]);

    subplot(1,3,1);
    histogram(prob_oof(~logical(y)), 0:0.02:1, 'FaceColor',[0.7 0.7 0.7],
'EdgeColor','none'); hold on;
    histogram(prob_oof(logical(y)), 0:0.02:1, 'FaceColor',[0.2 0.6 1], 'EdgeColor','none');
    xline(th_opt,'r--','LineWidth',1.5);
    xlabel('p_{PIN-ChAT} (CV)'); ylabel('count');
    title(sprintf('Probability distribution (AUC=%.3f)', AUC));
    legend({'Negative','PIN-ChAT','Threshold'],'Location','best');

    subplot(1,3,2);
    plot(FPR, TPR, 'b-', 'LineWidth',1.5); hold on;
    plot([0 1],[0 1],'k--');
    plot(FPR(idxJ), TPR(idxJ), 'ro', 'MarkerFaceColor','r');
    xlabel('FPR'); ylabel('TPR'); title('ROC & Youden J');

    subplot(1,3,3);
    boxchart(categorical(y), prob_oof);
    xlabel('isPIN-ChAT (0/1)'); ylabel('p (CV)');
    title('Class-probability comparison');
catch ME
    warning('Plotting failed: %s', ME.message);
end

```